

Study	1) Recruitment method; 2) Setting *	Inclusion/exclusion criteria	Sample: N. approached/ n in database vs n eligible to participate vs n consented to participate/n included in study? †	1)Attrition rate/Reasons for withdrawal. ‡ 2) Missing data	Population age: Mean (SD) [Range] §	Patient baseline/previous health characteristics	1) Pre-existing restorative material. 2) Condition requiring restoration	Total duration of study [Duration of follow up] ¶	PROGRESS+ characteristics at baseline **
<i>Dental professionals</i>									
Duplinsky 2012 ¹	1) Health status data using insurance utilization data. Authors given permission by participants to access pharmacy claims data, medical claims data, and biographical data. PBM and TPA contacted to obtain data. Population data base developed by PBM using social security number identifier. Data used in this study reflect a combination of census information, raw prescription claims, NBC information,	<u>Inclusion:</u> Random representative sample male GPD + controls: matched to 1) geographic area; 2) PBM 3) many had same physician; 4) same prescription drug card and card restrictions 5) sex, 6) age 7) only claims for drugs prescribed by a physician used 8) control group typical utilization history (paid loss ratio) of 200,000 insured. <u>GPDs. Exclusion:</u> 1) self-prescribing dentists (n=15), 2) female: (n=29)	Adults. 2175 total dentists in geographical area Vs. 1549 GPD in this area. Total 200,000 insured. Random representative sample of dentists: 600 (only GPDs for analysis (n=440)) + controls from matched group 1109 adults. Vs. Final sample: 396 dentists, 708 controls	1)NA 2)NR	Average age GPD and controls: 49yrs (NR) [NR]	NR	1)NR 2)NR	Drug utilization data collected from Nov-1997 to Feb-1999 (2-years) [NR]	Gender/sex. Male: 100% Occupation. Study vs Geographical area of study, n (%). GPD: 440 (73.3%) vs 1549 (71.2%).

	<p>authors own drug categories, dentist specialty information and miscellaneous code and description tables e.g. gender description and age groups tables. Data transmitted to authors for analysis with social security number identifier modified by altering algorithm, protecting anonymity.</p> <p>2)NA.</p>								
Franzblau 2012 ²	<p>1)Subjects who volunteered to attend ≥ 1 health screenings conducted during the annual ADA conferences (1997–2006)</p> <p>2) ADA conferences.</p>	<p>Dentists. Inclusion: at least 1) one urine Hg value, 2) one set of nerve conduction tests 3) completed health questionnaire performed on same day. Exclusion: 1) all observations of subjects who self-reported DM and/or RA at any time point (n=111), 2) history of CTS excluded from analyses related to the median nerve,</p>	<p>Adults.2767 study participants + 3772 observations available vs. 2656 subjects eligible (after exclusion) with 3594 observations vs. NA</p>	<p>1)NR.</p> <p>2)For BMI: Many did not report height and/or weight on the questionnaire. If a subject had observations in other years, missing BMI value replaced with an average BMI over all the years with available data for that subject</p>	<p>49.6 years (at time of first visit) (10.3) [21-85]</p>	<p>History of CTS: 8% History of DM and RA: see inclusion and exclusion criteria. BMI (kg/m²) at first time visit (mean): 26.4 (3.4) [16.9-46.9]</p>	<p>1)Amalgams placed and removed on a weekly basis</p> <p>2)NR.</p>	<p>Data collected over 10 years [NA].</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Earliest observation only (without exclusion criteria applied) (n = 2767). With imputed BMI – Male: 2123 (77%); Female 644 (23%).</p> <p>Including all observations (n = 3771). With Imputed BMI – Male: 2950 (78%);</p>

		but not the ulnar nerve, 3) hand temperature <27.5 °C or > 38.0 °C excluded from all analyses.		(n = 110 subjects). If a subject had no other observations with available height and/or weight data, BMI values imputed based on average BMI for subjects of similar gender/ age in study sample (n = 770 subjects with 838 observations). <u>For age/gender:</u> 60 observations missing values for age but determined for 46 of these after examining info. from the same subject in different years. Subjects with missing age or gender were excluded from analyses.					Female: 821 (22%). Earliest observation only (n = 1997). No Imputed BMI - Male 1600 (80%); Female 397 (20%). Including all observations (n = 2993) No Imputed BMI - Male 2383 (81%); Female 550 (19%). Occupation: Dentists, dental assistants and dental hygienists
Heratizadeh 2018 ³	1)Data from 2001-2015 obtained from the central IVDK database, which includes patch test results from all patients tested in	Study group <u>Inclusion:</u> dental technicians patch tested in IVDK and diagnosed with occupational contact dermatitis. Controls. Inclusion: Dental technicians without occupational contact dermatitis.	Adults. 163 261 patients patch tested in IVDK vs 399 eligible as DTs vs 350 included in final analysis: 226 OCD; 142 No OCD. (49 of eligible DTs had no clear diagnosis or info. on work)	1)NA 2)NR	Mean NR. Age ≥ 40yrs, n (%) - Study group: 117 (51.8) vs. Control group: 65 (52.4%)	Study group vs control group, n (%), p-value: <u>Atopic dermatitis (past/present):</u> 67 (29.6) vs 40 (32.3), 0.61 <u>Hand dermatitis:</u> 200 (88.5) vs 42 (33.9), <0.0001 <u>Leg dermatitis:</u> 0 (0.0) vs 3 (2.4),	1)NR 2)NA	Retrospective study using data from 2001-2015 [NA]	Gender/sex. Study vs control group, n (%)- Male: 105 (46.5%) vs 39 (31.5%) p=0.006 Occupation. All participants were DTs.

	participating IVDK centres. 2)NA.					0.044 <u>Face dermatitis:</u> 12 (5.3) vs 28 (22.6), <0.0001			
Hilt 2009 ⁴	1) Dental assistants: Asked public dental health care system and some dentists in private practice in 3 counties in Central Norway for lists of all employees who had ever worked as dental assistants. All the identified women were invited to participate in the study by filling questionnaire and answering a second questionnaire relating work career and working conditions in dental health care system. Submit both questionnaires in prepaid envelope.	Dental assistants. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Female dental assistants, 1) 69yrs ≥ Controls. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) matched for county, with categorical matching for age within 5-year group. 2) not to have been engaged in dental health care, 3) have worked outside their homes for more than 5 years after 1960. Both groups- <u>Exclusion:</u> age>69yrs	Adults. DA: 1224 candidates all sent survey vs. 608 eligible + included in analysis. Control: 1062 approached vs. 456 eligible + participated (31 excluded) so 425 included in analysis.	1)NR 2) Dental assistants (n=608) vs control (n=425). N of participants missing data for- <u>Mood score:</u> 3 vs 4. <u>Memory:</u> 3 vs 0, <u>Concentration:</u> 5 vs 2. <u>Sleep disturbance:</u> 4 vs 2. <u>Neurological symptoms:</u> 0 vs 3. <u>Psychosomatic symptoms:</u> 4 vs 4. <u>Fatigue:</u> 3 vs 3.	Dental assistants: 51.7 years (9.7) [NR]. Controls: 49.4 years (10.8) [NR].	Dental assistant's vs controls, % of participants. <u>Current diseases-</u> DM: 2.0 vs 3.5. Arterial hypertension: 13.3 vs 13.4. <u>Smoking habits-</u> Yes, daily: 18.4 vs 21.2. Yes, now and then: 9.3 vs 8.0. Ex-smoker: 33.2 vs 26.9. Never smoker: 39.0 vs 43.9. <u>Use of alcohol last year:</u> Yes, every week: 25.6 vs 23.3. Yes, more seldom: 63.5 vs 61.8. No use: 10.9 vs 14.9. Used to use more in earlier life: 7.5 vs 13.	Dental assistants vs controls (% of participants): <u>Amalgam in own teeth:</u> 92.1 vs. 89.1. <u>Had major removal of amalgam fillings:</u> 23.5 vs. 26.2. <u>N of surfaces, mean (SD):</u> 8.2 (4.3) vs. 9.0 (4.7). Of 559 who provided date on when started to work in dental health care system: 233 (41.7%), confirmed used copper amalgam in work, most before 1990, 6 later than that. Out of 469 who answered, 44 (4.3%) reported having experienced serious spills of Hg in working environment at least once during career. 2) NR.	NR [NA]	Gender/sex. Female: 100%. Occupation. Dental assistants. Education. Formal education (Dental Assistants vs Control, %)- Elementary: 20.2 vs 18.5. College/vocational training: 66.8 vs 32.4. University: 12.9 vs 39.1.

	<p>Control group: randomly chosen by Norwegian Central Bureau of Statistics. All asked to participate via postal survey.</p> <p>2) NA. See recruitment method.</p>								
Hilt 2011 ⁵	<p>1)Dentists. Asked offices of dental health care authorities in 3 counties (More and Romsdal, South-Trondelag, North-Trondelag) in Central Norway for lists of all dental personnel known to have worked in region, to identify dentists. Dental workers invited to participate by postal questionnaire.</p> <p>Control group randomly chosen by</p>	<p>Dental workers. <u>Inclusion: dentists.</u></p> <p>Controls. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) matched for county with categorical matching for sex and age within 5-year groups 2) <70yrs 3) not been engaged in dental health care 4) have worked outside their homes for > five yrs after 1960 5) For valid comparison with dentists, only control persons with university degree included.</p>	<p>Adults. Dentists: 2,247 dental workers identified- 790 dentists invited to participate (452 responded (57.2%)) vs. 406 eligible + included in analysis. Control group: 1500 identified (690 participated) vs. 583 eligible vs. 217 included in analysis</p>	<p>1)NR.</p> <p>2)Dentists (n=406) vs Control (n=217). N of participants missing data for: <u>Mood score:</u> 2 vs 2. <u>Memory:</u> 1 vs 0. <u>Concentration:</u> 3 vs 0. <u>Sleep disturbance:</u> 3 vs 0. <u>Neurological:</u> 3 vs 1. <u>Psychosomatic:</u> 4 vs 3. <u>Fatigue:</u> 4 vs 0</p> <p>Only 118 dentists had results of previous urine Hg measurements available.</p>	<p>Dentists: 52.1 years (12.4) NR], Controls: 48.4 years (10.8) [NR]</p>	<p>Dentists vs controls, % of participants. <u>Smoking habits:</u> _Yes, daily: 6 vs 13 Yes, now and then: 5 vs 7.4 Ex-smoker: 24.3 vs 27.8 Never smoker: 64.7 vs 51.8 <u>Use of alcohol last year:</u> Yes, every week: 49.1 vs 33.8 Yes, more seldom: 43.4 vs 53.7 No use: 7.4 vs 12.5 <u>Current diseases:</u> DM: 1.2 vs 1.8 Arterial hypertension: 11.8 vs 9.7.</p>	<p>1) Dentists vs controls: <u>Amalgam in own teeth, %-</u> Yes: 83.5 vs 91.7 <u>Number of surfaces, mean (SD)-</u> 8.7 (5.2) vs 9.8 (5.2).</p> <p>2)NA</p>	<p>NR [NA]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Dentists vs controls, %. Female: 42.6 vs 76.</p> <p>Occupation. Dentists. Years of professional work, Mean (SD) (Dentists vs controls): 26.3 (12.6) vs 24.0 (10.5)</p>

	Norwegian Central Bureau of Statistics. 2)NA. See recruitment method.								
Jones 2007 ⁶	1) Exposed group: Total population sampling method used on 4-year cohort (1968–1971) of graduates from the Willis Street School for Dental Nurses, Wellington, NZ. Control group: sisters or friends of exposed group. 2)See Recruitment method.	Exposed group. <u>Inclusion:</u> Ex-School Dental Service employees in a Hg-exposed group. Controls. <u>Inclusion:</u> Matched on age, alcohol/ tobacco intake and self-reported state of health.	Adults. Exposed group: 115 dental nurses approached vs NR vs 43 participated (n=1 excluded from analysis due to confounding TBI) Controls: NR vs NR vs 32 participated	1)Non-completion rate (exposed vs control, %): 0.03% vs 0.02%. 2) Reproductive data missing from exposed group: n=2 (chose not to have children).	Exposed group: 52.19 years (1.20) [NR]. Control group: 51.39 years (4.54) [NR]	Exposed vs control group, mean (SD). <u>Alcohol intake-</u> (4-point scale: 0=none, 3=very frequent): 1.76 (0.95) vs 1.78 (0.75). <u>Tobacco smoking-</u> (4-point scale: 0=none, 3=very frequent): 0.32(0.82) vs 0.30 (0.87) <u>State of health-</u> (1=poor to 7 excellent): 6.05(0.83) vs 6.03(0.81).	1)NR 2)NR.	Participants sampled over four-year cohort (1968–1971) [NA]	Gender/sex. Female: 100% Occupation: Dental nurses
Thygesen 2011 ⁷	1) Obtained info. from several registers (link individual data through unique ID number (CPR number)): <u>1. ATP:</u> established 1964 as compulsory	<u>Inclusion:</u> 1) workers who had paid into a supplementary pension between 1 April 1964 and 31 December 2006. 3 employment groups divided into 7 occupational groups: dentists, DAs, GPs, nurses, medical secretaries, lawyers and legal	Adults. 130715 in databases (n=4128 from dental clinic, n=38584 from GPs clinic and n=53 598 from lawyer's office) See Figure 1) vs 122481 vs See Table 1 for n. in each occupational group/employment years. ^b	1)NA. 2)NR.	Age at employment- dentist: 30.2 years (SD) [NR]; Assistant - 23.8 years (SD) [NR]. GP: 37.3 years (SD) [NR] Nurse: 37.3 years (SD) [NR].	Dentist vs assistant vs GP vs Nurse vs Secretary (GP) vs Lawyer vs Secretary (Lawyer). <u>Neurological disease cases, n:</u> 191 vs 1227 148 vs 195 vs 1085 vs 355 vs 1540	1)NR. 2)NR.	[1 st employment or 1 January 1977 to the date of disease diagnosis, date of death, emigration or disappearance	Gender/sex. Female, n (%). Dental clinics- Dentists: 2693 (50.1) vs Dental Assistant, 33,858 (100.0) GP clinics- GP: 2455 (39.9) vs Nurse: 5872 (100.0) vs Secretary (GP): 22,785 (100.0)

	<p>supplementary pension fund for all workers aged 18-66 + employed in Denmark for more than 8 h/wk.</p> <p><u>2.RAHP</u>- info. on all workers with Danish authorisation to work as healthcare personnel including dentists, GPs and nurses contains info. back to 1982.</p> <p><u>3.CRS</u> - info. on mortality, emigration, immigration and disappearance for all Danish residents since 1968 + people can voluntarily register info. on their most important job title with CRS (not rated).</p> <p>4. <u>LMM at Statistics Denmark</u>-info. on occupational classification for all Danes for November of each year since 1980</p>	<p>secretaries. Study thereby included 2 occupational groups exposed to Hg (dentists and DAs) and five control groups.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> 1) Highly educated workers (see figure 1 for the numbers of workers in each category), 2) subjects who emigrated from Denmark before they were employed (n=70) 3) Analyses for DAs, medical and legal secretaries only included women from these groups, thereby excluding men (n=6053). For dentists, GPs and lawyers included both sexes.</p>			<p>Secretary (GP): 35.5 years (SD) [NR]. Lawyer: 27.7 years (SD) [NR]</p> <p>Secretary (lawyer): 27.6 years (SD) [NR]</p>	<p><u>Neurological disease IR^a:</u> 15.9 vs 20.6 vs 22.6 vs 18.3 vs 22.2 vs 29.1 20.3.</p> <p><u>PD cases, n:</u> 8 vs 14 vs 6 vs 1 vs 34 vs 16 vs 53.</p> <p><u>PD IR^a:</u> 1.2 vs 0.6 vs 1.6 vs 0.2 vs 0.8 vs 2.5 vs 1.1</p> <p><u>Renal disease cases, n:</u> 122 vs 625 vs 86 vs 68 vs 395 vs 237 vs 660.</p> <p><u>Renal disease IR:</u> 5.7 vs 10.1 vs 6.7 vs 6.4 vs 8.4 vs 5.3 vs 8.9</p>		<p>nce, or end of follow-up (31 December 2006), whichever came first; 1977-2006]</p>	<p>Lawyer offices- Lawyer: 1916 (16.8) vs Secretary (Lawyer): 37,717 (100.0).</p> <p>Occupation. Period of employment: Dentists vs Assistant vs GP vs nurse vs secretary (GP) vs lawyer vs secretary (lawyer):</p> <p><u>Persons employed 1964-2006:</u> 5371 vs 33 858 vs 6154 vs 5872 vs 22 785 vs 11 433 vs 37 717</p> <p><u>Persons employed 1964-1979:</u> 2033 vs 12 065 vs 778 vs 1433 vs 7626 vs 3787 vs 15659</p> <p><u>Persons employed 1980-1994:</u> 3493 vs 17 514 vs 3018 vs 2447 vs 12 450 vs 5527 vs 18 848.</p> <p><u>Persons employed 1995-2006:</u> 3448 vs 16789 vs 3667 vs 3805 vs 11 537 vs 5940 vs 16 393.</p>
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	(does not include category for DA). 2)NA								
<i>Maternal Exposure</i>									
Adams, 2008 ⁸	<p>1) Study advertised by 2x autism chapters in Arizona, and national autism parent listserves. Typical children recruited from friends of autism families.</p> <p>2) Samples sent to RTI International for testing and 20 samples with largest mass of hair were split + sent to MIT Nuclear Reactor Lab for measurement.</p>	<p>Both groups. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Birth between 1988-1999, 2) Sample of the "first-cut" baby hair between 12-24 months (3) no previous measurements of Hg levels in child blood, urine, or hair Autistic children. <u>Inclusion:</u> diagnosis of autism per DSM IV criteria by certified professional (psychologist, psychiatrist) Normal children. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) normal development – no ASD/PDD/ADD/ADHD or speech/language delay, 2) no asthma, severe atopic allergies, Type I diabetes, or other autoimmune disease 3) no first or second-degree relatives diagnosed with ASD/PDD/ADD/ADHD 4) normal vaccination schedule up to age of first haircut 5) validation of autism</p>	<p>Child patient: NR vs NR vs 109 (Autism n=78, Controls n=31)</p>	<p>1)NR 2)Missing data: most families could not provide vaccination info. so not analysed.</p>	<p>Age when haircut. Autism vs controls: 16.6 months (4.4) [NR] vs 16.5 months (5.0) [NR]</p>	<p>Autism vs control (%). <u>Anti-Rho D immunoglobulin:</u> 19% vs 15%, <u>Antibiotic use during pregnancy:</u> 34% vs 20%, <u>Maternal antibiotic use during nursing:</u> 23% vs 12% <u>Maternal antibiotic use during pregnancy or nursing:</u> 44% vs 23%. <u>Percentage using oral antibiotics 0–18 month:</u> 87% vs 65%. Autism vs control, mean (SD). <u>Antibiotic usage 0–6 months:</u> 0.94(1.2) vs 0.36 (0.6), <u>Antibiotic usage 7–12 months:</u> 1.7(2.1) vs 0.65 (1.0), <u>Antibiotic usage 13–18 months:</u> 1.2 (1.6) vs 0.46 (0.9),</p>	<p>1)NR 2)NR</p>	<p>NR [Sample of "first-cut" baby hair between 12-24 months required]. ATEC checklist completed retrospectively for when child 3yrs old</p>	<p>Gender/sex, n (%) of children Autism- male: 67 (87%); female: 11 (14%). Controls- male: 21 (68%); female: 11(32%) Place of residence: Autism vs Control, %. US regions- Southwest: 46% vs 39%. Midwest: 17% vs 13%. Southeast: 14% vs 13%. Northeast: 12% vs 29%. West: 12% vs 6%.</p>

		diagnosis not undertaken.				<p><u>Antibiotic usage 19–24 months:</u> 0.84(1.3) vs 0.46 (1.1)</p> <p><u>Total antibiotic usage 0–18 months:</u> 3.8 (3.7) vs 1.5 (2.1).</p> <p><u>Maternal Fish Consumption (servings/month):</u> 2.3 (2.9) vs 1.9 (2.3).</p>			
Bjorkman 2018 ⁹	1)MoBa: prospective population-based pregnancy cohort study conducted by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health. From 1999-2008 pregnant women from Norway invited to participate in conjunction with appointment for routine ultrasound scan around wk 17 pregnancy. Current study: based on version 8 of quality-assured MoBa data files released for research on exposure to dental	<u>Inclusion:</u> mother able to read in Norwegian.	Mother and child. NR vs 114,500 children and 95,200 mother's vs 72,038 singleton pregnancies (62,832 mothers participating with 1-4 pregnancies)	1)NR 2)Missing data within a variable given the code missing and included in analyses as a category within the actual variable. Detailed in Table 1.	Mean NR- see Table 1 in study for n of participant in each age-range group	<p>Maternal exposure Amalgam group: 0, 1–4, 5–8, 9–12, 13+, Total. n (%)</p> <p><u>Body mass index (kg/m2)</u> - <18.5: 537 (3.4%), 817 (3.1%), 456 (2.4%), 156 (1.8%), 44 (1.7%), 2010 (2.8%); 18.5–25: 10679 (68.0%); 17285 (66.4%); 11684 (61.3%), 4946 (56.9%), 1334 (52.3%), 45928 (63.8%)</p> <p>25–30: 2959 (18.8%), 5102 (19.6%), 4331 (22.7%), 2216 (25.5%), 695 (27.2%), 15303 (21.2%)</p> <p>30–35: 822 (5.2%), 1512 (5.8%), 1432 (7.5%), 732 (8.4%), 261 (10.2%), 4759(6.6%).</p>	1) n of teeth filled with amalgam. N. of pregnancies (%). 0 teeth: 15699 (21.8%); 1-4 teeth: 26031 (36.1%); 5-8 teeth: 19072 (26.5%); 9-12 teeth: 8685 (12.1%); 13+ teeth: 2551 (3.5%). 2) NR	1999-2008. 9 years [Outcomes at ≥ 22 weeks and 0–7 days after birth]	<p>Gender/sex: Women 100%</p> <p>Offspring (in adjusted analysis)- Boys: n=36, 537; Girls: n=35,207.</p> <p>Education. Amalgam group 0, 1–4 ,5–8, 9–12 ,13+, Total n (%). Education (years) -12 yrs: 4493 (28.6%); 7501 (28.8%); 6240 (32.7%); 3283 (37.8%); 1043 (40.9%); 22560 (31.3%); 13–16 yrs: 6210 (39.6%), 10625 (40.8%), 7663 (40.2%), 3434 (39.5%), 946 (37.1%), 28878 (40.1%); 17+ yrs: 3932 (25.0%), 6405 (24.6%), 4108 (21.5%), 1534 (17.7%), 427</p>

	restorative materials during pregnancy + pregnancy outcomes. 2)NR.				35–40: 207 (1.3%), 422 (1.6%), 353 (1.9%), 251 (2.9%), 78 (3.1%), 1311 (1.8%) >40: 64 (0.4%), 122 (0.5%), 126 (0.7%), 81 (0.9%), 35 (1.4%), 428 (0.6%). Missing: 431 (2.7%), 771 (3.0%), 690 (3.6%), 303 (3.5%), 104 (4.1%), 2299 (3.2%) <u>Current smoking-</u> Non-smoker: 13395 (85.3%), 21331 (81.9%), 14679 (77.0%), 6327 (72.8%), 1721 (67.5%), 57453 (79.8%); Occasionally: 338 (2.2%), 609 (2.3%), 506 (2.7%), 283 (3.3%), 80 (3.1%), 1816 (2.5%). Daily smoking: 474 (3.0%), 1047 (4.0%), 1103 (5.8%), 614 (7.1%), 231 (9.1%), 3469 (4.8%) Missing: 1492 (9.5%), 3044 (11.7%), 2784 (14.6%), 1461		(16.7%), 16406 (22.8%); Missing: 1064 (6.8%), 1500 (5.8%), 1061 (5.6%), 434 (5.0%), 135 (5.3%), 4194 (5.8%).
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						<p>(16.8%), 519 (20.3%), 9300 (12.9%).</p> <p><u>Use of alcohol-</u> Never: 12238 (78.0%), 19488 (74.9%), 13834 (72.5%), 6047 (69.6%), 1688 (66.2%), 53295 (74.0%). 1–3 times per month or less: 1290 (8.2%), 2618 (10.1%), 2289 (12.0%), 1171 (13.5%), 384 (15.1%), 7752 (10.8%). 1 time per week or more 51 (0.3%), 113 (0.4%), 113 (0.6%), 65 (0.7%), 18 (0.7%), 360 (0.5%). Missing: 2120 (13.5%), 3812 (14.6%), 2836 (14.9%), 1402 (16.1%), 461 (18.1%), 10631 (14.8%).</p>			
Daniels 2007 ¹⁰	<p>1)Expectant mothers recruited during routine prenatal health visits.</p> <p>2)Hospital.</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1) all pregnancies of mothers resident in Bristol, England and surrounding areas 2) expected dates of delivery between April 1991- December 1992 Present investigation restricted to</p>	<p>Mother and child. NR vs 15000 pregnancies vs 8251 (singleton live born children)</p>	<p>1)NR. 2)NR.</p>	<p>28.9 (4.6) [NR] (patients included in sample)</p>	<p><u>Smoke during pregnancy, n (%).</u> No: 6220 (84.3) Yes: 1155 (15.7) Missing: 2362 <u>Alcohol during pregnancy, n (%):</u> No: 3290 (44.6) Yes: 4085 (55.4) Missing: 1466</p>	<p>1) Nearly 90% of the women in this study received dental care during pregnancy (Table 1). Among those, 31% had amalgams placed or removed. Most women (71%) also had 4 or more</p>	<p>NR [Follow-up until: Child age - 15 months.]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Women: 100% Child's sex- female: 3815 (51.7%), Male: 3560 (48.3%).</p> <p>Education, n (%): CSE (very low): 763 (10.4).</p>

		singleton live born children with data on gestational age and birthweight, and whose mothers provided prenatal dental history.					amalgams in place prior to conception. 2) NR		Vocational (low): 647 (8.8) O Level (moderate): 2640 (35.7) A Level (moderately high): 1912 (25.9) Degree (high): 1129 (15.3) Missing: 284 (3.9) (patients included in sample) Place of residence. All mothers resided in Bristol, England and surrounding areas. ^c
Lindbohm 2007 ¹¹	1)Info. on women belonging to trade unions of dentists, dental nurses and hygienists, dental technicians and dental laboratory workers, pharmacists, secretaries and receptionists in health care. Data on occupation, working tasks and occupational exposure during the first	Inclusion: 1) Women born in 1951 or later 2) belonged to union during 1992-9, 3) pregnancy that started between 1992-1998, 4) member of the union during first 3 months of pregnancy 5) aged 25-39 at the beginning of the pregnancy. First eligible pregnancy of a woman selected for study. Exclusion: 1) births of seriously malformed children in controls, 2) 15 women did not confirm the study pregnancy in the	Adults. 12992 women identified from trade unions (8537 births (controls) and 10229 miscarriages (cases), 801 other pregnancies) vs 1074 women with pregnancy data between 1992-1998 (358 cases vs 716 controls) eligible; vs Confirmed pregnancy and consented to participate: 222 cases and 498 controls.	1) After three postings the response rate was 68% (66% for the cases and 70% for the controls). See sample size for final n in analysis. 2) Statistical models include a category for missing information when necessary (Tables 2 and 3). Some of early recognised abortions may not have been treated in hospital, and	NR	Cases vs controls, n. Pregnancy history. <u>Previous miscarriage:</u> 38 vs 66. <u>Previous induced abortion/extrauterine pregnancy:</u> 19 vs 25. <u>Previous births-</u> 1: 61 vs 135; 2: 41 vs 110; 3 ≤: 13 vs 26. <u>Use of intrauterine device or pills at conception.</u> 6 vs 9 Diseases and drugs. <u>Cervicitis:</u> 0 vs 28;	1)N. of own amalgam fillings. Cases vs controls (n)- 5-9: 105 vs 219; 10 ≤: 69 vs 168 2)NA	[NA]	Gender/sex. Female: 100%. Child's sex: NR. Occupation. Cases vs controls, n (%). <u>Dental technicians and laboratory workers:</u> 6 (54.6%) vs 20 (76.9%); <u>Dentists:</u> 49 (67.1%) vs 106 (68.0%); <u>Dental nurses and hygienists:</u> 86 (61.4%) vs 183 (65.4%); <u>Pharmacists:</u> 69 (74.2%) vs. 139 (76.0%); <u>Receptionists +</u>

	<p>trimester of pregnancy were obtained using postal questionnaires .</p> <p>2)NA. See recruitment method.</p>	<p>questionnaire were excluded (2 controls, 13 cases).</p>		<p>these + very early, unrecognised losses might be missing from the data. Possible that some of the pregnancies of exposed women ended at subclinical stage and therefore missing from data.</p>		<p><u>Inflammation of uterine cavity</u>: 7 vs 4; <u>Oophoritis</u>: 6 vs 11; <u>Other disease of genital organs</u>: 4 vs 3; <u>Medical examination because of infertility</u>: 16 vs 24. <u>Diabetes (treated with insulin)</u>: 3 vs 4; <u>Disease of the thyroid gland</u>: 4 vs 9. <u>Fever</u>: 25 vs 60; <u>Potentially harmful drugs</u>: 5 vs 8.</p> <p>Other. <u>Smoking</u>-1-4 cigarettes/ day: 7 vs 19; 5 ≤cigarettes per day: 8 vs 9 <u>Alcohol consumption</u>- less than 1 drink a week: 44 vs 129; 1 drink or more a week: 15 vs 19. <u>BMI (reference group 20-25kg/m2)</u>- less than 18: 5 vs 6; 18-19: 15 vs 54; 26-27: 28 vs 67; 28-30: 16 vs 31; more than 30: 17 vs 39.</p>			<p><u>departmental secretaries in healthcare</u>: 25 (61.0%) vs 52 (73.2%).</p> <p>Other: Occupational exposure (bjorkfactor) - <u>Solvents</u>: 76 vs 182, <u>Metal fumes and dust</u>: 61 vs 127, <u>Welding fumes or soldering smoke</u>: 49 vs 105, <u>Pesticides</u>: 14 vs 22, <u>Temperature of 30 degrees or over at work</u>: 42 vs 100.</p> <p>Features of relationship. Paternal factors. Cases vs controls, n. <u>Smoking</u>- 1-4 cigarettes a day: 12 vs 25; 5-14 cigarettes a day: 22 vs 53; 15 or more cigarettes per day: 25 vs 54; <u>Alcohol consumption</u>: less than 2 drinks a week: 67 vs 167; 2-6 drink a week: 84 vs 192, 7-14 drinks a week: 37 vs 75</p>
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Heggland 2011 ¹²	<p>1) Dental staff. Record linkage between dental authorities/public archives; lists of current and previous employees in public dental healthcare system from all 19 counties in Norway except Rogaland+ three largest national trade unions of dental assistants and dentists provided info. about members who agreed to participate in the study. General population: MBRN.</p> <p>2) NA. See recruitment method.</p>	<p>Dental staff. <u>Inclusion:</u> female DA and dentists registered from archive establishment until time of data collection (included dentists in private practice) + 3 largest national trade unions of DA and dentists provided info. about members who had been addressed and agreed to participate Exposed group. <u>Inclusion:</u> Infants delivered to female dental personnel during 1967–2006. Unexposed group. <u>Inclusion:</u> all other females.</p>	<p>Adults. NR vs NR vs Final study population- Total: 1,130,251 mothers, of whom. Dental personnel: 5493 (4482 DA, 1011 dentists). Control: 1124758</p>	<p>1) NA. 2) Data on employment time periods incomplete/missing for considerable n of dental personnel so used available data on employment periods to identify dental personnel known to be in employment before each delivery. Trade union data did not include dates of employment, so women identified solely from trade unions not included in group “dental personnel in employment”. Not registered with higher education: 6 dentists.</p>	<p>Maternal age 1st delivery: Dental assistants: 25.1 years (4.5) [NR] Dentists: 29.3 years (3.8) [NR]. Control group: 26.0 years (5.2) [NR],</p>	<p>Mean n of children/woman- Control: 2.07. Dental Assistants: 2.09. Dentists: 2.05.</p>	<p>1) NR 2) NR</p>	<p>Data collected from establishment of archives (all prior to 1967 to 2007/08) [NA]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Female: 100%. Child’s sex (proportion of boys)- Control: n=1 192 805, dental assistants: n=192, dentists: n=52. Occupation. Dentists n=1011, Dental assistants n=4482 Education. Controls vs DA vs Dentists. Highest registered education (%)- <u>Primary and lower secondary/unknown:</u> 27.6 vs 24.4 vs: 4.8^d <u>Upper secondary:</u> 43.1 vs 64.2 vs. 1.2^d <u>University/university college:</u> 29.3, vs 11.4 vs 94.0.</p>
Lygre 2016 ¹³	<p>1) Data from MoBa conducted by Norwegian Institute of Public Health. Participants recruited among all pregnant</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> pregnant women in Norway 1999-2008 signed up to routine ultrasound at 17wks gestation. Pregnancy=unit of observation. Woman could participate with >1 pregnancy.</p>	<p>Adult. 108 264 pregnancies recruited 1999–2008 vs 69,474 eligible vs 43.5% of women approached agreed to participate.</p>	<p>1) NR 2) Missing information for maternal education (n = 3391), alcohol during pregnancy (n = 9612), smoking</p>	<p>30.3 years (4.5) [NR]</p>	<p><u>Parity</u> – 1st pregnancy: 32464 (46.7%), 2nd pregnancy or more: 37010(53.3%). <u>Consulted dentist during pregnancy</u> - Yes: 27306 (39.3%),</p>	<p>1) Amalgam fillings placed: 510 (0.73%), Amalgam fillings removed: 2154 (60.7). Mean self-assessed n. of teeth with amalgam fillings</p>	<p>Mothers recruited 1999-2008 [37-42 weeks]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Female: 100%. Child’s sex/gender. Boys (total): n=35514 (51.1%). Education. Maternal education, n (%)-</p>

	women in Norway 1999–2008. Postal invitations based on hospital lists sent to pregnant women after signing up for routine ultrasound around 17 gestational weeks. 2)NA. See recruitment method.	Only singleton births included. <u>Exclusion:</u> individuals with invalid data on amalgam fillings, weight, and height.		during pregnancy (n = 659). ^e		No: 42168 (60.7%). <u>BMI, mean (SD):</u> 24.0 (4.2). <u>Smoking during pregnancy -</u> Never: 64220 (92.4%), Occasionally: 1426 (2.1%), Daily: 3169 (4.6%). <u>Alcohol during pregnancy -</u> Never: 51978 (74.8%), <1x/wk:7532 (10.8%), 1x/wk: 296 (0.43%), >1x/wk: 56(0.08%)	among 69 474 pregnancies was 4.4 (SD 4.0). In subgroup including only participants with amalgam fillings: 5.6 (SD 3.6). 2)NR		</= 12 yrs: 31863 (31.5%), 13-16yrs: 28175 (40.6), >/=17yrs: 16045 (23.1%)
Lygre 2018 ¹⁴	1)See Lygre 2016 2)See Lygre 2016.	<u>Inclusion:</u> See Lygre 2016.	Adult. Women consented to participate in 41% pregnancies (info on: 114.700 children); 69652 eligible children included in study	1)NR 2)Missing data ADHD symptoms- at 3 years: 27 489 children; at 5yrs: n=46350 children. Based on 42163 mothers with child 3 yrs old, n (%): missing data on mean BMI: 345 (0.83%); Smoking during pregnancy: 345 (0.83%); alcohol during pregnancy 4758 (11.3%)	Of 42163 mothers with child 3yrs old: 30.5 years (4.4) [NR].	Based on 42163 mothers with child 3 yrs old: <u>Mean BMI (kg/m2):</u> 24.0 (SD 4.1). <u>Smoking during pregnancy, n (%)-</u> Never: 39472 (93.6%), Occasionally: 757 (1.8%), Daily: 1589 (3.8%) Missing data: 345 (0.83%). <u>Alcohol during pregnancy, n (%):</u> Never: 32494 (77.1%), < 1/wk: 4683(11.1%), 1/wk: 187 (0.44%), >1/wk: 41 (0.78%), Missing data: 4758 (11.3%).	Based on 42163 mothers with child 3 yrs old: <u>Amalgam fillings placed:</u> Yes; 270 (0.64%), No: 41893 (99.4%). <u>Amalgam fillings removed:</u> Yes: 1268 (3.0%), No: 40895 (97%). Of mothers who had amalgam fillings removed during pregnancy: 49 (0.52%) had no amalgam fillings after removal. 2)NR	Mothers recruited 1999-2008 [5 years post-partum follow-up]	Gender/sex. Female: 100%. Child's sex/gender: both boy and girls (look at Tables in appendix of study for specific n at each analysis) Education. Based on 42163 mothers with child 3 yrs old. Maternal education- Less/equal to 12 yrs: 11779 (27.9%), 13-16yrs: 17978 (42.6%), equal to/more than 17 years: 10507 (24.9%).

						<p><u>Consulted dentist during pregnancy, n (%)</u>: Yes: 16722 (39.7%), No: 25441 (60.3%). <u>Parity</u>: 1st pregnancy: 20140 (47.8%); 2nd pregnancy or more: 20023 (52.2%)</p>			Missing info: 1899 (4.1%)
Naimi-Akbar 2012 ¹⁵	<p>1) Occupations of women identified using Swedish Population and Housing Census (1960, 1970, 1980, 1985, and 1990). 2) Offspring of female dentists/dental nurses identified using Multi-Generation Register.</p> <p>2)NA</p>	<p><u>Inclusion</u>: Male offspring of female dentists/dental assistants (of 2 consensus years duration) born between 1960-1987. Several subjects could have same mother. Dentists' offspring matched with physician's offspring and those of dental nurses with assistant nurses' children. Matching ratio planned as 1:5 and if not able to obtain this ratio, selected all available subjects.</p>	<p>Mother and child. Exposed: Included sons female dentists: 365 vs sons of female nurses: 3181. Comparator: Included sons of physicians:378 vs Sons of assistant nurse: 12667.</p>	<p>1)NA</p> <p>2) Missing data: Father's education. Total: n=1403 (Dentists, n=39; dental nurse, n=235; physician, n=54; assistant nurse, n=1075)</p>	<p>Mother's age at subject's birth, n (%). Dentist vs dental nurse vs physician vs assistant nurse. ≤ 25: 3 (0.8) vs 1200 (37.7) vs 2 (0.5) vs 5254 (41.5) 26-34: 280 (76.7) vs 1838 (57.8) vs 252 (66.7) vs 6769 (53.4). ≥ 35: 82 (22.5) vs 143 (4.5) vs 124 (32.8) vs 644 (5.1).</p>	NR	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)NA</p>	NR	<p>Gender/sex. Newborns- male: 100%, born to 100% female nurses</p> <p>Occupation. Mother's occupation. Dentists: n=365, Dental nurse: n=3181, Physician: n=378, Assistant nurse: n=12667.</p> <p>Education. Father's education reported Table 1.</p>
Naimi-Akbar 2014 ¹⁶	<p>1)See Naimi-Akbar 2012. Mortality data obtained from Statistics Sweden.</p> <p>2) NA See Naimi-Akbar 2012</p>	See Naimi-Akbar 2012.	<p>Mother and child. Exposed. Total participated=12110. Dental nurses n=10420, Dentists n=1690. Comparator. Total participate n=47591. Assistant nurse n=44908, Physician n=2683</p>	<p>1)NA</p> <p>2) Father's education Total: n=2512</p>	Table 1 paper reports Mother's age at subjects birth.	NR	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)NA</p>	NR	<p>Gender/sex. Newborns- male: 100%, born to 100% female nurses</p> <p>Occupation. Mother's occupation, n. Dental nurses n=10420, Dentists n=1690,</p>

									Assistant nurse n=44908, Physician n=2683. Education. Father's education reported Table 1.
Watson 2011 ¹⁷	1)The SCDS Main Cohort is a well-described group of 779 mother-infant pairs residing in the Republic of Seychelles. Enrolled in 1989-1990. 2)NR	NR	Mother and child. 779 mother infant pairs vs 711 vs 587.	1)NR 2)From Table 2. N of participants missing data on-McCarthy GCI score:0; PLS Total Score: 40; W-J Applied Problems: 3; W-J Letter word: 4; Bender Gestalts Errors Raw Score: 14; CBCL Total Score: 1; Prenatal MeHg: 0; Postnatal MeHg: 0; Prenatal Hg0 (LEL surfaces): 338 missing. Prenatal Hg0 (UEL surfaces): 154; Prenatal Hg0 (LEL Occlusal Points): 341; Prenatal Hg0 (UEL Occlusal Points): 156; HOME Score: 0 Caregiver Intelligence Raven: 0	Maternal age. Overall (n=587): 25.96 years (5.78) [14.33-44.79]; Females (n=291): 26.06 years (5.64) [NR]; males (n=296): 25.86 years (5.92) [NR]	Total vs Females (n=291) vs Males (n=296). Characteristic (n), Mean (SD) [Min-Max] vs Mean (SD) vs Mean (SD). <u>McCarthy GCI:</u> n= 587, 94.48 (12.44) [49.00-126.00] vs 95.63 (12.74) vs 93.35 (12.04) <u>PLS Total Score:</u> n= 547, 70.10 (6.55) [49.00-90.00] vs 70.80 (6.77) vs 69.43 (6.27) <u>W-J Applied Problems:</u> n= 584, 87.33 (17.23) [8.00-138.00] vs 88.70 (17.79) vs 85.98 (16.57) <u>W-J Letter Word:</u> n= 583, 77.01 (10.57) [47.00-116.00] vs 77.76 (10.57) vs 76.27 (10.53) <u>Bender Gestalt Errors Raw Scores:</u> n=573, 10.18 (3.79)	1)Amalgam 2)NR	Mothers enrolled in 1989-1990; [Battery test for child at 66 months]	Gender/sex, n (%) . Child's sex: Females:291 (49.6%); Males: 296 (50.4%). SES. Hollingshead SES, mean (SD) [range]: n= 587, 26.03 (10.27) [5.00-61.00] vs 26.15 (10.48) vs 25.91 (10.08). Other. HOME score. n= 587, 33.30 (5.32) [13.00-47.00] vs 33.58 (4.96) vs 33.03 (5.65).

						<p>[0.00-21.00] vs 10.54 (3.73) vs 9.82 (3.81) <u>CBCL Total T</u> <u>Score:</u> n= 586, 59.64 (9.90) [24.00-92.00] 59.40 (10.06) vs 59.88 (9.75) <u>Prenatal MeHg:</u> n= 587, 6.71 (4.43) [0.54- 22.74] vs 6.84 (4.48) vs 6.59 (4.38) <u>Postnatal MeHg:</u> n= 587, 6.44 (3.30) [0.88- 25.81] vs 6.68 (3.28) vs 6.21 (3.30) <u>Prenatal Hg0</u> <u>(LEL Surfaces):</u> n= 249, 5.12 (4.11) [1.00- 22.00] vs 4.82 (4.07) vs 5.37 (4.13) <u>Prenatal Hg0</u> <u>(UEL Surfaces):</u> n= 433, 6.75 (5.29) [1.00- 31.00] vs 6.16 (4.85) vs 7.28 (5.60) <u>Prenatal Hg0 (LEL</u> <u>Occlusal Points):</u> n=246, 8.43 (5.77) [2.00- 28.00] vs 8.14 (5.63) vs 8.66 (5.89) <u>Prenatal Hg0</u> <u>(UEL Occlusal</u> <u>Points):</u> n= 431, 11.05 (7.17)</p>			
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						<p>[2.00-45.00] vs 10.59 (6.77) vs 11.46 (7.50) <u>Caregiver Intelligence (Raven)</u>: n=587, 23.30 (10.44) [3.00-56.00] vs 23.55 (10.18) vs 23.06 (10.71) <u>Birth Weight (kg)</u>: 587 3.21 0.49 1.50 5.32 3.15 0.47 3.27 0.51</p>			
Watson 2012 ¹⁸	Enrolment and setting have been reported previously (Davidson et al., 2008) ^f	<p><u>Inclusion</u>: mother-infant pairs residing in the Republic of Seychelles.</p> <p>Inclusion/exclusion criteria have been reported previously (Davidson et al., 2008)^e</p>	229 previously reported by Davidson et al., 2008 ^e vs 228 of these eligible in this study (one was missing amalgam data) + 14 additional subjects = 242 subjects available for analysis.	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2) From Table 1. N. of participants with data available for MDI at 9 months: 239, PDI at 9 months: 238, MDI at 30 months: 241, PDI at 30 months: 238, data on amalgam surfaces > 0: 196, data on occlusal points > 0: 196</p>	Maternal age (years): All subjects - 27.82 (5.95) [16-43]; Boys : 27.88 (6.24) Girls : 27.76 (5.68).	<p>All Subjects vs Boys vs Girls. N, mean (SD) [min-max] vs mean (SD)</p> <p><u>MDI, at 9 months</u>: n= 239, 102.86 (8.32) [72-122] vs 102.58 (8.41) vs 103.12 (8.25). <u>PDI, at 9 months</u>: n=238, 105.78 (10.27) [68-141] vs 104.77 (9.49) vs 106.78 (10.93). <u>MDI, at 30 months</u>: n= 241, 85.08 (9.54), [56-115] vs 83.25 (8.58) vs 86.87 (10.10). <u>PDI, at 30 months</u>: n=238, 89.85 (13.78) [50-123] vs 86.05 (13.09) vs 93.53 (13.47); <u>Occlusal Points ≥ 0</u>: n= 196, 13.49 (8.61) [2-40] vs</p>	<p>All subjects vs Boys vs Girls. Amalgam Surfaces > 0: n= 196, 8.49 (6.27) [1-28] vs 8.65 (6.98) vs 8.35 (5.57)</p> <p>2)NR</p>	Mothers enrolled in 1989-1990; [Amalgam surfaces and MDI and PDI at 9 and 30 months]	<p>Gender/sex. Child's sex-Boys: 120 (49.6%); Girls: 122 (50.4%).</p> <p>SES. All Subjects vs Boys vs Girls. n, mean (SD) [min-max] SES (Mod. Hollingshead)-242: 33.96 (10.81) [13-63] vs 34.15 (11.25) vs 33.77 (10.40), p-value= 0.79</p> <p>Others. All Subjects vs Boys vs Girls. n, mean (SD) [min-max]/ <u>Living with 2 parents (%)</u>: 242, 50 (50) [0-100] vs 48 (50) vs 52 (50), p-value= 0.44 <u>Home environment (PROCESS)</u>: 242, 151.88 (14.78) [113-190] vs</p>

						<p>13.72 (9.68) vs 13.27 (7.55). <u>Maternal MeHg (ppm)</u>: n=242, 5.60 (3.65) [0.19-18.49] vs 5.51 (3.69) vs 5.69 (3.62); <u>Omega-3 PUFA (mg/mL)</u>: n= 242, 0.03 (0.01) [0.01-0.06] vs 0.03 (0.01) vs 0.03 (0.01) <u>Omega-6 PUFA (mg/mL)</u>: n= 242, 1.22 (0.21), [0.66-1.72] vs 1.23 (0.23) vs 1.20 (0.18). <u>Child's birth weight (kg)</u>: n= 242 , 3.24 (0.49) [1.65- 4.45] vs 3.33 (0.48) vs 3.14 (0.48) <u>Maternal intelligence (K-BIT)</u>: n=242, 86.26 (13.96) [48-117] vs 85.84 (14.65) vs 86.67 (13.29)</p>			151.73 (15.11) vs 152.03 (14.51), p-value= 0.88,
Watson 2013 ¹⁹	<p>The SCDNS Cohort is a prospective, double-blind, longitudinal study of mother-infant pairs residing in the Republic of Seychelles.</p> <p>See Davidson et al., 2008^f for</p>	<p><u>Inclusion</u>: healthy pregnant women</p> <p><u>Exclusion</u>: 1) not pregnant (n=4), 2) miscarriage/termination of pregnancy/ stillbirth (n=14), 3) premature twin delivery (n=1) 4) delivering abroad (n=1), 5) mother with preeclampsia (n=1),</p>	NR vs 276 eligible for this study vs NR	<p>1)1 woman withdrew.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Mother's age at Delivery 27.77 years (6.03) [16-43]; Child's age 5.62 (0.30) [5.14-6.33]</p>	<p>n = 236. Mean, Median (SD) [Min-Max] <u>Finger Tapping Dominant Hand</u>:23.43, 23.50 (5.62) [5.40-39.60] <u>Finger Tapping Non-dominant Hand</u>: 21.35, 21.50 (4.82) [8.60-34.80]</p>	<p>1)Amalgam surfaces (n=236). Mean, median (SD) [Min-max]: 6.96, 5.00 (6.58) [0-28]</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Mothers enrolled in 1989-1990; [Outcomes at child's 5 years]</p>	<p>Gender/sex (child)- male: 118 (50%); female: 85 (36%).</p> <p>SES. Hollingshead SES at 5 years, mean, median (SD) [min-max]: 31.53, 30.00 (10.95) [8-63].</p>

	<p>details on enrolment + setting</p>	<p>6) baby with trisomy 21 (n=1).</p> <p>Full inclusion/exclusion criteria have been reported previously (Davidson et al., 2008)^f</p>				<p><u>PLS-Total Language:</u> 118.79, 120.00 (5.32) [100-128]</p> <p><u>PLS-Auditory Comprehension:</u> 55.63, 56.00 (2.70) [47-60]</p> <p><u>PLS-Verbal Ability:</u> 63.16, 63.50 (3.22) [51-68]</p> <p><u>W-J Applied Problems:</u> 15.14, 16.00 (4.07) [2-24]</p> <p><u>W-J Letter Word:</u> 10.96, 11.00 (6.00) [1-24]</p> <p><u>CBCL - Total Score:</u> 59.29, 60.00 (8.59) [25-77]</p> <p><u>Child KBIT - Verbal Knowledge:</u> 11.87, 12.00 (2.77) [6-18]</p> <p><u>Child KBIT - Matrices:</u> 7.74, 8.00 (1.20) [2-9]</p> <p><u>Prenatal Hair MeHg (ppm):</u> 5.63, 4.91 (3.65) [0.19-18.49]</p> <p><u>Maternal mean DHA (mg/mL):</u> 0.028, 0.027 (0.007) [0.011-0.051]</p> <p><u>Maternal mean AA (mg/mL):</u> 0.099, 0.097 (0.021) [0.059-0.171]</p>	<p>Other. Home environment (PROCESS) score: 151.78, 151.50, (14.91) [113-190].</p>
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						<p><u>Maternal serum omega-3 (mg/mL):</u> 0.032, 0.032 (0.009) [0.013-0.058]</p> <p><u>Maternal serum omega-6 (mg/mL):</u> 1.216, 1.219 (0.207) [0.656-1.723]</p> <p><u>Occlusal points score:</u> 11.01, 9.00 (9.38) [0-40]</p> <p><u>Maternal KBIT:</u> 86.40, 88.00 (13.90) [48-117].</p> <p><u>Child's birth weight (kg):</u> 3.23, 3.22 (0.49) [1.65-4.45]</p>			
<i>Patient outcomes</i>									
<i>Casa Pia Trial</i>									
de Rouen 2006 (2002) ²⁰	<p>1) Students at the Casa Pia school system in Lisbon, Portugal.</p> <p>2) Data/specimens on inclusion measures collected in Lisbon, shipped to Seattle for laboratory analyses, and collated by coordinating centre in Seattle to determine eligibility and</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> Children, 1) aged 8-10yrs on January 1, 1997 (born 1986, 1987, 1988). Over time, those who became 8yrs old (born 1989) also included 2) at least one carious lesion in a permanent tooth, 3) no previous exposure to amalgam, 4) urinary Hg level lower than 10 µg/L, (5) blood lead level lower than 15 µg/dL, 6) CTONI IQ min. 67, 7) no interfering health conditions.</p>	<p>Children. 845 potentially eligible children identified vs 647 parents/guardians consented vs. 507 randomised (253 amalgam, 254 composite)</p> <p>Included in primary analysis: those that completed ≥1 follow-up- Amalgam: 246 vs composite: 243.</p> <p>Included in imputation analysis- amalgam:</p>	<p>1) Lost to follow up - Amalgam cohort: Year 1: 7; Year 2: 7; Year 3: 4; Year 4: 8; Year 5: 5. (222 completed studies through Yr 5, 195 reconsented). Follow up Year 6: 3; Year 7: 16. See Figure 1 in paper for specific reasons for withdrawal.</p> <p>Composite cohort: Year 1: 11; Year 2: 5; Year 3: 1; Year 4: 4; Year 5: 6. (228 completed</p>	<p>Amalgam: 10.2 (1.0) [8.1-12.4].</p> <p>Composite: 10.1 (0.9) [8.3-12.0]</p>	<p>Amalgam vs Composite group. Mean (SD) [range]</p> <p><u>Creatinine-adjusted urinary Hg concentration (µg/g):</u> 1.8 (2.0) [0.1-23.5] vs 1.9 (1.8) [0.1-13.7],</p> <p><u>Blood lead concentration (µg/dL):</u> 4.7 (2.5) [1-16] vs 4.5 (2.2) [1-12];</p> <p><u>Creatinine-adjusted albumin concentration, median (IQR).</u> mg/g: 8.6 (4.8-</p>	<p>1) No prior exposure to amalgam.</p> <p>2) Carious surfaces (n): 15.6 (9.0) [0-52] vs 15.9 (10.2) [1-53].</p>	8 yrs [7yr follow-up]	<p>Gender/sex. Amalgam vs Composite, n (%): Female: 116 (46) vs 112 (44); Male: 137 (54) vs 142 (56).</p> <p>Race/ethnicity. Amalgam vs Composite, n (%): White: 178 (70) vs 181 (71); Black: 75 (30) vs 68 (27); Asian: 0 vs 5 (2)</p> <p>Place of residence. Casa Pia system enrolls more than 4000</p>

	<p>randomized treatments assignment and transmitted to Lisbon.</p>		<p>253 vs composite:254.</p>	<p><i>study through year 5. 205 reconsented).</i> Year 6: 10; Year 7: 17. See Figure 1 in paper for specific reasons for withdrawal,</p> <p>2)Missing data: Of all data that could have been collected if all 507 children had remained in the study for 7 years of follow-up, 5% missing because of missed visits or tests for children remaining in the study, and 13% because of children lost to follow-up.</p> <p>Primary outcome variables- <u>Neurobehavioral tests:</u> most complete data. <u>Nerve conduction tests:</u> less data completeness than for neurobehavioral tests in last 2 years due to issues in scheduling and timing of tests. Follow-up and</p>		<p>14.7) vs 8.3 (5.2-16.7).</p>		<p>students from 7 campuses throughout Lisbon. School system selected because University of Lisbon students have diverse backgrounds, high oral disease rates, limited prior dental treatment, and low rates of migration out of Lisbon</p>
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				<p>data completeness %s similar in the 2 treatment groups. <u>Urinary Hg concentrations:</u> obtained for at least 80% of children through year 5, and for years 6 and 7 lower rates of 73% and 65% reflect declining retention rate. <u>Urinary albumin:</u> added to protocol during 1st year and therefore available for only 56% of the amalgam group and 57% of composite group at baseline (follow-up %s similar to urinary Hg). <u>CTONLIQ:</u> obtained for all at baseline and year 7 CTONI and WASI measures available for 66% of amalgam group</p>					
Geier 2011 ²¹	1)Cohort of children examined came from the parent study which	<u>Inclusion:</u> 1) residents of Casa Pia school system in Lisbon, Portugal 2)8-18 years old (were 8-12 years old	Children. NR vs NR vs 462 subjects examined in present study (n. includes both amalgam and composite groups)	1)NR 2)NR	All subjects: 10.11 years (0.9) [NR]}	All subjects, mean ± (SD). <u>Blood lead level (µg/dL):</u> 4.63 ± (2.4)	1)All participants receiving composites had amalgam exposure level of zero except 2 subjects who	8 years [7 years follow-up]	Gender/sex. 57% male. Race/ethnicity. Asian: 1% Black: 29%

	<p>recruited children residents of Casa Pia school system in Lisbon, Portugal. See De Rouen 2006.</p> <p>2)University of Lisbon School of Dental Medicine</p>	<p>at inception of parent study).</p> <p>Exclusion: 1) Children with preexisting neurological/developmental disabilities.</p> <p>See de Rouen et al., 2006 for further detail.</p>				<p><u>Urinary mercury level (µg/L):</u> 1.48 ± (1.1)</p> <p><u>Uroporphyrin (µ/L):</u> 8.56 ± (8.8)</p> <p><u>Heptacarboxyporphyrin (µ/L):</u> 1.76 ± (2.8)</p> <p><u>Hexacarboxyporphyrin (µg/L):</u> 0.43 ± (0.8)</p> <p><u>Pentacarboxyporphyrin (µg/L):</u> 1.35 ± (3.1)</p> <p><u>Precoproporphyrin (µg/L):</u> 3.56 ± (3.9)</p> <p><u>Coproporphyrin (µg/L):</u> 34.84 ± (38.4)</p>	<p>received amalgam restorations in error.</p> <p>2)NR</p>		White: 70%
Geier 2013 ²²	<p>1)Further examines the Casa Pia children's amalgam data. Re-analysis datasets from parent study (DeRouen 2006)</p> <p>2)University of Lisbon School of Dental Medicine.</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1) residents of Casa Pia school system in Lisbon, Portugal 2) 8-12yrs old.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> children with preexisting neurological/developmental disabilities.</p> <p>See de Rouen et al., 2006 for further detail.</p>	<p>Children. NR vs. NR vs n of samples taken: GST T- α: n=344, GST- π: n=447.</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>GST- α group: 10.09 years (1.0) [NR]; GST-π: 10.11 years (0.9) [NR].</p>	<p>GST- α (n=344) vs GST-π (n=447), mean (SD).</p> <p><u>Blood lead level (mg/dL):</u> 4.59 (2.3) vs 4.61 (2.4).</p> <p><u>Urinary Hg (mg/L):</u> 1.44 (1.1) vs 1.47 (1.1).</p> <p><u>Uroporphyrin (mg/L):</u> 8.51 (9.5) vs 8.52 (8.9).</p> <p><u>Heptacarboxyporphyrin (mg/L):</u> 1.74 (3.1) vs 1.74 (2.8).</p> <p><u>Hexacarboxyporphyrin (mg/L):</u> 0.41 (0.9) vs 0.43 (0.8).</p> <p><u>Pentacarboxyporphyrin (mg/L):</u> 1.31 (3.5) vs 1.33 (3.2).</p>	<p>1)All participants receiving composites had amalgam exposure level of zero except 2 subjects who received amalgam restorations in error.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	8 yrs [7yr follow up]	<p>Gender/sex. GST- α group- Male: 58%; female: 42%; GST- π group- male: 56%; female: 44%</p> <p>Race/ethnicity. GST- α group- Asian: 1%, Black: 31%, White: 68% GST- π group- Asian: 1%, Black: 29%, White: 70%.</p>

						<p>Precoproporphyrin (mg/L): 3.35 (3.7) vs 3.48 (3.9). Coproporphyrin (mg/L): 33.44 (38.9) vs 34.60 (38.2). Mean GST-a (mg/L): 7.95 (8.3) vs 7.93 (8.3) §. Mean GST-π (mg/L): 1.71 (3.3) § vs 1.69 (3.0).</p>			
Lauterbach 2008 ²³	<p>1) Children from Casa Pia school system (Lisbon). Enrolment started 1997.</p> <p>2) Neurological examination took place in schools.</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1) 8-12 yrs. sold at time of enrolment, 2) Baseline min. 1 carious lesion in permanent tooth, 3) no previous exposure to amalgam treatments, 4) urinary Hg level < 10 µg/L, blood lead level < 15 µg/ dl, 5) IQ ≥ 67 as obtained with the C-TONI 6) no interfering health condition e.g. progressive neurological disease or renal insufficiency.</p>	<p>Children. NR vs 507 randomised (253 in amalgam group vs 253 in RBC group) vs n consented NR</p>	<p>1) Lost to follow up at Yr 7- Amalgam: n=117 vs. RBC: n=111. N participants who received neurological examination each year sometimes < n with data at primary endpoints due to children unable to attend. N. of participants not uniform across study years (dropouts and missed appointments).</p> <p>2) Data from neurological examination missing for n=1 in RBC.</p>	<p>Age baseline: Amalgam (n=253): 10.2 years (0.98) [8-12]. RBC (n=253): 10.1 years (0.94) [8-12].</p>	<p>RBC vs amalgam NHS before dental treatment: 2.4% vs 3.6%.</p>	<p>1) At baseline: no previous amalgam restorations.</p> <p>2) Carious lesion permanent tooth.</p>	<p>8 yrs [7yr follow up]</p>	<p>Gender/sex, n. Amalgam vs RBC. Male: 137 vs 141; Female: 116 vs 112.</p> <p>Race/ethnicity. Amalgam vs RBC- White: 178 (70%) vs 180 (71%). Non-white: 75 (30%) vs 73 (29%).</p>
Martin 2008 ²⁴	<p>1) Recruited from Casa Pia</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1) should have considerable n.</p>	<p>Children. NR vs NR vs 507 (8-12 yrs at</p>	<p>1) NR</p>	<p>Mean NR- N of subjects with</p>	<p>Considerable number of</p>	<p>1) NR - 1 inclusion criterion is</p>	<p>Children enrolled</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Amalgam vs</p>

	<p>schools. See De Rouen 2006.</p> <p>2) Casa Pia school system in Lisbon, Portugal.</p>	<p>of untreated dental caries but not have had prior exposure to amalgam. Only reporting data 9-17yrs - see detail on missing data. See De Rouen 2006</p>	<p>baseline) from De Rouen 2006 were included.</p>	<p>2) Because of relatively low n. of measurements of urinary creatinine concentrations for ages 8, 18, and 19, only data for ages 9-17 reported. But data from these ages included in overall tests for race, sex, treatment, and age effects. Of 507, n. of subjects with creatine measurements at each age: 9yrs=212, 10yrs=393, 11yrs=463, 12yrs=458, 13yrs=445, 14yrs, -425, 15yrs=402, 16yrs=314, 17yrs=200</p>	<p>creatinine measurements at each age (years): 8 (n=74); 9 (n=212); 10 (n=393); 11 (n=463); 12 (n=458); 13 (n=445); 14 (n=425); 15 (n=402); 16 (n=314); 17 (n=200); 18 (n=59); 19 (n=2).</p>	<p>untreated dental caries.</p>	<p>untreated dental caries</p> <p>2) Dental caries</p>	<p>over an 18-month period [followed for 7yrs from enrolment date]</p>	<p>composite, n, Female 116 vs 112; Male 137 vs 142.</p> <p>Race/ethnicity. Amalgam vs composite, n, Caucasian: 178 vs 181; Black 75 vs 68; Asian 0 vs 5.</p>
Roberts 2008 ²⁵	<p>1) Subset of children from Casa Pia school system (Lisbon). enrolment started 1997 (reported in De Rouen 2006)</p> <p>2) Oral and urine samples were shipped to the University of</p>	<p>See De Rouen 2006</p>	<p>Children. NA vs NA vs NA (n=150 subset from De Rouen 2006 included)</p>	<p>1) Lost to follow up Yr 7: total n=59</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p>Amalgam: 10.4 years (0.8) [NR].</p> <p>RBC: 10.4 years (0.7) [NR]</p>	<p>N of carious surfaces restored at baseline similar in two groups, but more subsequent dental treatment required for children in RBC. N. of surfaces restored at baseline, mean (SD). Amalgam: 9.5 (4.6) vs RBC: 9.0 (6.6).</p>	<p>1) No amalgam</p> <p>2) Carious lesion permanent tooth. Total carious surfaces at baseline, mean (SD) [range]. Amalgam: 15.3 (9.25) [1-49] vs RBC: 14.4 (9.5) [1-49].</p>	<p>8 yrs [7yr follow up]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Amalgam: 37 female (48%), Male 40 (52%), RBC: 36 female (49%), male 37 (51%).</p> <p>Race/ethnicity. Amalgam: White n=65(84%), Black n=10(13%), Asian 2 (3%). RBC: White n=57 (78%), Black n=15</p>

	Washington laboratory.								(21%), Asian n=1 (1%)
Woods 2008 ²⁶	1)See de Rouen 2006. 2)University of Lisbon School of Dental Medicine.	See Lauterbach 2008	Children. 507 randomised from original sample.	1)NR 2) N. of subjects differ between analyses: differences successful assays GST-a, GST-p and albumin, 8yr olds excluded from age group-specific analyses owing to too few subjects in age group	Original study: Mean NR (NR) [8-12yrs] at inception. This paper: Mean NR (NR) [8-18yrs]	NR	1)No amalgam. 2) Carious lesion permanent tooth.	8 yrs [7yr follow up]	Gender, Race/ethnicity. Place of residence. See de Rouen 2006.
Woods 2009 ²⁷	1)See De Rouen 2006. 2)University of Lisbon School of Dental Medicine	See De Rouen 2006	Children. 507 randomised from original sample vs 479 with porphyrin analyses available (237 amalgam, 242 RBC) vs Restricted to 8-9yrs: 195 in final analysis (88 amalgam, 107 RBC)	1)All subjects-Lost from baseline to follow up at Yr 7: n=75 2) NR	Whole sample. Amalgam: 10.0yrs (NR) [8-12], RBC: 10yrs (NR) [8-12]. Restricted sample 8-9yrs: Amalgam 9.1 yrs (NR) [8-9] vs RBC: 9.2 (NR) [8-9].	Mean n. of cavities at baseline. All subjects-amalgam group: 15.6. 8- to 9-yr-olds-amalgam group: 17.8	1)See DeRouen 2006 2)See De Rouen 2006	8 yrs [7yr follow up]	Gender/sex, %. Total (n=242)-Male: 57%. Race/ethnicity. White: 70%
New England Children Amalgam's Trial									
Bellinger 2006 ²⁸	1)NR. A detailed discussion of the design of the NECAT has been previously published ^h 2)New England Research	<u>Inclusion:</u> 1) 6-10 yrs of age, 2) fluent in English 3) no prior/existing amalgam restorations, 4) 2+ occlusal dental caries lesions in posterior teeth. <u>Exclusion:</u> clinical evidence of	Child patient. 5116 vs 598 vs 534 ⁱ (267amalgam vs 267 composite)	1) Amalgam: 42 Withdrew from Trial.-See Fig.1 in paper for specific reasons. Composite: 43 Withdrew from Trial. See Fig.1 in paper for	534. Amalgam vs Composite: 7.9 (1.3) [NR] vs 7.9 (1.4) [NR]	Carious surfaces, mean (SD) [range]: Amalgam: 9.8 (6.9) [2-39], Composite: 9.3 (6.2) [2-36]. Mean n. total caries at baseline: 9.5 decayed tooth surfaces, with 1.7	1)No amalgam. 2) 2+ occlusal dental caries lesions.	Children recruited over 2 year period (1997-1999) [5 years follow-up]	Gender/sex, n (%). Amalgam vs Composite: Female 131 (49.1) vs 156 (58.4). Male 136 (50.9) 111 (41.6). Race/ethnicity^j. n (%) Amalgam vs Composite:

	<p>Institutes, independent Forsyth Institute, Hospital-affiliated dental clinics (affiliated with Franklin Memorial Hospital in Maine, and the Cambridge Health Alliance, Boston University Medical Centre, or Children's Hospital Boston in Massachusetts).</p>	<p>existing psychological, behavioural, neurologic, immunosuppressive, or renal disorders.</p>		<p>specific reasons.</p> <p>2) Amalgam. <u>Available data-Full-scale IQ data:</u> 265 at Baseline, 223 at Year 3, 220 at Year 5, 222 at Baseline and Year 3, 219 at Baseline and Year 5. <u>Renal data:</u> 206 Year 5.</p> <p>Composite. <u>Available data-Full-Scale IQ data:</u> 261 at Baseline, 225 at Year 3, 222 at Year 5, 220 at Baseline and Year 3, 217 at Baseline and Year 5. <u>Renal data:</u> 203 at Year 5. Any missing IQ data not obtained due to a missed visit. Missing renal data due to missed visit or insufficient volume of urine sample.</p> <p><u>Annual neuropsychological outcome data:</u> available for min 75% enrolled</p>		<p>of surfaces being permanent teeth. 54% children had 5 or more teeth with caries that required restoration with rest having 2-4</p>			<p>Non-Hispanic white 165 (64.0) vs 158 (60.3), Non-Hispanic black 49 (19.0) vs 49 (18.7), Hispanic 15 (5.8) vs 23 (8.8), Other 29 (11.2) vs 32 (12.2). Children who withdrew tended to be of minority race, especially Hispanic</p> <p>Place of residence, n (%)^k. Amalgam vs Composite: Boston 144 (53.9) vs 147 (55.1). Maine 123 (46.1) vs 120 (44.9).</p> <p>Education primary caretaker, n (%). Amalgam vs Composite: <High school 34 (13.2) vs 38 (14.6), High school graduate 197 (76.4) vs 194 (74.3), College graduate 18 (7.9) vs 17 (6.5), Postcollege degree 9 (3.5) vs 12 (4.6). Children who withdrew tended to have parents with</p>
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				<p>children except yr 2: data collection hiatus due to funding uncertainty.</p> <p>From all trial participants (n=534). Data available (n). <u>Race and lead</u>: n=520. <u>Income</u>: n= 513; <u>Education and hair mercury</u>: n=519; <u>WISC-III</u>: n= 526. <u>Urinary mercury</u>: n= 498.</p>					<p>lower educational achievement</p> <p>Socioeconomic Status, n (%). Household income [n (%)] ≤ \$20,000: 74 (29.2) vs 86 (33.1) \$20,001–\$40,000: 113 (44.7) vs 109 (41.9) > \$40,000: 66 (26.1) vs 65 (25.0). Children who withdrew tended to have lower parental income.</p>
Barregard 2008 ²⁹	<p>1) Recruited over 2yr period in Boston, Massachusetts and Farmington, Maine.</p> <p>2) Data collection: hospitals.</p>	<p>Child patient. See Bellinger 2006</p> <p><u>Excluded from analyses</u>: children with a) diabetes (n=6) (baseline= 1, follow-up: 5; 3 in each treatment group). b) other kidney disease (n=6) (all postbaseline; 3 in each treatment group c) increased excretion of γ-GT at baseline (amalgam: n=7; composite: n=17</p>	See Bellinger 2006.	<p>1) See Bellinger 2006</p> <p>2) Missing data: At each visit some children did not supply urine sample + some samples too small to permit several analyses, so priority was given to Hg and γ-GT analyses at the laboratory in Rochester. Consequently, total n of results lower for albumin, A1M, and NAG. Sample sizes lower in y2 because of</p>	<p>Amalgam: 7.9 (1.3) [5.9-11.4]. Composite: 7.9 (1.4) [5.9-11.5]</p>	<p>Amalgam vs. composite. Hair Hg [μg/g (mean (SD))] 0.4 (0.5) vs 0.4 (0.5) BPb (baseline blood level) [μg/dL (mean (SD))] 2.4 (1.9) vs 2.3 (1.5) At baseline, children had an average of 9.5 decayed tooth surfaces (range, 2–39)</p>	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	<p>Gender/sex; Race/ethnicity; Education; Socioeconomic Status.</p> <p>See Bellinger 2006.</p>

				<p>funding uncertainty and severe curtailment of data collection.</p> <p>From all trial participants (n=534). Data available (n). <u>Race and lead:</u> n=520. <u>Income:</u> n= 513; <u>Education and hair mercury:</u> n=519; <u>WISC-III:</u> n= 526. <u>Urinary mercury:</u> n= 498.</p>					
Bellinger 2007a [Dental amalgam restorations, neuropsychological] ³⁰	<p>1)Community dental clinics in the Boston/Cambridge, Massachusetts (urban setting) and a dental clinic in Farmington, Maine (rural area).</p> <p>2)Dental clinics.</p>	See Bellinger, 2006.	See Bellinger, 2006	<p>1)NR 2)NR</p>	<p>Amalgam: 7.9 (1.3) [5.9-11.4]. Composite: 7.9 (1.4) [5.9-11.5]</p>	<p>Amalgam vs. composite: <u>Hair Hg</u> [<u>µg/g (mean (SD))</u>] 0.4 (0.5) vs 0.4 (0.5) <u>Urinary Hg</u> [<u>≥ 1.5 ng/mL [no. (%)]:</u> 21 (8.4) vs 11 (4.5) <u>BPb (baseline blood level)</u> [<u>µg/dL (mean (SD))</u>] 2.4 (1.9) vs 2.3 (1.5).</p>	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	Gender/sex; Race/ethnicity. Education; Socioeconomic status. See Bellinger 2006
Bellinger 2007b [dose effect] ³¹	See Bellinger 2007a	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006.	1) Did not include 'some' in the analyses because they dropped out of the study before the end.	See Bellinger 2007a	<p>Amalgam vs composite: <u>Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-Third Edition Full-Scale IQ Score.</u> Mean (SD)</p>	See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	Gender/sex; Race/ethnicity; Education; Socioeconomic Status. See Bellinger 2006.

				2) Did not include 'some' in the analyses because authors could not collect complete data on exposures and outcomes.		[Range] 95.1 (14.5) [65-141] vs 96.1(12.1) [62-123] <u>Urinary Hg</u> (>= 1.5 ng/mL). N (%) - 21 (8.4) vs 11(4.5); <u>Hair Hg</u> (µg/g). Mean (SD) [Range]: 0.4 (0.5) [0.1-4.4] vs 0.4 (0.5) [0.1-4.5]. <u>Blood Lead</u> (µg/dl). Mean (SD) [Range]: 2.4 (1.9) [1-13] vs 2.3 (1.5) [1-11].			
Bellinger 2008 ³²	1) See Bellinger 2007a. 2) NR	See Bellinger 2006	Child patient. 534 from NECAT trial vs 395 children with complete data for CBCL and included in analysis (197 amalgam vs 198 non-amalgam)	1) See Bellinger 2006. 2) Remaining 54 children missing data on baseline or 5-year CBCL scores.	Amalgam: 7.9 (1.4) [6.1-11.5]; Composite: 7.8 (1.3) [6.0-11.2].	Amalgam vs non amalgam Pregnancy exposures: n (%) - <u>Any alcohol</u> : 30 (16.3%) vs 17 (8.8%) <u>Any smoking</u> : 65, (35.3%) vs 76 (39.2%). <u>Any drug use</u> : 7 (3.8%) vs 6 (3.1%). <u>Family stress: mean, (SD)</u> : 10.3 (10.2) vs 6.9 (8.1) <u>Randomization stratum: N (%)</u> Boston, 2-4 caries: 40, (20.3%) vs 31 (15.7%).	See Bellinger 2006.	See Bellinger 2006	Gender/sex. Amalgam vs non amalgam, N (%) <u>Female</u> : 96 (48.7) vs 106 (53.5) <u>Male</u> : 101 (51.3) vs 92 (46.5) Race/ethnicity.^j Amalgam vs non amalgam. N (%) non-Hispanic white: 144 (73.1) vs 146 (73.7). Non-Hispanic black: 40 (20.3) vs 23 (11.6). Hispanic/Other 13 (6.6) vs 29, (14.6) Education of primary caregiver n, %. Amalgam vs non-amalgam. < High school 19 (9.62) vs 23, (11.6)

									<p>High school graduate: 89, (45.2) vs 103, (52.0) College graduate: 63 (32.0) vs 59, (29.8) Post-college degree: 26, (13.2) vs 13 (6.6).</p> <p>Socioeconomic status. Amalgam vs non amalgam Socio-economic status (mean, SD) 53.3 (6.9) vs 52.2, (6.1)</p>
Maserejian 2012 [Dental composite restorations and neuropsychological] ³³	<p>1)See Bellinger 2006. 2) See Bellinger 2006.</p>	<p>See Bellinger 2006. <u>Exclusion:</u> Children missing outcome data.</p>	<p>Children. 5116 vs 598 vs 534 consented (444 had yr5 outcome data, 409 yr4 outcome data)</p>	<p>1)NR 2)Children missing outcome data were excluded from analysis.</p>	<p>8.1 years (1.4) [NR]</p>	<p>From n=444. <u>Blood lead level, mean (SD) ($\mu\text{g/dL}$):</u> 2.3 (1.8) Birth weight, mean (SD): 3360 g (542)</p>	<p>1)No previous restorations. 2) See Bellinger 2006</p>	<p>See Bellinger 2006</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Female: n=237 (53.4%)</p> <p>Race/ethnicity, n (%). Non-Hispanic White: 290 (65.3), Non-Hispanic Black: 88 (19.8%), Hispanic (non-mixed): 30 (6.8%), Other: 36 (8.1%).</p> <p>Place of residence, n (%). Urban (Boston, Mass.): n=229 (51.6%), Rural (Farmington, Maine): 2125 (48.4%).</p>

									<p>SES, n (%). Low: 136 (30.6), Medium: 153 (34.5%), High: 155 (34.9).</p> <p>Other. Drinking water source, n (%): Bottled: 122 (28.1), Tap: 157(36.2), Mixed: 115 (26.5), Don't know: 40 (9.2)</p>
Maserejian 2012 [Dental composite restorations and psychosocial...] 34	<p>1) See Bellinger 2006.</p> <p>2) See Bellinger 2006.</p>	<p>See Bellinger 2006. <u>Exclusion</u>: children missing outcome data.</p>	<p>Children. 5116 vs 598 vs Follow-up data for either BASC-SR or CBCL available for 434 children (81.3% NECAT cohort) vs Final sample sizes for analyses: n = 415 for BASC-SR, and n = 351 for CBCL.</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2) Children missing outcome data were excluded from analysis. Missing data, n (%). <u>Premature birth</u>: n=38(8.8%). <u>Maternal alcohol/illicit drug exposure</u>: n=38 (8.8%). <u>Baseline data on marital status of primary caregiver</u>: n=3. <u>Fruit/vegetable intake</u>: n=3 <u>Gum-chewing frequency</u>: n=3 <u>Baseline blood level</u>: n=7. <u>Birth weight (self-reported by parent)</u>: n= 41.</p>	<p>8.1 years (1.4) [NR]</p>	<p>From n=434. Mean (SD)- Blood lead level ($\mu\text{g/dL}$): 2.3 (1.8) <u>Birth weight</u>: 3361 g (545). <u>N. of carious teeth</u>: 5.2(6.6). <u>N. of carious surfaces</u>: 9.3(6.6). <u>Fruit/veg servings/day</u>: 1.3 (0.6).</p> <p>N (%)- <u>Premature birth</u>: Yes: 51 (11.8), No: 345 (79.5). <u>Gum chewing frequency</u>: Not at all: 30 (7.0), Occasionally: 360 (83.5), Daily: 2.3 (1.8). <u>Maternal/illicit drug exposure during pregnancy</u> - Yes: 142 (327), No: 254 (58.5)</p>	<p>1)No amalgam restorations.</p> <p>2)See Bellinger 2006.</p>	<p>See Bellinger 2006.</p>	<p>Gender/sex. N (%)- Female: 227(52.3), Male: 207 (47.7)</p> <p>Race/ethnicity, n (%)†. Race/ethnicity, n (%) a: Non-Hispanic white 285 (65.7), non-Hispanic black 83 (19.1), Hispanic (non-mixed) 28 (6.5), Other 38 (8.8)</p> <p>Place of residence. Geographic location, n (%): Urban (Boston, MA) 220 (50.7), Rural (Farmington, ME): 214 (49.3)</p> <p>SES, n (%)† - Low: 117 (27.0), Medium: 211 (211)</p>

									(48.6), High: 106 (24.4). Other. Drinking water source, n (%): Bottled: 122 (28.1), Tap: 157(36.2), Mixed: 115 (26.5), Don't know: 40 (9.2).
Maserejian 2012[Dental composites and amalgam and physical health] ³⁵	1)See Bellinger 2006 2) See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Complete data on growth outcomes 2) no self-reported GI disorders (e.g., colitis) that may influence nutritional absorption <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) GI illness (n=1 from amalgam arm), 2) Missing anthropometric data (n=4 from amalgam arm and n=5 from composite arm)	Children. 5116 vs 598 vs 534 randomized vs 474 included in analysis vs. Included in growth outcomes analysis: Amalgam - 117 males, 121 females; Composite: 101 males, 135 females	1)Amalgam arm: 24 withdrew vs Composite arm: 26 withdrew. (See Figure 1 in paper for specific reasons) 2) Missing data, n (%): Amalgam v s Composite: <u>Birth weight data</u> ^m : 37 (14%) vs 32 (12%); <u>Maternal education:</u> 7 (3%) vs 2 (1%), <u>Household income:</u> 8 (3%) vs. 3 (1%). Exploratory analysis of age at menarche was restricted to girls from rural Maine site, because menarche data collection incomplete in the Boston site.	Amalgam: (n=266): 7.5 years (1.3) [NR] Composite: (n=267): 7.4 years (1.4) [NR]	Amalgam vs composite. Mean (SD)- <u>N. of carious teeth:</u> 5.4 (3.0) vs 5.3 (2.8). <u>N. of carious surfaces:</u> 9.8 (6.9) vs 9.2 (6.2). <u>Fruit and vegetable servings/day:</u> 1.3 (0.6) vs 1.3 (0.6). <u>Body fat %:</u> 22.3 (10.3) vs 23.4 (10.7). <u>BMI (kg/m2):</u> 17.9 (3.7) vs 18.1 (4.2). <u>Height, cm:</u> 128.2 (10.4) vs 127.4 (10.3). <u>BMI-by-age Z-score:</u> 0.58 (1.09) vs 0.61 (1.11). N (%) - <u>Birth weight</u> ^m : < 2500g: 12 (5%) vs 17 (6%), 2500-3500g: (48%) vs (48%), >= 3500g: 89 (34%) vs 89 (33%).	1)See Bellinger 2006. 2)See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006	Gender/sex. Total- Males: n=218; Females: n=256. Amalgam vs composite n (%): Female: 131 (49%) vs 156 (58%), Male: 135 (51%) vs 111 (42%). Race/ethnicity, n (%) . ^j Amalgam vs composite- Non-Hispanic White: 165 (62%) vs 161 (60%), Non-Hispanic Black: 54 (20%) vs 54 (20%), Hispanic: 15 (6%) vs 24 (9%), Other: 32 (12%) vs 28 (11%). Place of residence: Geographic location, n (%) Amalgam vs Composite: Urban (Boston, MA): 144 (54%) vs

						<p>At baseline, 35% of boys and 32% of girls in NECAT were overweight or obese.</p>		<p>147 (55%), Rural (Farmington, ME): 122 (46%) 120 (45%).</p> <p>Education. Maternal Education, n (%) Amalgam vs Composite: Less than high school: 34 (13%) vs 39 (15%), High school: 198 (74%) vs 197 (74%), College: 18 (7%) vs 17 (6%), Post-graduate: 9 (3%) vs 12 (5%).</p> <p>SES_Household Income (\$US) - Amalgam vs Composite, n (%): ≤ \$20,000: 78 (29%) vs 89 (33%), \$20,000-40,000: 113 (43%) vs 110 (41%), >\$40,000: 67 (25%) vs 65 (24%).</p> <p>Socio-economic status, n (%)¹, Amalgam vs Composite, n (%)- Low: 83 (31%) vs 86 (32%), Medium: 99 (37%) vs 85 (32%), High 84 (32%) vs 96 (36%)</p>
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									<p>Other. Drinking water source, Amalgam vs Composite, n (%): Bottled: 67 (32%) vs 65 (32%), Tap: 81 (38%) vs 77 (38%), Mixed: 59 (28%) vs 58 (28%), Do not know: 4 (2%) vs 4 (2%).</p>
<p>Maserejian 2014 [Dental sealants and composite restorations]³⁶</p>	<p>1) See Bellinger 2006 2) See Bellinger 2006</p>	<p>See Bellinger 2006. <u>Exclusion:</u> Children missing outcome data.</p>	<p>Children. 257 invited vs 66 (consented: 35 amalgam, 31 composite Data available for analysis: 59 (29 amalgam, 30 composite)</p>	<p>1) NR 2) No immune function data at baseline and/or 5yr follow up: n=7.</p>	<p>N=59. Amalgam: 8.1 years (1.3) [NR], Composite: 8.0 years (1.4) [NR]</p>	<p><u>Asthma</u> (n=11); <u>Allergy</u> (n=9) reported by 29% participants at baseline. Sub study participants similar to those in parent study regarding presence of allergy or asthma and the extent of dental treatment needs. See Shenker2008 for Full details.</p> <p>Overall, baseline counts of lymphocytes and granulocytes within normal reference values. Although 15% and 20%, respectively, fell outside this range, there were no consistent changes in these %s over follow-up, and no</p>	<p>1) See Bellinger 2006 2) See Bellinger 2006</p>	<p>See Bellinger 2006.</p>	<p>Race/ethnicity. Sub study participants were more likely than those in parent study to be non-Hispanic white (89.8% vs. 62.1%).</p> <p>Place of residence. Sub study participants were more likely than those in parent study to be from the rural study site (57.6% vs. 45.5%)</p>

						differences by dental composite/ amalgam treatment group (data not shown). Monocyte counts commonly higher than expected (44%) at baseline.			
Maserejian 2014 [dental sealands and flowable composite restorations] ³⁷	1) See Bellinger 2006 2) See Bellinger 2006	<u>Exclusion</u> : children with missing data on placement of sealants, PRR or both	Children 534 original trial vs 450 in analytic cohort.	1) NR 2) Missing data- baseline data on marital status of primary caregiver: n=3; fruit/vegetable intake: n=3; gum chewing frequency: n=3. Blood lead level: n=7; birth weight: n=1.	7.4 years (1.3) [NR].	Mean (SD)- <u>N. of carious teeth</u> : 5.3 (2.9); <u>N. of carious surfaces</u> : 9.4 (6.7) <u>Fruits and vegetables servings/day</u> : 1.3 (0.6); <u>Blood lead level (mg/dl)</u> : 2.3 (1.8); <u>Birth weight</u> ^o (g): 3340 (543). <u>Body fat (%)</u> : 22.7 (10.4). <u>BMI (kg/m²)</u> : 18.0 (3.9); <u>BMI-by-age Z-score</u> : 0.6 (1.1)	1) No previous amalgam restorations. N. of sealed surfaces, mean (SD) ^p : 4.0 (3.9). N. of children with composite fillings, 15- N. of composite fillings, mean (SD): 0.1 (0.5). 2) Sound pits and fissures of posterior teeth (sealants); shallow, incipient caries that did not extent into dentin (flowable composite); restoration: composite (permanent teeth); compomer (primary teeth).	See Bellinger 2006.	Gender/sex. Female: n=240 (53.3%) Race/ethnicity, n (%) . ^j Race n (%): Non-Hispanic White: 291 (64.7), Non-Hispanic Black: 87 (19.3%), Hispanic (non-mixed): 28 (6.2%), Other: 44 (9.8%). Place of residence: Urban (Boston, Mass.): n=230 (51.1%), Rural (Farmington, Maine): 220 (48.9%). SES, n (%) ^l . Low: 124 (27.6), Medium: 209 (46.4%), High: 117 (26.0). Others. Drinking water source, n (%): Bottled: 119 (30.3), Tap: 153(38.9), Mixed:

									113 (28.8), Don't know: 8 (2.0)
Shenker 2008 ³⁸	1)See Bellinger 2006 2)See Bellinger 2006	See Bellinger 2006 Baseline and follow-up immune function data required.	Children. 257 invited vs 66 consented to participate (35 amalgam, 31 composite) vs 59 included in analysis (29 amalgam, 30 composite)	1)Amalgam: 2 withdrew from parent trial; 4 withdrew immune trial Composite: 1 withdrew from immune trial. See Figure 1 in paper for specific reasons given. 2) Data available for immune function (n, amalgam vs composite): Baseline: 29 vs 30, 5-7 days: 23 vs 24, 6 months: 24 vs 29, 12 months: 17 vs 21, 18 months: 12 vs 17, 5 years: 20 vs 23 From all trial participants (n=534). Data available (n). Race and lead: n=520. Income: n= 513; Education and hair mercury: n=519; WISC-III: n= 526. Urinary mercury: n= 498.	N=59. Amalgam: 8.1 years (1.3) [NR], Composite: 8.0 years (1.4) [NR]	(N=59) Amalgam vs Composite – Ever had asthma, n (%): Yes: 6 (20.7) vs 5 (16.7), No: 23 (79.3) vs 25 (83.3). Ever had allergies, n (%): Yes: 4 (13.8) vs 5 (16.7), No: 25 (86.2) vs 25 (83.3). Hair Hg concentration, mean (SD) [range], ng/mg hair: 0.4 (0.3) [0.1–1.1] vs 0.4 (0.5) [0.1–1.1]. Blood lead concentration, mean (SD) [range], µg/dl: 1.9 (1.4) [1–7] vs 2.2 (1.4) [1–6] [Baseline Immune Data - see paper Table 2]	1)See Bellinger 2006 2)See Bellinger 2006. Carious surfaces, mean (SD)[Range]: 7.8 (5.2) [2–17] vs 10.1 (6.3) [2–27].	See Bellinger 2006	Gender/sex, n (%) Amalgam vs composite: Female: 10 (34.5) vs 19 (63.3); Male: 19 (65.5) vs 11 (36.7). Race/ethnicity, n (%) . Amalgam vs composite: Non-Hispanic White: 26 (89.7) vs 27 (90.0); Non-Hispanic Black: 1 (3.5) vs 1 (3.3); Hispanic: 0 (0) vs 0 (0); Other: 2 (6.9) vs 2 (6.7) Place of residence^k. Amalgam vs Composite, n(%) - Boston: 11 (37.9) vs 14 (46.7); Maine: 18 (62.1) vs 16 (53.3) Education. Primary caretaker, N(%) Amalgam vs composite: < High school: 5 (17.2) vs 7 (23.3), High school graduate: 23 (79.3) vs 22 (73.3), College graduate: 1 (3.5) vs 1 (3.3). SES. Household income, n (%).

									Amalgam vs Composite: ≤\$20,000: 5 (18.5) vs 10 (33.3), \$20,001 – \$40,000: 14 (51.9) vs 13 (43.3), >\$40,000: 8 (29.6) vs 7 (23.3).
<i>Bergen Amalgam Trial</i>									
Bjorkman 2020 ³⁹	1) Amalgam cohort: (patients with MUPS attributed to amalgam restorations.) Patients with longstanding health complaints attributed to dental amalgam fillings and interested to participate instructed to send an application + declarations from patient's dentist and the patient's GP to the study office. These patients expressed their wish to have amalgam fillings removed and had to fill in and sign an application to	All groups. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) 20-70 years 2) permanent residence in Norway 3) ability to comply with the protocol. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) pregnancy, planned pregnancy and lactation. Amalgam cohort. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Health complaints attributed (by the patient) to dental amalgam restorations, 2) ≥ 3 months duration of the health complaints attributed (by the patient) to amalgam restorations, 3) Presence of at least one amalgam filling, 4) Wish to have all amalgam fillings removed, 5) Examination by patient's physician and dentist according to guidelines from the	Adults. Total; Amalgam; MUPS; healthy. 129;49;52;28 recruited and signed informed consent; 95: 37, 33, 25 fulfilled all eligibility criteria and included.	1) Available for analyses 79 (32,28,19) so 16 (5,5,6) lost to follow up. 2) NR	Amalgam (n = 37): 51.0 (7.9) [NR]; MUPS (n= 33): 48.6 (10.4) [NR]; Healthy (n=25): 46.7 (12.8) [NR]	Amalgam vs MUPS vs Healthy, n (%). <u>Smoking habits:</u> No, never ever: 11 (36.7) vs 13 (52.0) vs 5 (45.5) No, stopped less than one year ago: 1 (3.3) vs 1 (4.0) vs 0 (0) No, stopped more than one year ago: 14 (46.7) vs 6 (24.0) vs 3 (27.3). Yes, but not daily 0 (0) vs 2 (8.0) vs 2 (18.2) Yes, daily: 4 (13.3) vs 2 (8.0) vs 1 (9.1) Missing data: 0 (0) vs 1 (4.0) vs 0 (0). <u>Sick leave/sickness benefits:</u> 24 (64.9) vs 21 (63.6) vs 1 (4.0); <u>Self-reported general health complaints, mean (SD), GHC index:</u> 42.4 (17.4) vs 35.4	1) NR (Amalgam cohort had at least one amalgam filling + participants in comparison groups recruited regardless of amalgam status). 2) NR	Recruitment period: 2013-2015 + [The follow-up period was from June 2015 to September 2018]. Total duration of study: 5 years	Gender/sex: Amalgam vs MUPS vs Healthy Female gender, n (%): 22 (59) vs 29 (88) vs 17 (68). Occupation: Amalgam vs MUPS vs Healthy. Sick leave/sickness benefits, n (%); 24 (64.9) vs 21 (63.6) vs 1 (4.0) Education: Amalgam vs MUPS vs Healthy, n (%). Primary and lower secondary school: 3 (8.1) vs 4 (12.1) vs 0 (0); Upper secondary school, vocational program: 10 (27.0) vs 9 (27.3) vs 1 (4.0) Upper secondary school, general program: 4 (10.8) vs 9 (27.3) vs 6 (24.0)

	<p>participate in the study.</p> <p>Comparison group 1(MUPS cohort): patients with MUPS recruited from general practice.</p> <p>Comparison group 2 (Healthy cohort): identified themselves as healthy. Recruited at dental practices. Participants in comparison groups recruited regardless of amalgam status. Recruitment period: March 2013-December 2015. Further details regarding recruitment procedures presented in pp. 1423-1427.</p> <p>2) The Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit</p>	<p>Norwegian Directorate of Health, 6) patient's general practitioner/family physician and dentist assess that the general and dental health of the patient most likely not will deteriorate due to participation in the project, 7) Patient's dentist assesses that there are no major risks for complications following amalgam removal (e.g. need for root canal treatments or extractions.)</p> <p>MUPS cohort. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) No attribution to amalgam and no explicit wish to remove amalgam, 2) ≥ 3 months duration of unspecific health complaints</p> <p>Amalgam and MUPS cohorts. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Diagnosed diseases adequately treated, 2) Subjective symptoms without corresponding objective findings after medical examination(s), including symptoms not explained by</p>				<p>(14.6) vs 10.5 (14.0) <u>SF-36 Physical Component Summary:</u> 35.3 (9.3) vs 37.3 (8.0) vs 54.3 (4.8). <u>SF-36 Mental Component Summary:</u> 45.7 (9.2) vs 47.8 (11.1) vs 53.9 (5.8); Worry about risk for personal health—<u>Dental amalgam fillings:</u> 3.6 (0.9) vs 2.2 (1.2) vs 1.5 (1.0)</p>			<p>Higher education (less than 4 years): 11 (29.7) vs 9 (27.3) vs 6 (24.0) Higher education (4 years or more): 9 (24.3) vs 2 (6.1) vs 12 (48.0)</p> <p>Socioeconomic status. Amalgam vs MUPS vs Healthy. Household yearly income; median group 1000 NOK: 550-750 vs 550-750 vs >1000</p>
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	in Bergen organised in collaboration with Research Unit for General Practice in Bergen, both located at Uni Research Health, Bergen, Norway. Several Regional Dental Centres of Competence appointed for clinical post-treatment examination of patients in Amalgam cohort.	patient's diagnoses, 3) Moderate or severe functional impairment (physician-assessed) <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) life-threatening disease, patients with ongoing cancers, severe cardiopulmonary, neurological or psychiatric diseases (assessed by the GP) 2) organic cause of all complaints. Healthy cohort. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Subjectively healthy (self-assessed) 2) No medication (intake of vitamins and minerals allowed)							
Bjorkman 2023 ⁴⁰	1)Participants in this analysis took part in a prospective cohort study on changes of health complaints after removal of amalgam restorations (see Bjorkman 2020 for details). Target group: patients with MUPS attributed to dental amalgam	All groups. <u>Inclusion:</u> See Bjorkman 2020 Amalgam and MUPS cohort. <u>Inclusion and exclusion:</u> See Bjorkman 2020 (items 3, 4, 5 of inclusion criteria for Amalgam reported in Bjorkman 2020 NR in this study)	Adults. Total: Amalgam, MUPS, healthy. 79: 32, 28, 19 provided data at both baseline and 1 st follow-up vs 66: 30 ,25,11 had data available for analyses	1) 3 patients (amalgam cohort) terminated participation before finished treatment due to health reasons. 2) For smoking habits. Amalgam, n=0; MUPS, n =1 (4%); Healthy, n=0	Amalgam (n=30): 52.5 (7.4) [NR]; MUPS (n=25): 50.3 (10.8) [NR]; Healthy (n=11): 51.3 (11.2) [NR].	Amalgam vs MUPS vs healthy, n (%): <u>Smoking habits-</u> No, never ever: 11 (36.7) vs 13 (52.0) vs 5 (45.5) No, stopped less than one year ago: 1 (3.3) vs 1 (4.0) vs 0 (0). No, stopped more than one year ago: 14 (46.7) vs 6 (24.0) vs 3 (27.3). Yes, but not daily: 0 (0) vs 2 (8.0) vs 2 (18.2). Yes, daily: 4 (13.3) vs.	1)NR (Amalgam cohort had at least one amalgam filling + participants in comparison groups recruited regardless of amalgam status). 2) NR	NR [Follow-up before and 1 year after removal of the fillings.]	Gender/sex: Amalgam (n =30) vs MUPS (n = 25) vs Healthy (n = 11). Female gender, n (%): 18 (60) vs 21 (84) vs 8 (72)

	<p>fillings (Amalgam cohort) had to send application to study office to participate in project.</p> <p>2) Dental setting: GP.</p>					<p>2 (8.0) vs. 1 (9.1) Missing data: 0 (0) vs 1 (4.0) vs 0 (0); <u>GHC index, mean (SD)</u>. At baseline (Q1): 43.6 (18.0) vs 37.5 (14.5) vs 9.2 (16.8).</p>			
Sinha 2024 ⁴¹	<p>1)Amalgam cohort: sent application to study office; MUPS cohort: recruited via family physician/GP Healthy cohort: via dentists participating in project</p> <p>2) Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit in Bergen, Norway.</p>	See Bjorkman 2020.	<p>Adult. Amalgam cohort- 59 applied vs 37 eligible vs 32 had fillings removed and responded to Q2, 22 responded to Q3; MUPS cohort: 52 signed informed consent vs 33 eligible vs 28 responded to Q1, Q2, 22 responded to Q3; Healthy cohort: 28 signed informed consent vs 19 in analysis as responded both to Q1 and Q2, 12 responded to Q3.</p>	<p>1) Amalgam cohort: 10 lost from Q2 to Q3. MUPS cohort: 6 lost from Q2 TO Q3; Healthy cohort: 6 lost from Q1 to Q2, 7 lost from Q2 to Q3</p> <p>2)Data for local complaints were not available for the MUPS cohort.</p>	<p>Amalgam (n=32): 52.1 years (7.5) [20-70], MUPS (n=28): 49.9 years (10.3) [20-70], Healthy (n=19): 46.9 years (13.1) [20-70].</p>	<p>Amalgam vs MUPS vs Healthy. <u>General health complaints at baseline: mean (SD):</u> 43.3 (17.8), vs 36.6 (14.2), vs 10.0 (15.0); <u>Smoking habits, n(%):</u> No, never ever: 13 (40.6%) vs 15 (55.6%) vs 11 (57.9%), No, stopped <1yr ago: 1 (3.1%) vs 1 (3.7%) vs 0 (0.0%), No, stopped >1yr ago: 14 (43.8%) vs 6 (22.2%) vs 5 (26.3%), Yes, but not daily: 0 (0.0%) vs 3 (11.1%) vs 2 (10.5%), Yes, Daily: 4 (12.5%) vs 2 (7.4%) vs 1 (5.3%)</p>	<p>1)Amalgam cohort: amalgam restorations.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Participant recruitment March 13- Dec 15 [5 years]</p>	<p>Amalgam cohort vs MUPS cohort vs Healthy cohort, n(%):</p> <p>Gender/sex. - Male: 13 (40.6%), vs 4 (14.3%), vs 6 (31.6%); Female: 19 (59.4%) vs 24 (85.7%) vs 13 (68.4%).</p> <p>Education 1ry and 2ry school: 3 (9.4%) vs 3(10.7%) vs 0 (0%); upper 2ry school, vocational program: 9 (28.1%) vs7 (25.0%) vs 1 (5.3) ; upper 2ry school, general program: 2 (6.3%) vs 7 (25.0%) vs 4 (21.1%); higher education (less than 4 years): 1 (34.4%) vs 9 (32.1%) vs 6 (31.6%); Higher education (4 years or more): 7</p>

									(21.9%) vs 2 (7.1%) vs 8 (42.1%).
Sjursen 2011 ⁴²	<p>1) Participants recruited from patients examined at the Norwegian Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit in the period 1993–1999. Majority of patients referred to unit because of health complaints attributed to amalgam fillings identified by either patient or referring physician/ dentist.</p> <p>2) Norwegian Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit.</p>	<p>Inclusion:</p> <p>1) Referred to: see recruitment method, 2) Amalgam fillings still present 3) No diagnosed contact allergy to substances in resin-based dental materials 4) Health complaints from 3 ≤ organ systems. 5) Data on Hg in blood and urine from initial examination, 6) 25–55 yrs. at initial examination 7) Accepted to be contacted in follow-up study</p> <p>Exclusion (treatment group and reserves):</p> <p>1) Severe medical disorders (e.g. MS, ALS, severe RA), 2) Severe food allergies 3) Psychological difficulties or psychiatric disorders that could influence dental treatment 4) Complicated therapy (severe periodontitis, high caries activity and/or need for complicated dental rehabilitation – e.g. bridges), 5) Inclusion</p>	<p>Adult. 358 of original 368 referred asked to complete follow up questionnaire (207 returned questionnaires) vs 50 vs 50 (20 amalgam group; 10 reserve; 20 no treatment)</p>	<p>1) N=1 could not attend 3-month follow-up; n=1 could not attend the 3-year follow-up</p> <p>2) Treatment group - For analysis of changes in health complaints from Q1 to 3-year follow-up, data from 19 participants analysed. For repeated measures analysis, data from 18 participants analysed (Fig. 1).</p>	<p>°Treatment group vs Reference group vs Excluded from treatment group: Age (years) in September 2000: 46.9 (6.7) [NR] vs 44.7 (6.5) [NR] vs 52.6 (7.0) [NR]</p>	<p>°Treatment group vs Reference group vs Excluded from treatment group. <u>Concentration of Hg, mean (SD)-</u> Blood (nmol L-1): 23.5 (10.4) vs 27.5 (12.5) vs 33.0 (22.1) Urine (nmol L-1): 24.0 (17.6) vs 22.0 (19.7) Urine (nmol per mmol creatinine): 2.7 (1.9) 2.6 (2.7) 2.4 (2.3) <u>Self-reported health complaints, mean (SD)-</u> Intra-oral index: 8.4 (6.6) vs 13.0 (12.0) vs. 11.2 (7.2) Extra-oral index 6.9 (8.4) vs 11.0 (9.3) vs 9.2 (8.0) General index 41.5 (16.0) vs 47.3 (21.2) vs 42.3 (15.0)</p>	<p>1) Treatment group vs Reference group vs Excluded from treatment group. N. of amalgam surfaces, mean (s.d.): 36.8 (11.1) vs 38.0 (11.3) vs 27.2 (16.3)</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p>8 years (2000-2007) and follow up three years (but last date is 2008)</p>	<p>°Treatment group (n = 20) vs Reference group (n = 20) vs Excluded from treatment group (n = 10).</p> <p>Gender/sex. - Women, n (%): 14 (70) vs 16 (80) vs 8 (80).</p> <p>Occupation/disability. On sick leave or disability pension, n (%): 9 (45) vs 7 (35) vs 9 (90).</p> <p>Education. Years, mean (s.d.): 11.5 (3.6) vs 11.3 (2.8) vs 10.3 (2.6).</p>

		criteria no longer fulfilled							
Bjorkman 2012 ⁴³	<p>1)Patients: Previously examined by dentists and physicians at the Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit in Bergen, Norway. Referred from dentist and physicians.</p> <p>Controls: samples retrieved from existing biobank.</p> <p>2)Patients: Data collection: dental surgeries.</p> <p>Controls: see recruitment method.</p>	<p>Patients. Inclusion: Patients with health complaints attributed to their amalgam restorations. See Sjursen 2011.</p> <p>Controls. Inclusion: blood donors matched for age and gender.</p>	<p>Adult patients: 20 referred vs.20 vs. 20 consented</p> <p>Blood donors: samples retrieved from 20 controls.</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Patients - at pre-treatment examination 49 (6.7) [NR];</p> <p>Blood donors (comparison group) - 54 (6.4) [NR]</p>	<p>Patients: 1) no signs of lichenoid contact lesions to amalgam restorations or other dental materials. 2) no patients had medication which was assessed to have influence on the serum levels of the analysed cytokines.</p>	<p>1)Amalgam: At pre-treatment examination, the mean number of amalgam surfaces was 23.5 (SD 10.6)</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>NR [12 months follow-up in total (also at 3 months)]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Patients- Men: 6; women:14</p> <p>Blood donors (comparison groups)- Men: 6; women: 14.</p>
Bjorkman 2017 ⁴⁴	<p>1)See Sjursen 2011. Referred to the Norwegian Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit for examination of health complaints attributed to amalgam fillings.</p>	<p>See Sjursen 2011.</p>	<p>Adult patient. NR vs NR vs 20 (See Sjursen 2011).</p>	<p>1) n=1 could not attend the 3-month follow-up, and n=1 could not attend the 3-year follow-up.</p> <p>2) Some participants did not answer all questions in the questionnaires at all follow-ups, and thus,</p>	<p>At study start treatment group: 48.9 (6.7) [NR].</p>	<p>See Sjursen 2011</p>	<p>1)Amalgam</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p>Recruitment period 6 years (1993-1999) [5 years follow-up]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Women: 14; Men: 6</p> <p>Occupation. Working full/part time: n=15 (4 on sick leave) Full-time disability pensions n=3. Part-time disability pension + part-time work: n=2.</p>

	2)Norwegian Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit.			there are some missing data.					<p>Education. n of years of education: 11.5 yrs (SD 3.6).</p> <p>Disability: Full-time disability pensions: n=3. Part-time disability pension + part-time work: n=2.</p>
German Amalgam Trial									
Melchart 2008 ⁴⁵	<p>1)Reports in local newspapers</p> <p>2)University of Munich Unit of Dentistry</p>	<p>Inclusion: 1) persons with dental amalgam restorations who suspected their health complaints caused by dental amalgam; 1) reported at 10 ≤ symptoms (including 3 ≤ of strong intensity) 3) 20-50 y/o.</p> <p>Exclusion: 1) persons with bridges, crowns, or gold inlays; 2) having undergone unsuccessful endodontic treatment; 3) having relevant organic, allergic, or mental disorders; 4) inability to understand study; 5) alcohol/ drug abuse; pregnancy/ lactation; 6) participation in any clinical research study in preceding 3 months.</p>	<p>Adults. 1200 vs 91 vs 90 randomized.</p>	<p>1)N=1 randomized to removal group dropped out before treatment without complete baseline data on dental status. (90 people in the ITT population)</p> <p>N=2 in removal group N=2 in removal-plus n=8 in non-removal group withdrew or lost to follow-up at month 12. (See Figure 1 in paper for specific reasons).</p> <p>2)Statistical testing of main outcome measure performed on the ITT</p>	<p>'Group A (removal of amalgam): 33.2 years (6.0) [NR];</p> <p>Group B (amalgam removal plus 'biological detoxification': 34.8 years (6.0) [NR];</p> <p>Group C (no amalgam removal): 35.1 years (6.4) [NR].</p>	<p>'Amalgam removal group vs amalgam removal plus group vs no amalgam removal group, mean (SD).</p> <p>BMI: 24.0 (3.6) vs. 25.2 (5.5); vs. 23.7 (3.2);</p> <p>SAM private self-consciousness: 5.4 (1.8) vs 5.3 (1.6) vs 5.0 (1.6);</p> <p>SAM public self-consciousness: 5.6 (1.8) vs 6.0 (1.6) vs 5.1 (1.5).</p> <p>FPI-R introversion: 4.4 (1.7) vs 4.4 (1.7) vs 4.3 (1.8).</p> <p>FPI-R neuroticism: 5.3 (1.9) vs 5.6 (1.7) vs 5.2 (1.7).</p> <p>Main complaints since (yrs): 12.3 (7.2) vs 12.3 (7.6)</p>	<p>1)'N.of amalgam restoration surfaces, mean (SD)- removal group: 21.0 (10.6); removal plus: 23.4 (11.8); no removal: 20.4 (9.6)</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Participants included between April 1998-July 2002 [18 months]</p>	<p>'Amalgam removal group vs amalgam 'plus' vs no amalgam removal group.</p> <p>Gender/sex. Female: 47% vs 45% vs 48%. Male: 53% vs 55% vs 52%.</p> <p>Occupation. Employment, n (%) -26 (87%) vs 24 (83%) vs. 28 (90%).</p> <p>Education, n (%). Grammar school completed:13 (43%) vs 17 (59%) vs 15 (48%) University degree: 7 (23%) vs 9 (31%) vs 7 (23%).</p> <p>Features of relationships. One person household, n (%):</p>

				<p>population, with missing data replaced with baseline values (thus setting the differences compared with baseline to zero) by analysis of variance. Missing data/outcome reported Table 2.</p>	<p>vs 11.2 (7.7) 0.842.</p> <p>Baseline values for outcome measurements.</p> <p><u>Main complaints sum score:</u> 6.9 (1.1) vs. 7.4 (1.0) vs. 7.3 (0.8); <u>Total symptom score (0-150)</u>- 41.3 (15.1) vs. 44.9 (17.1) vs. 35.8 (13.3);</p> <p><u>N. of complaints (0-50):</u> 24.8 (8.0) vs. 26.4 (8.4) vs. 21.9 (7.6);</p> <p><u>N. of strong complaints (0-50):</u> 5.3 (3.2) vs. 5.9 (4.0) vs. 4.7 (2.3);</p> <p><u>SF-36 physical health:</u> 47.0 (11.3) vs. 46.1 (8.1) vs. 47.9 (9.2);</p> <p><u>SF-36 mental health:</u> 44.2 (10.8) vs.. 43.1 (9.2) vs. 45.5 (11.2);</p> <p><u>SCL-90-R Global Severity Index:</u> 57.4 (6.8) vs. 58.8 (8.2) vs. 56.3 (8.3)</p> <p><u>KKG internal locus of control:</u> 52.8 (9.5) vs.. 48.1 (9.5) vs.. 49.4 (12.2)</p> <p><u>KKG external locus of control:</u> 55.3 (12.5) vs</p>	<p>12 (40%) vs 8 (28%) vs 10 (32%)</p>
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						<p>54.5 (10.2) vs 53.4 (9.7) <u>KKG fatalistic externality</u>: 49.0 (11.3) vs 49.7 (11.2) vs. 50.8 (14.6) Baseline Hg levels- <u>Total in blood plasma (ng/mL)</u>: 0.80 (0.40) vs. 0.80 (0.61) vs. 0.76 (0.31); <u>Inorganic in blood plasma (ng/mL)</u>: 0.60 (0.35) vs 0.59 (0.54) vs 0.57 (0.25) <u>Total in erythrocytes (ng/mL)</u>: 1.81 (2.00) vs.. 1.70 (1.86) vs. 1.75 (1.36) <u>Inorganic in erythrocytes (ng/mL)</u>: 0.54 (0.36) vs 0.53 (0.46) vs 0.52 (0.29) <u>In urine (ng/mL)</u>: 2.05 (1.83) vs. 2.08 (2.69) vs. 2.09 (1.52). <u>In urine excretion (ng/8hrs)</u>: 733.3 (545.1) vs 851.8 (991.5) vs 829.3 (569.1) [See Appendix for group N/outcome at baseline]</p>			
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<p>Weidenhammer 2009⁴⁶</p>	<p>1) Sample 1 (amalgam group): 90 patients out of a randomized trial (See Melchart 2008): to compare the reduction of subjective complaints by 3 treatment regimens (conventional removal of dental amalgam, removal plus biologic detoxification, health promotion program without removal) recruited from 1999 to 2002. Sample 2 (other group): Our database of 309 environmental outpatients existing from 1998-2000 screened for patients' causal attributions for their complaints. 2) Sample 1: NR; Sample 2: NA</p>	<p>Sample 1. Inclusion and Exclusion: See Melchart 2008. Sample 2. Inclusion: 1) patients identified attributing their complaints to diverse environmental chemicals such as solvents, pesticides, or timber preservatives, but not Hg from dental restorations. 2) patients aged 20-50 and complete data sets were selected for analysis (for matching)</p>	<p>Adults. Sample 1 + sample 2: NR + 309 patients in database vs NR + 211 (patients not attributing complaints to Hg from dental restorations) vs 90 +116 included (age matched)</p>	<p>1) Sample 1: NR; Sample 2: NA 2) "Other causes" group had no available data on amalgam surfaces</p>	<p>Amalgam (n=90): 34.4 years (6.1) [22-50] vs other causes (n=116): 37.5 years (7.9) [18-50] p<0.01</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>1) Amalgam surfaces- mean (SD) [range]. Amalgam (n=90): 21.6 (10.6) [1-45]; Other causes (n=116): Data not available 2) NR</p>	<p>Sample 1 - recruited 1999-2002 [NR] Sample 2 - database of environmental outpatients existing from 1998-2000 [NR]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Amalgam (n=90) vs other causes (n=116), n (%) Female: 42 (46.7) vs 72 (62.1), p<0.05; Male: 48 (53.3) vs 44 (37.9), p<0.05. Occupation. Amalgam (n=90) vs other causes (n=116), n (%). Employment: 78 (86.7) vs 93 (80.2), p= 0.22. Education. Amalgam (n=90) vs other causes (n=116), n (%). > 12 school years: 45 (50.0) vs 36 (31.0), p< 0.01.</p>
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<p>Weidenhammer 2010⁴⁷</p>	<p>1) Post hoc analysis refers to 90 patients from a randomized trial (See Melchart 2008) which compared the effects of 3 treatment regimens (conventional removal of dental amalgam, removal plus biologic detoxification, health promotion program without removal) on subjective complaints.</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p><u>Inclusion and Exclusion:</u> See Melchart 2008.</p>	<p>Adults. NR vs NR vs 90</p>	<p>1) 12 patients withdrew not included in analysis</p> <p>2) Sporadically missing data at month 12 (<7% of patients) were replaced by the arithmetic mean of the corresponding variable to avoid different sample configurations because of missing data of the variables in the analysis.</p>	<p>Removal (n = 55) vs No removal (n = 78). 34.2 yrs (6.0) [NR] vs. 35.4 yrs (6.3) [NR] vs 34.6 yrs (6.1) [NR], p= 0.42</p>	<p>Removal (n = 55) vs No removal (n = 23) Total (n = 78).</p> <p><u>BMI</u>- 24.4 (4.4) vs 23.9 (3.3) vs 24.2 (4.1), p= 0.64.</p> <p><u>Duration of complaints (years)</u>- 10.4 (4.8) vs 8.4 (5.0) vs 9.8 (4.9), p= 0.10; <u>FPI extraversion</u>- 4.3 (1.7) vs 4.5 (1.9) vs 4.4 (1.7), p= 0.60.</p> <p><u>FPI emotional instability</u>- 5.5 (1.7) vs 5.3 (1.8) vs 5.4 (1.7), p= 0.70.</p> <p><u>Symptom score:</u> 42.8 (15.9) vs 32.8 (10.2) vs 39.9 (15.1), p <0.01; <u>SCL-90 GSI psych. distress</u>-58.1 (7.5) vs 55.7 (8.7) vs 57.4 (7.9), p= 0.22.</p> <p><u>SCL-90 GSI psych. Distress:</u> 58.1 (7.5) 55.7 (8.7) 57.4 (7.9) 0.22.</p> <p><u>SF-36 physical comp score</u>- 47.2 (9.4) vs 49.2 (9.4) vs 47.8 (9.4), p= 0.41.</p> <p><u>SF-36 physical comp. score:</u> 47.2 (9.4) 49.2 (9.4) 47.8 (9.4), p= 0.41.</p>	<p>1) Removal (n = 55) vs No removal (n = 23) Total (n = 78).</p> <p>N. of amalgam filling surfaces, mean (SD): 21.9 (10.9) vs 22.9 (8.9) vs 22.2 (10.3), p= 0.70.</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p>Sample 1 - recruited 1999-2002</p> <p>Sample 2 - database of environmental outpatients existing from 1998-2000 [12 months follow-up]</p>	<p>Gender/sex.</p> <p>Removal (n = 55); vs No removal (n = 23) vs. Total (n = 78). Female: 43.6% vs 43.5% vs. 43.6%, p= 0.99.</p> <p>Occupation.</p> <p>Removal (n = 55) vs No removal (n = 23) vs Total (n = 78). Employed- 83.6% vs 95.7% vs. 87.2%, p= 0.15.</p> <p>Education.</p> <p>Removal (n = 55) vs. No removal (n = 23) vs. Total (n = 78). High educational level (>12 years): 47.3% vs. 43.5% vs. 46.2%, p= 0.76</p>
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						<p>SF-36 mental comp score: 43.2 (9.9) vs 45.8 (10.6) vs 44.0 (10.1), p= 0.31.</p> <p>Hg total in erythrocytes (ng/ml): 1.81 (1.97) vs 1.85 (1.47) vs 1.82 (1.83), p= 0.93.</p> <p>Inorg. Hg in plasma (ng/ml): 0.60 (0.47) vs 0.61 (0.25) vs 0.61 (0.41), p=0.90;</p> <p>Hg in urine (ng/ml): 2.11 (2.31) vs 2.09 (1.36) vs 2.10 (2.06), p= 0.98</p>			
Ahlgren, 2014 ⁴⁸	<p>1) Consecutive patients referred for suspicion of OLL invited to participate.</p> <p>2) Patients (OLL group)- referred to a) Oral and Maxillofacial Unit in Halmstad, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery and Oral Medicine, Faculty of Odontology at Malmö</p>	<p>Patients (OLL group)- Inclusion: Fulfilled revised WHO criteria. Exclusion: 1) current systemic corticosteroid treatment, 2) lesions limited to the gingiva 3) age < 20 yrs.</p> <p>Control 1 (dermatitis patients). Inclusion: age and gender matched dermatitis patients. Exclusion: 1) referred for suspicion of oral mucosal problems or adverse reactions to dental materials 2)</p>	<p>Adult OLL patients: 96 referred vs 95 vs 83</p> <p>Control 1 (dermatitis patients): 154 referred vs 148 vs 83.</p> <p>Control 2 (patients selected from files): 319 patients selected from database</p>	<p>1) OLL patients: 13 withdrawals/ineligible (See Fig 1 in paper for specific reasons).</p> <p>Control 1: 71 withdrawals/ineligible (See Fig 1 in paper for specific reasons).</p> <p>2) Missing data: 44 controls from group 1 did not complete medical questionnaire (general and</p>	<p>OLL patients: 60 (NR)[32-83yrs]</p> <p>Control 1: 56.5(NR)[2183yrs] Control 2: NR</p>	NR	<p>Amalgam fillings- OLL patients: n=74 (89%) Group 1 (Dermatitis patients): n=73 (88%).</p>	<p>2005-2008: 3 years [NA]</p>	<p>Gender/sex, %: OLL group- female: 65.1%. Control 1)- female: 72.3%; Control 2: NR (Age/gender matched to OLL group)</p>

	<p>University, OR b) to Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Skåne University Hospital, Malmö.</p> <p>Controls: group 1 (dermatitis patients) referred to Department of Occupational and Environmental Dermatology, Skåne University Hospital, Malmö, Sweden. OR group 2 (patients selected from files) Randomly selected from the database used for registration of patch test results at Department for Control group 1</p>	<p><20 yrs 3) under systemic corticosteroid treatment.</p> <p>Control 2 (patients selected from files): Inclusion: 1) patch- tested dermatitis patients randomly selected from files. 2) age/gender match to OLL group. Exclusion: tested with dental series and cheilitis series.</p>		<p>oral health, current medication and skin problems). Answered questions on oral health so patients with allergic oral symptoms caused by dental materials could be excluded</p>					
<p>Cabana-Munoz 2015⁴⁹</p>	<p>1)NR 2)NR</p>	<p>Amalgam group. Inclusion: 1) Women with ≤ 4 dental amalgam fillings 2) women subject with >4 dental fillings. All had dental amalgam</p>	<p>NR vs 55 vs 55 (42 amalgam fillings + 13 controls)</p>	<p>1)NR. 2)NR</p>	<p>44 (NR) [NR]</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>1)Dental amalgam fillings: 42 (all had fillings for at least 10 years; average 15 years). ≤ 4 fillings (n = 27); >4 fillings (n=15);</p>	<p>NR [NA]</p>	<p>Gender/sex: Women: 100%</p> <p>Socioeconomic status: Patients (women) had a</p>

		<p>fillings for 10 ≤ years</p> <p>Controls. Inclusion: women without dental amalgam fillings matched in similar age range.</p> <p>All women. Inclusion: 1) Absence of psychiatric disease 2) no previous history of DMSA use 3) women untreated with prescription chelators 4) any current treatment for iron deficiency (anaemia), 5) No history of liver/ kidney disease.</p> <p>Exclusion: 1) Physically handicapped women with metabolic diseases or progressive neurological disorders (4th Edition, DSM IV) 2) taking regular medication such as stimulants, anticonvulsants, and atypical antipsychotic drugs.</p>					<p>Controls: (no amalgam fillings) (n=13)</p> <p>2)NR</p>		<p>medium/higher sociocultural status.</p>
<p>Cabana-Munoz 2019⁵⁰</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Patients. Inclusion: dental titanium implants + amalgams (A + I) for 10 ≤ years + those with long-term dental amalgams alone.</p> <p>Controls. Inclusion:</p>	<p>NR vs 130 vs 130 (54 A + I ; 51 amalgam only; 25 controls)</p>	<p>1)NR.</p> <p>2)NR.</p>	<p>(A + I): 58; amalgams only: 49; controls: 42^s</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>1)A + I for at least 10 years: n= 54 (average: 17 years in mouth); long-term dental amalgams alone: n= 5. Controls without implants: n=25.</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>Gender/sex: Women: 60%</p> <p>SES: All recruited patients have a medium/high sociocultural status .</p>

		without implants and/or dental amalgams. Age-matched. All participants. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) titanium implants alone; 2) periodontal disease 3) metabolic diseases/diabetes; neurological/psychiatric disorders 4) Patients taking chelators or other chronic medications (stimulants, anticonvulsants, antidepressants or psychiatric/bipolar drugs), 5) history of metabolic disease (liver, kidney disease, lupus), 6) patient tattoos.					2)NR		Place of residence: 80% are from Murcia and 20% from Alicante. ^c
Chen 2020 ⁵¹	1)2010 LHID: info. of 1 million people selected randomly from beneficiaries registered compulsory NHI procedure in Taiwan, covering 99.9% of Taiwanese population in 2010. 2)NA	Patients. Inclusion: 1) Adults who had received ≥ 3 consensus diagnoses of PD, 2) outpatient between 2000-2013. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) <20 years, 2) withdrawn from NHI procedure, 3) missing data in 2010 LHID. Controls: Inclusion: Propensity score matching by 1:1 ratio according to urbanization level, CCI, age, socioeconomic status, and sex.	Adults. LHID2010: 1 million vs 823,547 Outpatient between 2000-2013 from NHIRD for year 2010 (PD: n=6,950; No PD: N=816, 597) vs Matched (1:1)- PD: n=5,712; No PD: n=5712.	1)NA. 2)NR	76.87 (11.473) [NR]	Total population (n, %): CCI. Score 0: 515 (4.51%), Score 1: 1106 (9.68%), Score 3 or above: 8161 (71.44%). No sig difference case vs control.	1)Amalgam fillings, n (%). With PD: 2184 (38.24); Without PD: 2108 (36.90); No amalgam fillings, n (%). With PD: 3528 (61.76); Without PD: 3604 (63.10); 2)NR	NR. LHID2010 contains raw insurance claims data and registration documents for 2000–2013.	Gender/sex. Total population- Female: 5806 (50.82%), Male: 5618 (49.18%). SES. Total population: Monthly income (n, %)- <NT\$ 20,000: 9481 (82.99%), NT\$ 20,000-40,000: 1235 (10.81%), >NT\$40,000: 708 (6.2%). No sig difference case vs control. Place of residence. Total

									population-Urban: 6378 (55.83%), Suburban: 3596 (31.48%), Rural: 1450 (12.69%). No sig difference case vs control
Chen 2021 ⁵²	<p>1)Patients: 2010 LHID.</p> <p>Comparison subjects: from random sample general population.</p> <p>2) NA</p>	<p>Patients. Inclusion:</p> <p>1) Outpatient between 2000-2013</p> <p>2) ≥ 3 consensus diagnoses of pSS (ICD-9-CM).</p> <p>Exclusion: 1) <18 yrs, 2) incomplete medical records, or missing data 3) autoimmune diseases e.g. systemic lupus erythematous, dermatomyositis, polymyositis, rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis. Conditionally.</p> <p>Comparison subjects. Inclusion: Matched by sex, age, urbanization level, socioeconomic status, and comorbidities using the propensity score method at 1:1 ratio.</p>	<p>Adults.LHID2010: 1 million vs 781,566 outpatient between 2000-2013 from NHIRD for year 2010 after exclusion criteria (PSS n=5,985; No PSS n=775, 581) vs Matched (1:1)-PSS: n=5848; No PSS n=5848.</p>	<p>1)NA</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p>Total population: 58.27 (17.23) [NR]. No sig. difference between case vs controls.</p>	<p>Total population. Comorbid diseases (n. %).</p> <p>Alcoholism: 99 (0.85%), CAD: 2468 (21.1%), DM: 797 (6.81%), Hyperlipidaemia: 422 (3.61%), Hypertension: 5791 (49.51%), Obesity: 15 (0.13%), Tobacco use disorder: 2732 (23.36%).</p> <p>No sig differences between case vs controls.</p>	<p>1)Amalgam fillings. pSS patients: 3282; no pSS patients: 3324;</p> <p>No amalgam. pSS patients: 2566 no Pss patients: 2524.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>NR.</p> <p>LHID2010 contains raw insurance claims data and registration documents for 2000–2013.</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Total population-Female: 8456 (72.30%), Male: 3240(27.7%). No sig difference case vs control.</p> <p>SES. Total population-Monthly income (n.%)- <NT\$ 20,000: 8891 (76.02%), NT\$ 20,000-40,000: 1860 (15.9%), >NT\$40,000: 945 (8.08%) No sig difference case vs control.</p> <p>Place of residence. Total population-Urban: 7252 (62%), Suburban: 3535 (30.22%), Rural: 909 (7.77%). No sig difference case vs control</p>
Daume 2021 ⁵³	<p>1)Patients with clinical and histological features of</p>	<p>Inclusion: diagnosis of oral lichen planus (reticular and non-reticular) - clinical</p>	<p>112 patients recruited and participated</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>60.00 (10.07) [58.00-61.99]</p>	<p>Patients had either 'reticular OLP' or 'non-reticular OLP'.</p>	<p>1)In 112 participants, n (%):</p>	<p>NA</p>	<p>Gender/sex, n (%). Female: 91 (81.25); Male: 21 (18.75)</p>

	<p>oral lichen planus from the Department of Cranio-Maxillofacial Surgery at the University Hospital of Münster</p> <p>2) Department of Cranio-Maxillofacial Surgery at the University Hospital of Münster.</p>	<p>signs were documented with photos and diagnosis was confirmed with a biopsy.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> 1) patients with other confirmed oral mucosal diseases; 2) patients after radiotherapy</p>				<p>Non-reticular form included all patients with erosive-ulcerative, bullous and atrophic OLP. Papular and plaque OLP did not occur in the patients examined. Distinction made between "local" and "generalized" presentation form of disease. If OLP visible in >3 sites in oral cavity="generalized" presentation form.</p>	<p><u>Composite:</u> 95, (84.8) <u>Amalgam:</u> 55, (49.1) <u>Ceramic:</u> 81 (72.3) <u>Gold:</u> 47 (42.0) <u>Non-precious metal:</u> 69 (61.6)</p> <p>2)NR</p>		<p>Significantly more women were examined (p<0.05).</p>
<p>Dermata 2018⁵⁴</p>	<p>1)Patients at the postgraduate clinic.</p> <p>2)Department of Paediatric Dentistry, Dental School, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece.</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Healthy (ASA I, II) and co-operative (Frankl 3, 4), 2) 4.0–7.5 yrs 3) min. one first/second primary molar requiring class II restoration.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> 1) Carious lesions that invaded inner third of dentine 2) teeth requiring multi-surface restorations.</p>	<p>Child patient.65 assessed for eligibility vs 55 people/124 teeth vs. 48 people/ 114 teeth received intervention/control (Z250 n=23 patients/55 teeth; Vitremer (RMGIC) n=25 patients/61 teeth) vs. Analysed at 2 yrs: 44 (Z250 n=21 patients/49 teeth; Vitremer n=23 patients/55 teeth).</p>	<p>1)Dropouts at 6 months: Z250 n=5 patients/8 teeth; Vitremer n=2 patients/2 teeth. <u>Lost to follow-up at 12 months:</u> Z250: n=2 patients/4 teeth Vitremer: n=2 patients/6 teeth. (See Figure 1 in paper for further detail).</p> <p>1 Vitremer restoration lost at 12 months vs 3 Z250 at 24 months</p>	<p>Both groups: 80.7 months (15.5) [NR]. Composite resin: 80.5 months (15.3) [NR]; Vitremer (RMGIC): 81.0 months (16.0) [NR].</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>1)Restorations/patient. One, Two, Three, Four, Five, Six, n (%). <u>Overall:</u> 17 (31%), 22(40), 5(9), 8 (15), 2(4), 1 (2). <u>Z250:</u> 8 (29), 12 (43), 3 (11), 5 (18), 0 (0), 0 (0). <u>Vitremer:</u> 9 (33), 10 (37), 2 (7), 3 (11), 2 (7), 1 (4).</p> <p>2) First/second primary molar requiring class II restoration. 113 (60 first and 52 second) primary molars evaluated at 12-month follow-up, VS. 104</p>	<p>[2yrs follow-up.]</p>	<p>Gender/sex, n (%). Girls: 31 (56%); Boys: 24 (44%).</p>

				2)NR			(58 first and 51 second) primary molars evaluated at 24-month follow-up. 124 Class II restorations placed, 61 Z250 vs 63 Vitremer		
Eyson 2010 ⁵⁵	1) Records obtained from consecutive patients specifically presenting to the Oral Medicine Unit at Guy's Hospital during 2003-04. 2) NA. See recruitment method.	Patients. Inclusion: 1) Consecutive patients presenting to Unit during 2003-04, 2) belief their oral/medical symptoms/conditions caused by Hg toxicity from amalgam filling. Controls. Inclusion: 1) 6 healthy volunteers 2) no reported medical disorders 3) free of amalgam restorations.	Adults. Records of 62 patients obtained from database	1) Failed to attend follow-up appointment after outlier Hg/Urine result: 1 subject. 2)No records of n of teeth with amalgam restorations: 11 subjects. Notes of these subjects did not include radiographs at time of examination.	Controls: 45yrs (NR) [NR].	36 patients had previously consulted other specialists regarding chronic Hg toxicity with various perceived symptoms. 20 subjects previously labelled to have Hg toxicity by commercial practitioners using unconventional testing panels. Patients, n (%). <u>Allergies:</u> 26 (46.43); <u>Auto-immune disorders:</u> 8 (14.29); <u>Depression:</u> 6 (10.71); <u>MS:</u> 2 (3.57); <u>CVD:</u> 13, (23.21); <u>Other:</u> 13 (23.2)	1)N teeth with amalgams ranged from 0-21. N. of amalgams, n (%) (n=45): 0-5 amalgams: 8 (17.8); 6-10 amalgams: 18 (40.0); >10 amalgams: 19 (42.2%). 2)NR	Data collected over 2 yrs [NA]	Gender/sex, n (%). Female: 43 (76.79); Male: 13 (23.21).
Forkel 2024 ⁵⁶	1)NA (data obtained from 50 dermatological departments in IVDK, located in Germany,	Patients. Inclusion: 1) referred for patch testing because of oral mucosa complaints (and possible additional complaints on lips/perioral skin).	Adults. 169 834 patients patch tested in IVDK dermatology departments vs. 6273 eligible vs. 2730 patch tested+	1)NA 2)NR	Mean NR-Age≥40 years, n (%): Allergic stomatitis (n=512): 469 (91.6), Nonallergic stomatitis	Overall: 1) 512 patients (444 women and 68 men) diagnosed with allergic contact dermatitis, allergic	1)Dental prostheses, fillings or implants. 2)NR.	Data used from 2005 to 2019 [NA].	Gender/sex. Total-Women: 81.2%. Patients with allergic stomatitis to dental materials-women: 86.7%

	<p>Switzerland and Austria.</p> <p>2) NA (Analysed at University Medical Centre of Göttingen (Göttingen, Germany))</p>	<p>Dental prostheses, fillings or implants considered problematic materials.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> 1) patients with occupationally associated dermatitis, 2) those working as dental technicians, dentists, DA.</p> <p>275 patients with unspecific diagnoses excluded from analysis</p>	<p>included in final analysis.</p>		<p>(n=687): 655 (95.3)[§]</p> <p>Noninflammatory oral complaints (n=1531): 1410 (92.1)</p>	<p>stomatitis or allergic cheilitis (study group: 'allergic stomatitis'; including allergic lichenoid eczema); 2) 687 patients (541 women and 146 men) diagnosed with irritant or unclassified dermatitis, stomatitis or cheilitis, as well as lichen planus (control group 1: 'nonallergic stomatitis'); and 3) 1531 patients (1231 women and 300 men) diagnosed with glossodynia or in whom dental allergy was excluded (control group 2: 'noninflammatory oral complaints')</p> <p>Of patients aged ≥40 years.</p> <p>Allergic stomatitis (n=512): 469 (91.6);</p> <p>Nonallergic stomatitis (n=687): 655 (95.3)';</p> <p>Noninflammatory oral</p>			
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						complaints (n=1531): 1410 (92.1)			
Frisk 2007 ⁵⁷	1) Referred to Department of Clinical Metal Biology University Hospital, Uppsala, Sweden: 2) University hospital, Uppsala, Sweden:	Inclusion: 1) patients with severe health problems, 2) long history of being sick-listed or having disability pension.	Adult patients: 24 referred and participate + 22 sex- and age-matched controls. Total 46.	1) NR 2) NR	NR	Chronic fatigue - dominating symptom. Other adverse effects reported: skin problems from contact with metals e.g. jewellery/jeans buttons, substantiating suspicion of immunological reactions caused by metals exposure	1) NR 2) NR	NR [At least 12 months]	Disability. All patients had a history of being sick-listed or having disability pension.
Gavic 2019 ⁵⁸	1) Sample selected by examining subjects in need of one tooth decay treatment who visited the Dental Clinic for Paediatric and Preventive Dentistry at the School of Dental Medicine of the University of Zagreb. 2) Department of Paediatric and Preventive Dentistry, School of Dental Medicine,	Inclusion: 1) good general health (absence of acute and chronic diseases) without taking any medication, 2) no previous restorations in the oral cavity 3) no orthodontic appliance.	Child patient: NR vs NR vs 60	1) NR. 2) NR.	Total 8.67 years (2.15) [6-14].	NR ^u	1) All participants had no previous restorations 2) Tooth decay	NR [3 months follow-up]	Gender/sex. Boys: 22 (36.7%); Girls: 38 (63.3%)

	University of Zagreb.								
Halperin-Sternfeld 2016 ⁵⁹	<p>1) Data retrospectively retrieved from clinical record charts of patients attending a specialist private periodontal office.</p> <p>2) NA. See recruitment method.</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1) Patients whose records included periodontal chart at baseline visit (T0) and periodontal chart \geq 10 years after T0 (T2). From these, patients whose records included re-evaluation of periodontal chart following cause-related therapy (T1) included in the final analysis.</p>	<p>Adult patients. 92 vs. 50 vs. NA</p>	<p>1) NA</p> <p>2) Some missing data on confounding variables such as systemic condition and smoking (based on patient subjective reporting).</p>	<p>46.6 years (10.6) [27-70.4] at baseline</p>	<p>All patients diagnosed at T0 with chronic periodontitis. Patients diagnosed with plaque-related periodontal disease, ranging from gingivitis to chronic and aggressive periodontitis. Earlier periodontal charts included PPD at 6 points per tooth/implant (mesiobuccal, midbuccal, distobuccal, mesiolingual/palatal, midbuccal/palatal, distobuccal/palatal). Later charts also included BOP at six points per tooth/implant, and one plaque score per tooth/implant (recorded as highest plaque score for each tooth/implant according to Silness and Loe classification). CVD: n=6 (12%).</p>	<p>1) At baseline- 1,301 teeth assessed: 721 unrestored and 580 restored. Of the 580 restored teeth: amalgam restorations (n=255) vs composite restorations (n=93) vs FPDs (n=232).</p>	<p>[The follow-up period (T0 to T2) ranged between 10-18 years (mean \pm SD, 12.7 \pm 2.1).]</p>	<p>Gender/sex, n. Male: 19; Female: 31.</p>

						<p>Smoker: n=9 (18%) were smokers. Taking calcium channel blockers: n=1 Taking anticoagulant medications: n=5 (10%). No diabetes reported.</p>			
Hsu 2016 ⁶⁰	<p>1) Cohorts selected from among patients registered in the NHIRD, which was released for research purposes by the NHRI in 2008. As of 2007, 98.4% of Taiwan's population (approximately 22.96 million) was enrolled in NHIRD. Data in present study retrieved from subset of 1 million randomly sampled enrollees in NHIRD. This consisted of 1 million randomly selected subjects who represent</p>	<p>Amalgam cohort. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) ≥1 procedure code record of amalgam filling (89001C–89003C and 89101C–89103C) between 2000–2008. PD cases. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) patients diagnosed as having PD (ICD-9-CM code 3320) at least once; 2) aged ≥ 55 yrs. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) patients with newly diagnosed PD before index date (getting amalgam fillings), 2) diagnosis of dementia, cerebrovascular diseases, head injury, or psychotic disorders at the time of or 1 year before PD diagnosis 3) dates of amalgam fillings (i.e., index date) before January 1, 2002 4) aged <55, 5) unknown sex/age as of January 1, 2002.</p>	<p>Adults. NHIRD 2000-2008: 1 million vs 20,740 vs NA</p>	<p>1) NA 2) NA</p>	<p>Amalgam cohort: 64.39 years (7.30) [NR]. Non-amalgam cohort: 64.29 years (7.52) [NR].</p>	<p>Amalgam cohort vs non-amalgam cohort, n (%)- <u>Diabetes:</u> 1813 (17.71) VS. 506 (4.94%). <u>Hypertension:</u> 4431 (43.29) vs 1402 (13.70%). <u>Hyperlipidemia:</u> 2039 (19.92) vs: 358 (3.50%). <u>Cardiovascular disease:</u> 2679 (26.17) vs 675 (6.59%), <u>CCI score, mean (SD):</u> 1.06 (1.40) vs 0.28 (0.72), p<.0001 (SS)</p>	<p>1) NR 2) NR</p>	<p>7 years observation period [The mean follow-up time for: Amalgam cohort= 5.15 vs Non-Amalgam cohort = 5.22 years].</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Amalgam cohort vs non-amalgam cohort, n (%) - Female: 4173 (40.77%) vs 4173 (40.77%); Male: 6063 (59.23%) vs. 6063 (59.23%)</p>

	about 4.5% of the Taiwanese population from the entire NHI enrollee profile. 2)NA								
Hu 2021 ⁶¹	1) LHID 2010, part of Taiwan's NHIRD. Almost all Taiwanese population enrolled in this compulsory NHI program. LHID 2010 collected registration information and dental and medical data and contains 1 million beneficiaries randomly sampled from the 2010 registry of beneficiaries in NHIRD. 2)NA	<u>Inclusion:</u> 1) born between 1998-2005 2) received OD treatment between January 2000 - December 2008. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) OD treatment dates before 01/01/2001; ADHD group. <u>Inclusion:</u> diagnosed before 3 years old	Children 85,503 VS. 14,952 VS. NA	1)NA 2)NA	Age at index date (date of ADHD diagnosis)- ADHD group: 7.45 years (2.20) [NR] ; Without ADHD: 7.45 years (2.20) [NR]	Comorbidities. ADHD cohort vs no ADHD cohort, n (%). <u>Autism:</u> 392 (7.8%) vs 38 (0.4%) <u>Mental retardation:</u> 473 (9.4%) vs 53 (0.5%). <u>Developmental delay:</u> 923 (18.5%) vs 391 (3.9%).	1)NR 2)NR	NA [Patients followed from 1 st date for composite resin restoration until 5 years after the date OD treatment received// Mean follow-up-ADHD group: 3.17 years (SD: 2.15) vs no ADHD: 3.15 years (SD: 2.15)]	Gender/sex. Total vs ADHD group vs No ADHD group, n (%)- Male: 11,673 (78.1%) vs. 3891 (78.1%) vs. 7782 (78.1%) Female: 3279 (21.9%) vs 1093 (21.9%) vs 2186 (21.9%). Place of residence. Total vs ADHD group vs No ADHD group, n (%)- Urban, 11,415 (77.4%) vs 3973 (81.8%) vs 7442 (75.3%) Suburban, 1229 (8.33%) vs 336 (6.9%) vs. 893 (9.03%) Rural, 2104 (14.3%) vs. 550 (11.3%) vs. 1554 (15.7%).
Lartitegui-Sebastian 2012 ⁶²	1)Patients at the Clinical Dentistry Service of the University of the Basque Country /EHU.	<u>Inclusion:</u> 1) > 30 yrs old, 2) 1 ≤ silver amalgam restoration in rear teeth.	Adults. NR vs NR vs 100.	1)NR. 2)NR.	Total: 59 years (NR) [30-77]. ^v With OLL: 52 years (NR) [36-68]; Without OLL: 54.83 years (NR) [30-77]	Total vs with OLL vs without OLL, n (%). <u>Allergy history-</u> 15 (15) vs. 1 (14.28); vs 14 (15.05). <u>Drugs intake-</u> 30 (30%) vs. 3	1)Total vs with OLL vs without OLL, mean [range]. Teeth with fillings- 3.89 [1-11] vs. 5 [2-7] vs. 3.82 [1-11]. <u>Surfaces with fillings-</u> 5.75	NR [6 months follow-up]	Gender/sex, n (%) Total vs with OLL vs without OLL- Male: 53 (53%) vs 3 (42.9%) vs 50 (53.8%)

	2)University of the Basque Country.					(42.9%); vs 27 (29.03%) Periodontal disease -66 (66) vs. 6 (85.7%) vs. 60 (64.5%)	[1-22] vs. 7 [3-12] vs. 5.68 [1-22]. Time since fillings mean: 15 [1-40] vs. 27 [20-40] vs. 14,72 [1-35]		Female: 47 (47%) vs. 4 (57.1%) vs 43 (46.2%).
Leybovich 2014 ⁶³	1)NR. 2)NR.	Selection of sites. Inclusion: 1) patients ages \geq 18 yrs. old, 2) NCCLs apical to CEJ, 3) Miller Class I or II gingival recession defects, 4) sites limited to maxillary non-molar teeth. Exclusion: 1)patients < 18 yrs. old 2) smokers, 3) pregnant patients, 4)immunocompromised patients 5) any disease or condition precluding periodontal surgery 6) NCCLs extending coronal to CEJ 7) Miller Class III or IV recession defects, 8) mandibular sites, 9)maxillary sites distal to the second premolars, 10) previously treated non carious lesions by either periodontal plastic surgery or restorative procedures.	Adults. 9 patients with 26 sites recruited vs 9 vs 9 patients treated vs 8 sites included in final data collection (12 sites subepithelial CTG and 12 sites Class V CRR).	1)n=1 patient did not return for final postoperative appointment. 2)NR.	NR	NR	1)NR 2) NCCLs apical to CEJ, Miller Class I or II gingival recession defects, sites limited to maxillary non-molar teeth.	NR [3 months follow-up]	NR
Lin 2017 ⁶⁴	1) Taiwan NHI Program-records of the LHID2005, which	Inclusion: 1) 20 > yrs. old 2) without an outpatient/inpatient diagnosis of ADHD in 2001,3) 1 \leq cavity	Children/adolescents. 247604 received tooth restorations from LHID 2005 during	1)NA 2)NR	Amalgam: 9.56 years (5.28) [NR]; Other restoration:	Comorbidity, n (%) Amalgam vs other restoration: BD: 38 (0.1) vs 38	1)Min. 1 cavity restored during 2002-2010. N. of restorations during 2002-11, mean	8 years [NA]	Gender/sex, n (%). Amalgam vs other restoration- Female: 22 238

	<p>includes registration data and dental and medical claims filed between 2001 and 2011 of 1,000,000 beneficiaries randomly sampled.</p> <p>2)NA</p>	<p>restored during 2002-2010. Exposed group: people who received amalgam restorations. Non-exposed: other restorations including composite resin and glass ionomer.</p> <p>Exclusion: 1) People with missing or incomplete registry data (e.g. unknown or missing data on sex or urbanization level).</p> <p>Matching process: 1:1 matching for: recruitment time, age, sex, n of tooth restorations during 2002-2011, fluoride varnish application, medical institution, urbanization level and relevant underlying systemic diseases, namely BD (ICD-9-CM: 296), PDD (ICD-9-CM: 299), anxiety disorder (ICD-9-CM: 300), Tourette's disorder (ICD-9-CM: 307.23), conduct disorder (ICD-9-CM: 312), specific delays in development (ICD-9-CM: 315) and mild ID (ICD-9-CM: 317-318)</p>	<p>2001-11 vs 154509 met inclusion criteria/enrolled (71166 exposed group vs. 83343 non-exposed group) vs 44034 in each group selected for further analysis after matching.</p>		<p>9.58 years (5.27) [NR].</p>	<p>(0.1) <u>PDD:</u> 61 (0.1) vs 50 (0.1). <u>Anxiety disorder:</u> 216 (0.5) vs 221 (0.5). <u>Tourette's disorder:</u> 17 (0.04) vs 9 (0.02). <u>Conduct disorder:</u> 10 (0.02) vs 16 (0.04) <u>Specific delays in development:</u> 578 (1.3) vs 558 (1.3) <u>Mild ID:</u> 111 (0.3) vs 62 (0.1).</p>	<p>(SD) Amalgam vs other restoration: 9.17 (4.80) vs 9.17 (4.80).</p> <p>2)Cavities</p>	<p>(50.5) vs 22 238 (50.5).</p> <p>Place of residence. Urbanization level, n (%) Amalgam vs other restorations- 1 (Most urbanized): 13 797 (31.3) vs 13 797 (31.3) 2: 13 304 (30.2) vs 13 304 (30.2) 3: 8248 (18.7) vs 8248 (18.7) 4: (average) 6219 (14.1) vs 6219 (14.1) 5: 333 (0.8) vs 333 (0.8) 6: 1172 (2.7) vs 1172 (2.7) 7 (Least urbanized): 961 (2.2) vs 961 (2.2). SES. Medical institution, n (%). Amalgam vs other restoration: Hospital: 442 (1.0) vs 442 (1.0). Private practice: 43 592 (99.0) vs. 43 592 (99.0)</p>	
Louopou 2020 ⁶⁵	1)Study sites selected if they had	Data obtained from previously published MIREC study. ^w	Adults. 8716 women approached vs 5108 eligible vs	1)Of 2001 participants, 18 withdrew from	Maternal age (years). N. of dental	N. of dental amalgam reported at 1st	1)Amalgam/No amalgam	Women recruited between	Gender/sex. Women: 100%

<p>established clinical obstetrical research infrastructure in place + to represent different geographical regions of the country. Clinical site investigators from 10 cities across Canada asked to recruit a total of 2000 pregnant women from general population who were attending prenatal clinics (ultrasound, midwife and/or doctor's clinics) during 1st trimester of pregnancy (6 to <14 weeks). Recruitment between 2008-2011.</p> <p>2) Recruited from Vancouver, Edmonton, Winnipeg, Sudbury, Ottawa, Kingston,</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1) healthy women, 2) 1st trimester pregnancy 3) ability to consent and communicate in English/French, 4) ≥18 yrs, , 5) <14 weeks gestation, 6) willing to provide a sample of cord blood 7) planning on delivering at local hospital.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> 1) women who had known foetal abnormalities (e.g. Hydatidiform mole), or known foetal chromosomal/major malformations in current pregnancy, 2) women with history of medical complications, including: renal disease with altered renal function, epilepsy, any collagen disease such as lupus erythematosus/scleroderma, active and chronic liver disease (hepatitis), heart disease, serious pulmonary disease, cancer, haematological disorder (patient with anaemia or thrombophilia will be included), threatened spontaneous abortion (women with previous</p>	<p>2001 agreed to participate vs 1817 included in final sample (74 women excluded due to miscarriage/ stillbirth + excluded from analysis: 58 with chronic hypertension, 34 with missing data on hypertension status)</p>	<p>study and requested data to be destroyed.</p> <p>2) Missing data on hypertension status (n=34). (excluded from analysis). Highest refusal or 'don't know' responses for family income (2.5% and 2.2%, respectively) and pre-pregnancy BMI (7.6% missing) (data not shown).</p> <p>Only 48 women (2.4%) did not consent to having biospecimens and data stored in the Biobank. High proportion missing data (35%) concerning gestational diabetes status.</p>	<p>amalgam- 0: 31.86 years (5.01) [NR]; 1-4: 33.33 years (4.84) p < 0.05 [NR]; ≥ 5: 34.42 years (5.04) p < 0.05 [NR].</p> <p>Replacement within 12 months prior to 1st trimester visit- No: 32.71 (5.03) [NR]; Yes: 34.34 (4.94) [NR].</p>	<p>trimester visit. 0 vs 1-4 vs ≥ 5.</p> <p><u>Parity-</u> multiparous: 747 (56.6%) vs 510 (54.8%) vs 266 (62.7%); nulliparous: 115 (43.4%) vs 92 (45.2%) vs 37 (37.3%).</p> <p><u>Maternal smoking-</u> No: 809 (93.9%) vs 568 (94.4%) vs 279 (92.1%); Yes: 53 (6.1%) vs 34 (5.6%) vs 24 (7.9%).</p> <p><u>Multiple child pregnancy-</u> No: 827 (98.2%) vs 574 (96.8%) vs 292 (97.7%); Yes: 15 (1.8%) vs 19 (3.2%) vs 7 (2.3%).</p> <p><u>Autoimmune disease-</u> No: 840 (97.4%) vs 598 (99.3%) vs 298 (98.3%) Yes: 22 (2.6%) vs 4 (0.7%) vs 5 (1.7%).</p> <p><u>GH-</u> No: 784 (49.4%) vs 534 (33.6%) vs 269 (17.0%). Yes: 78 (43.3%) vs 68 (37.8%) vs 34 (18.9%).</p>	<p>2)NR</p>	<p>2008 and 2011 [Generally healthy women recruited in 1st trimester of pregnancy and followed until after delivery.]</p>	<p>N. of dental amalgam reported at 1st trimester visit.^x 0 vs 1-4 vs ≥ 5</p> <p>Race/ethnicity, n (%). Caucasian: 747 (86.7%) vs 510 (84.7%) vs 266 (87.8%). Non-Caucasian: 115 (13.3%) vs 92 (15.3%) vs 37 (12.2%).</p> <p>Education. Graduate university undergraduate: 228 (26.5%) vs 152 (25.3%) vs 79 (26.1%); University: 316 (36.7%) vs 221 (36.8%) vs 103 (34.0%); College: 225 (26.1%) vs 171 (28.5%) vs 81 (26.7%). Less college: 93 (10.8%) vs 56 (9.3%) vs 40 (13.2%).</p> <p>SES. Household income (\$CAN)- < 65,000: 255 (31.0%) vs 169 (29.4%) vs 86 (29.4%) 65,000 – 90,000: 237 (28.8%) vs 161 (28.0%) vs 90 (30.7%).</p>
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	Hamilton, Toronto, Montreal, and Halifax.	bleeding in 1 st trimester included if site documented a viable foetus at time of recruitment), illicit drug use.							
Lygre 2013 ⁶⁶	1)Patients referred to Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit. 2)Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit.	Treatment group. Inclusion: 1) referred to Norwegian Dental Biomaterials Adverse Reaction Unit for examination of health complaints attributed to amalgam fillings, 2) amalgam fillings still present, 3) no diagnosed contact allergy to substances in resin-based dental materials, 4) health complaints from 3 ≤ different organ systems, 5) data on Hg in blood and urine from initial examination, 6) aged 25–55 at initial examination; 7) Accepted to be contacted in follow-up study. Exclusion: 1) severe medical disorders (e.g. MS, ALS, severe RA), 2) severe food allergies; 3) psychological difficulties or psychiatric disorders which could influence dental treatment, 4) complicated therapy (severe periodontitis,	Adults. Treatment group. 368 referred and 358 asked to complete follow-up questionnaire (207 returned questionnaires) vs eligible final treatment group: 20 vs included in analysis: 19 External reference group. 800 approached vs 441 returned questionnaire	1)1 patient (treatment group) did not participate at 3-year follow-up 2)NR	Treatment group. At pre-treatment: 49 years (6.8) [NR] At 3 yr follow-up: 53 years (6.7) [NR].	23 complaints (see Figure 1) categorised as: 1) intra-oral complaints (6 items), 2) extra-oral complaints (5 items), 3) general complaints (12 items) (see Table III). Some also had lesions in contact with specific dental materials (lichenoid contact lesions). Of 19 participants at baseline, n (%): <u>On sick leave or disability pension:</u> 8 (42.1), <u>Used medication last 12 months:</u> Analgesics: 14 (73.7), Antidepressants: 3 (15.8), Vitamins/dietary supplements:13 (68.4). <u>Concentration of Hg at pre-treatment, M (SD):</u> Blood (nmol/L): 14 (6), Urine (nmol/L): 19 (13)	1) N. of amalgam surfaces pre-treatment, mean (SD): 24.3 (10.3). 2) NR	11 years (1993-2004) [3 yr follow-up]	Gender/sex, n (%) . Women: 13 (68); Men 6 (32). Education. Years, mean (SD): 11.2 (3.3) Disability: On sick leave or disability pension, n (%): 8 (42.1)

		<p>high caries activity and/or need for complicated dental rehabilitation, e.g. bridges), 5) inclusion criteria no longer fulfilled.</p> <p>External reference group. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) from general population in Norway, 2) similar to the treatment group regarding age, gender and education.</p>							
Lynch 2015 ⁶⁷	<p>1)Patients referred from oral medicine clinic. Identified via clinical database, referred by 2 oral medicine consultants.</p> <p>2)Patch testing: Dermatology clinic. Review of clinical progress: Oral medicine clinic.</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> patients with extensive OLLs and multiple amalgams where aetiology of OLL not clear.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> 1) patients with OLP/1 OLL in association with 1 amalgam as diagnosis of OLP/Oll more clear-cut. 1) Patients with evidence of dysplasia on oral mucosa biopsy without evidence of lichenoid inflammation.</p>	<p>Adults. 36 referred VS 31 eligible and tested/</p>	<p>1)4 patients did not attend follow-up (1 with positive reaction to Hg and 3 with negative reactions to Hg).</p> <p>2) Follow-up data missing in some patients (not specified).</p>	50.6 years (NR) [32-74]	<p>None had cutaneous lichen planus. 13 patients asymptomatic.</p> <p>In those patients with symptoms: duration of symptoms ranged from 3 wk -14 yrs; 30 had amalgams in direct contact with OLL, 1 had amalgams in close contact; pattern of OLL was reticular in 24, erosive/atrophic in 5, and ulcerative in 2. 4 had biopsy showing lichenoid inflammation in all biopsies. In addition to lichenoid</p>	<p>1)All patients had multiple amalgam fillings. Clinical corrosion of the amalgams recorded: n=6.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Women referred in 2007 and 208 [Mean duration follow-up 2.6 (range, 0-4.75) yrs]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Women: 22 (71%); Men: 9 (29%).</p>

						inflammation, evidence of mild dysplasia in 2/4 biopsies. <u>Smoking status.</u> Smokers (n=4); Ex-smokers (n=8); non-smokers (n=19).			
Ma 2021 ⁶⁸	1) LHID 2000 subset of NHIRD operated by Taiwanese government. 2)NA	Cases. Inclusion: subset of cases of patients diagnosed with incident OLP between January 1997-Dec 2013 (restricted to those diagnosed post 2001) according to WHO guidelines [see paper]. Controls. Inclusion: matched for age, sex, urbanization on a 1:20 ratio and propensity score matching on a 1:4 ratio for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, chronic liver disease, hep. C. viral infection, periodontitis and CCI. Exclusion: 1) missing demographic data; expired by 2000; 2) index year before 2000.	Adults. LHID2000: 1 million in database vs 2105 eligible and included in dataset (421 cases, 1684 controls) vs NA	1)NA 2)Missing demographic data, n=6,483 and consequently excluded from final sample.	Mean NR- See Table 1 for N(%) cases/control s by age bracket	OLP group vs Control group, n (%). All propensity score matched- Comorbidities- COPD: 55 (13.06%) vs 183 (10.87%). Chronic liver disease: 78 (18.53%) vs. 290 (17.22%); Periodontitis: 310 (73.63%) vs 1,256 (74.58%). Hepatitis C viral infection: 8 (1.9%) vs 23 (1.37%). CCI-0: 195 (46.32%) vs. 794 (47.15%); 1-2: 163 (38.72%) vs. 659 (39.13%); 3-4: 49 (11.64%) vs. 182 (10.81%); 5 or more: 14 (3.33%) vs. 49 (2.91%). Dental visit/yr (Mean within 3 years), n (%)- 0: 38 (9.03%) vs 150 (8.91%), <1: 63 (14.96%) vs 254 (15.08%), 1-2:	OLP group vs control group, n (%). Amalgam fillings (n. of teeth filled)- 0 times: 332 (78.86%) vs. 1,293 (76.78%); 1-2 times: 70 (16.63%) vs 295 (17.52%); 3-4 times: 14 (3.33%) vs. 62 (3.68%); 5 or more times: 5 (1.19%) vs 34 (2.02%). Resin fillings (n. of teeth filled) – 0 times: 182 (43.23%) vs 645 (38.30%); 1-2 times: 89 (21.14%) vs 355 (21.08%); 3-4 times: 44 (10.45%) vs. 268 (15.91%); 5 or more times: 106 (25.18%) vs. 416 (24.70%). 2) Caries, pulpitis or apical lesions, and gingival or periodontal diseases.	2001- 2013 [5 years]	Gender/sex. Propensity score matched. OLP group vs control, n (%). Female: 295 (70.07%) vs. 1,206 (71.62%); Male: 126 (29.93%) vs. 478 (28.38%). Place of residence. Propensity scored matched. OLP group vs Control group, n (%). Urban: 266 (63.18%) vs. 1,098 (65.20%); Sub-urban: 116 (27.55%) vs. 430 (25.53%); Rural: 39 (9.26%) vs. 156 (9.26%).

						<p>162 (38.48%) vs 649 (38.54%), ≥ 3: 158 (37.53%) vs 631 (37.47%)</p> <p><u>Root canal therapy</u>-N. of teeth - 0: 306 (72.68%) vs 1047 (62.17%), 1-2 times: 94 (22.33%) vs 503 (29.87%), 3-4 times: 17 (4.04%) vs 97 (5.76%), ≥ 5 times: 4 (0.95%) vs 37 (2.20%).</p> <p><u>Tooth extraction</u>- N. of teeth - 0: 277 (65.80%) vs 1013 (60.15%), 1~2 times: 116 (27.55%) vs 476 (28.27%), 3~4 times: 21 (4.99%) vs 119 (7.07%), ≥ 5 times: 7 (1.66%) vs 76 (4.51%)</p>			
Marell 2014 ⁶⁹	<p>1)1991-1998.</p> <p>Patients: examined because of signs and symptoms attributed to dental materials.</p> <p>Control: randomly selected from database at Department of Psychology, Umea University, Sweden.</p>	<p>Patients. Inclusion: at follow-up with diagnosis of oral lichenoid reactions.</p> <p>Control. Inclusion: group: sex- and age matched, healthy subjects.</p>	<p>Adults. 751 patients examined at baseline vs 73 approached for follow-up vs 44 consented</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2) University hospital of Umea criteria fulfilled by 31/44 patients. Diagnosis of lesions/biopsies taken for 36/44 patients.</p>	<p>Women (n=31): 62 years (NR) [44-78].</p> <p>Men (n=13): 57 years (NR) [37-73].</p>	<p><u>Diagnosis of OLR</u>- LCR: n=31; OLP: n=13.</p>	<p>1)LCR group (n=31) vs OLP group (n=13)- Mean n. of tooth surfaces restored with: Amalgam: 29.7 vs 27.5; Composite/glass ionomer): 12.3 vs 14.6.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Baseline 1991-1998. [Follow-up average 6.1yrs (range 4–10) after first examination]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Women: 31 (70%); Men: 13 (30%)</p>

	2)Department of Odontology, Umea University, Sweden.								
Mikhailichenko 2019 ⁷⁰	<p>1)Reimbursement data from LHID 2000 spanning the period 1997–2018.</p> <p>2)NA. See recruitment method.</p>	<p>Study group. <u>Inclusion:</u> Patients diagnosed with new-onset dementia (ICD-9-CM: 331.0, 290.0–290.4) between Jan. 1997- Dec. 2013. Diagnosis according to min. two outpatient visits or a single admission.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> Patients with dementia before January 2003 excluded (n = 3541)</p> <p>Controls. Inclusion: never diagnosed with dementia between Jan. 1997- Dec. 2013. 1:2 age-sex matched.</p>	<p>1 million database vs 925043 eligible vs age-sex matched and included in analysis: 49998- Diagnosed dementia: 16 666 vs control: 33,332</p>	<p>1)NA</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Adults. Age at index date (date of 1st visit for dementia). Control vs dementia cases, n (%): <u><40:</u> 236 (0.71%) vs 118 (0.71%), <u>40–59:</u> 1888 (5.66%) vs 944 (5.66%), <u>60–79:</u> 16,840 (50.52%) vs 8420 (50.52%), <u>≥80:</u> 14,368 (43.11%) vs 7184 (43.11%)</p>	<p>Comorbidities, n(%), control vs dementia cases: <u>Urticaria:</u> 3296 (9.89%) vs 1830 (10.98%), <u>Rheumatic diseases:</u> 1514 (4.54%) vs 979 (5.87%), <u>Thyroid disorders:</u> 846 (2.54%) vs 526 (3.16%), <u>Inflammatory diseases:</u> 11020 (33.06%) vs 5609 (33.66%), <u>Helicobacter pylori infection:</u> 129 (0.39%) vs 122 (0.73%), <u>Peptic ulcer:</u> 6677 (20.03%) vs 4658 (27.95%), <u>Hepatitis B virus infection:</u> 494 (1.48%) vs 318 (1.91%), <u>Hepatitis C virus infection:</u> 552 (1.66%) vs 389 (2.33%), <u>Psychiatric disorders:</u> 6325 (18.98%) vs 5996 (35.98%), <u>Asthma:</u> 3098 (9.29%) vs 1905 (11.43%),</p>	<p>1)Control vs dementia cases, n (%). Amalgam restoration: <u>0:</u> 23,651 (70.96%) vs 11,750 (70.5%), <u>1–3:</u> 6743 (20.23%) vs 3384 (20.3%), <u>≥4:</u> 2938 (8.81%) vs 1532 (9.19%). Resin restoration: <u>0:</u> 17,588 (52.77%) vs 8659 (51.96%), <u>1–8:</u> 10,257 (30.77%) vs 5147 (30.88%), <u>≥9:</u> 5487 (16.46%) vs 2860 (17.16%)</p> <p>2) Dental caries, pulpitis. Control vs dementia cases, n (%):9007 (27.02%) vs4421 (26.53%)</p>	<p>Data from database spanning the period 1997–2013 [NA]</p>	<p>Control vs Dementia cases, n (%). Gender/sex. Female: 17,674 (53.02%) vs 8837 (53.02%), Male: 15,658 (46.98%) vs 7829 (46.98%)</p> <p>Place of residence. <u>Urbanization-</u> Urban: 17,719 (53.16%) vs 8692 (52.15%), Suburban: 10,484 (31.45%) vs 5259 (31.56%) Rural: 5129 (15.39%) vs 2715 (16.29%)</p> <p>SES. Low-income: 296 (0.89%) vs 189 (1.13%)</p> <p>Time-dependent relationships. <u>Length of hospital stay (days)-</u> 0: 18,243 (54.73%) vs 5310 (31.86%),</p>

						<p><u>Chronic liver disease:</u> 3336 (10.01%) vs 2125 (12.75%), <u>DM:</u> 7603 (22.81%) vs 5498 (32.99%), <u>Hyperlipidemia:</u> 7812 (23.44%) vs 4509 (27.06%), <u>Heart failure:</u> 2731 (8.19%) vs 2141 (12.85%), <u>Hypertension:</u> 18,708 (56.13%) vs 11,559 (69.36%), <u>Coronary artery disease:</u> 7832 (23.5%) vs 5140 (30.84%), <u>COPD:</u> 7047 (21.14%) vs 4828 (28.97%), <u>Ischemic stroke:</u> 5197 (15.59%) vs 6383 (38.30%), <u>Cancer:</u> 2784 (8.35%) vs 1568 (9.41%), <u>Gingival and periodontal diseases:</u> 11,964 (35.89%) vs 6070 (36.42%) <u>CKD:</u> 2820 (8.46%) 2245 (13.47%) 0.16087 -0.00041 <u>PD:</u> 816 (2.45%) 1645 (9.87%) 0.31248 -0.02095</p>			<p>1-6: 5237 (15.71%) vs 2655 (15.93%), 7-13: 3808 (11.42%) vs 2401 (14.41%), ≥14: 6044 (18.13%) vs 6300 (37.8%)</p>
Montebugnoli 2012 ⁷¹	1)Patients referred to the Department of	<u>Inclusion:</u> 1) 1 ≤ amalgam filling, 2) 1 ≤ white or red lesions	Adults. NR vs NR vs 64	1)NR 2)NR	Mean NR- Age: Less than/equal to	<u>Smoking status:</u> Smokers (n=10);	1)All had ≥1 amalgam filling Patients referred 2005-2007	Gender/sex, n (%) . Males: 28	

	<p>Oral Sciences of the University of Bologna, Italy, from 2005 to 2007.</p> <p>2) See Recruitment method.</p>	<p>with some evidence of Wickham striae with unilateral OLL or bilateral OLP appearance, 3) clinical features unchanged for ≥ 6 months, 4) histologically: bandlike lymphocytic infiltrate filling the lamina propria, and liquefactive degeneration of basal keratinocytes, and Civatte bodies. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) positive hepatitis C virus test, 2) graft vs host or systemic autoimmune diseases, 3) chronic medication, 4) previous treatment with topical or systemic corticosteroids/other immunosuppressive agents</p>			<p>56 yrs: n=31; Greater than 56yrs: n=33</p>	<p>non-smokers (n=54). <u>Oral lesions:</u> <u>White reticular lesions:</u> n=47 <u>Erythematous/erosive lesions:</u> n=17. <u>OLL:</u> N=25 <u>QLP:</u> n=39. Positive patch test (n=15). Negative patch test (n=49)</p>	2)NR	<p>[every 3 months for min. 2 years]</p>	<p>(44%); Females: 36 (56%)</p>
<p>Naimi-Akbar 2013⁷²</p>	<p>1)Applicants for subsidized dental restoration replacement between 1999 and 2005. Comprise all applicants in 7/21 Swedish counties, approx. 39% of Swedish population.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Patients. Both groups. Inclusion: patients who applied for dental filling replacement between 1999-2005. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) rejected applications (n=81); 2) incomplete answer regarding filling replacement (n=12)</p> <p>Replacement group: <u>Inclusion:</u> subjects with approved applications who</p>	<p>546 applied for filling replacement vs 515 eligible vs 280 responded (233 replacement group, 31 non-replacement group) vs groups used for subgroup analysis: Approved application:199 (161 replacement group, 13 non-replacement group)</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2) Participants with incomplete answers were excluded from final subgroups for analysis. See inclusion/exclusion criteria column for details.</p>	<p>Replacement vs non-replacement group. Mean: 59 years (NR) [NR] vs 58 years (NR) [NR]</p> <p>Survey respondents (n=280)- Men vs women vs total, n(%): ≤54 years: 17 (37.8%) vs 79 (33.6%) vs 96</p>	NR	<p>1)<u>Dental restorative materials at present:</u> dental amalgam, dental composite, dental crowns of gold, cobalt–chromium, titanium and ceramics, acrylics and metals in removable dentures.</p>	<p>Data collected between 1999-2005 [Questionnaire posted 4-10yrs after application for removal, follow up 1, 2 and 3 yrs post removal]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Of total respondents Men: 45 vs Women: 235. <u>Replacement vs non-replacement group.</u> Women: 85.0% vs 77.4%</p>

		<p>stated that they had replaced dental amalgam fillings. <u>Exclusion:</u>1) not specified whether they had proceeded with replacement of dental amalgam fillings (n=11); 2) answered that they had not replaced dental amalgams (n=2)</p> <p>Non-replacement group: <u>Inclusion:</u> subjects with approved applications who stated that they had not replaced dental restorations.</p>			<p>(34.3%); <u>55-64 years:</u> 14 (31.1%) vs 78 (33.2%) vs 92 (32.9%), <u>≥65 years:</u> 14 (31.1%) vs 78 (33.2%) vs 92 (32.9%)</p>		<p><u>Replacement of dental restorations, n patients (%): in 233 (83.2%) patients-</u> Dental amalgam replaced: 211 (90.6%). Composite replaced: 48 (20.6%) Gold alloys replaced: 79 (33.9%) Ceramics replaced: 35 (15%). Titanium replaced: 20 (8.6%), Acrylics in dentures replaced: 19 (8.2%). Metals in dentures replaced: 10 (4.3%) and cobalt–chromium alloys replaced: 8 (3.4%).</p> <p><u>No replacement of dental restorations:</u> in 31 (11.1%) subjects, dental restorative materials had not been replaced because of symptoms that they attributed to dental restorative materials.</p> <p>2)NR</p>		
Perng 2023 ⁷³	1)The LHID 2000, subset of NHIRD with	Patients Inclusion: patients with newly-onset caries	LHID 2000: 1 million in database vs. 807,751 eligible	1)NA 2)NR	Non-dental caries group. (n=258,918):	Non-dental caries group (n=258,918) vs.	Dental caries group only (n=501,461), n (%).	[Time to event analysis, in	Non-dental caries group (n=258,918) vs

<p>temporal data based on electronic medical records.</p> <p>2)NA</p>	<p>regardless of whether caries comorbid with endodontic lesions, pulpal involvement, or pulpitis (primary ICD-9 code: 522.0), and whether carious teeth extracted.</p> <p>Exclusion: 1) missing demographic data, 2) dead before 1 January 2005, 3) aged <16 or 80 years or older in 2005, 4) diagnosed with SLE before 1 January 2005.</p> <p>Controls. Inclusion: non-dental caries.</p>	<p>(760, 379 with dental filling history and included in the analysis - 501461 in caries group) vs NA</p>			<p>49 years (15) [NR]. Dental caries group (n=501,46); 42 years (16) [NR]</p>	<p>dental caries group (n=501,461), n (%). Comorbidities-Sjorgen: 429 (0.17%) vs 1644 (0.33%); RA: 2040 (0.79%) vs. 4125 (0.82%); Hypertension: 34,276 (13.24%) vs. 46,724 (9.32%); DM: 17,218 (6.65%) vs. 24,610 (4.91%); Hyperlipidemia: 17,129 (6.62%) vs. 33,794 (6.74%); Stroke: 9826 (3.80%) vs. 10,231 (2.04%); CKD: 8342 (3.22%) vs. 12,789 (2.55%); COPD: 17,385 (6.71%) vs. 34,851 (6.95%); Chronic liver disease: 21,736 (8.39%) vs. 48,386 (9.65%); Asthma: 9212 (3.56%) vs. 23,027 (4.59%) Periodontitis from 1997 to 2004- No: 200,803 (77.57%) vs. 150,615 (30.04%); Yes: 58,088 (22.43%) 350,846 (69.96%) Dental pulpitis from 1997 to</p>	<p>Dental filling materials from 1997-2004- Only amalgam: 72,398 (14.44%); only resin: 180,127 (35.92%); amalgam + resin: 248,936 (49.64%). Restorative materials: only amalgam- 1-3: 55,053 (76.04%); 4-6: 12,291 (16.98%); ≥7 5054 (6.98%) Restorative material: resin only- 1-3: 94,312 (52.36%); 4-6: 40,844 (22.68%); ≥7: 44,971 (24.97%) Restorative materials: amalgam + resin- 1-3: 35,340 (14.20%); 4-6: 65,035 (26.13%); ≥7: 148,561 (59.68%) 2)NR</p>	<p>which index date defined as the fixed time point (January 2005) for every participant. Participants followed up from index date until occurrence of SLE, withdraw, or until the end of 2013, whichever occurred first.]</p>	<p>Caries group (n=501,461)</p> <p>Gender/sex. Female: 104,559 (40.38%) vs 268,840 (53.61%). Male: 154,359 (59.62%) vs 232,621 (46.39%).</p> <p>Place of residence. Urbanization. Highly urbanized towns: 71,930 (27.78%) vs. 167,760 (33.45%); Moderately urbanized towns: 76,488 (29.54%) vs. 155,311 (30.97%); Rising town: 49,381 (19.07%) vs. 85,912 (17.13%); General township: 33,155 (12.81%) vs. 54,794 (10.93%); Aging town: 4326 (1.67%) vs 5094 (1.02%); Agricultural town: 8943 (3.45%) vs. 10,988 (2.19%); Remote towns: 14,695 (5.68%) vs. 21,602 (4.31%).</p>
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						<p>2004- No: 244,469 (94.42% vs. 240,564 (47.97%); Yes: 14,449 (5.58%) vs. 260,897 (52.03%)</p> <p>Frequency of dental visit from 1997 to 2004- 0: 168,270 (64.99%) vs 8 (0.00%), 1-2: 57,799 (22.32%) vs 32,584 (6.50%), 3-10: 30,737 (11.87%) vs 229,593 (45.78%); ≥ 11: 2112 (0.82%) vs 239,276 (47.72%)</p> <p>Frequency of carious tooth extraction from 1997 to 2004- 0: 230,713 (89.11%) vs 304,780 (60.78%), 1-4: 26,842 (10.37%) vs 185,152 (36.92%); ≥5: 1363 (0.53%) vs 11,529 (2.30%).</p> <p><u>N. of carious teeth from 1997 to 2004- 0: 258,918 (100%) vs 0 (0%), 1-3: 0 (0%) vs 184,705 (36.83%), 4-6: 0 (0%) vs 118,170 (23.57%); ≥ 7: 0 (0%) vs 198,586 (39.60%).</u></p>			<p>Occupation. Insured classification ^y- 1st category: 7895 (3.05%) vs 25,749 (5.13%); 2nd category: 157,504 (60.83%) vs. 306,855 (61.19%); 3rd: 23,057 (8.91%) vs. 26,836 (5.35%); 4th category: 3338 (1.29%) vs. 3817 (0.76%); 5th category: 38,159 (14.74%) vs. 73,399 (14.64%); Dependent: 28,965 (11.19%) vs. 64,805 (12.92%).</p> <p>SES. Income-Dependent: 63,223 (24.42%) vs 170,993 (34.10%); Low: 145,558 (56.22%) vs 210,539 (41.99%); High: 50,137 (19.36%) vs. 119,929 (23.92%).</p>
Pettini, 2015 ⁷⁴	1)Group 1 - NR; Group 2 - Students at	Group 1 (exposed). Inclusion: healthy blood donors, not	Adult. Group 1: NR vs NR vs 20 participated; Group	1)NR 2)NR	Group 1: 23.5yrs (NR) [18-29],	Group 2 includes 9 smokers: smoking duration	1)Group 1: Total of between 10-16 (average 13) teeth	NR [NA]	Gender/sex. Exposed vs non-exposed (n) -

	University of Bari "Aldo Moro" Dental school. 2)Dental Clinic, Operative Unit of Restorative Dentistry.	taking any medication. Group 2 (controls). <u>Inclusion:</u> 1)non-smokers, 2) not alcohol consumers, 3) not taking any medication. Also included 9 additional smokers.	2: NR vs NR vs 20 participated		Group 2: 20.5yrs (NR)[18-23]	1-9yrs; n. cigarettes/day: 5-10	filled with same dental composite materials (Enamel Plus-HFO Micerium S.p.A., Avengno, Italy. No amalgam. Group 2: no exposure to dental composite materials (neither amalgam nor composite resin fillings). 2)NR		Male: 12 vs 10, Female: 8 vs 10. Race/ethnicity. Caucasian: 100%
Pezelj-Ribaric 2008 ⁷⁵	1)NR 2)Oral Medicine Unit of the Medical Faculty, University of Rijeka.	Patients. Inclusion: with OLR. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) patients taking drugs that might cause a lichenoid reaction, 2) lesions on skin or locations other than oral mucosa. Controls. Inclusion: healthy volunteers.	NR vs 40 (20 patients with OLR; 20 healthy controls) vs 40	1)NR 2)NR	OLR group: 50 years (9) [NR]; Control group (healthy): 51 years (9) [NR]	NR	1)Patients (n=20): Amalgam 2)NR	4 years: 2001-2005. [Follow-up period of between 2 months and 3.5 years.]	Gender/sex. OLR Patient group ² : Men: 16 (80%); Women: 4 (20%).
Ptak 2023 ⁷⁶	1)Medical records of all patients who received permanent large restorations in the Tufts University School of Dental Medicine Undergraduate Clinic.	<u>Inclusion:</u> 1) all patients who received large restorations (fillings, inlays, and onlays involving at least 3 surfaces or full-coverage crowns) on vital teeth in the Tufts University School of Dental Medicine Undergraduate Clinic between January 1, 2010 - January 1, 2015, 2) at least 1	2885 records in database vs 2177 vs NA	1)NA 2)NR	54 years (17.10) [NR]	NR	1)Non-crown restorations: Composite restorations, n (%): 1151 (64.7%); amalgam restorations, n (%): 628 (35.3%) 2)NR	5 years: Jan 12010- Jan 1, 2015 [At least 1 year follow-up]	Gender/sex. All patients (n=2177). Male: 1122 (51.58 %); Female: 1055 (48.42 %).

	2) NA	year of follow-up, 3) completed a comprehensive examination (code D0120) at least 365 days after first restorative procedure. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) Any patient who did not have at least 1 year of follow-up time after restoration, 2) patients whose teeth were endodontically treated before the initiation of restorative treatment (on the same tooth), 3) patients whose teeth were diagnosed as necrotic/ irreversible pulpitis before restorative treatment (on the same tooth), 4) patients whose restorative treatment required the tooth to serve as an abutment, 5) patients whose restorative treatment=implant crowns.							
Rojas-Alcayaga 2012 ⁷⁷	1) Atopic patients: recruited from Allergy Centre of Clinical Hospital. Non atopic subjects: selected from patients requesting	Atopic patients. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) 20- 65 yrs. of age 2) clinical history of atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis, allergic asthma or food allergies, confirmed by a prick test.	Adult. NR vs 80 vs 80	1)NR 2)NR	Atopic group: 34.6 years (NR) [NR]; non-atopic group: 41.87 years (NR) [NR]	NR	1)NR 2)NR	NR [NA]	Gender/sex. Atopic group (n=40)- male: 12 (30%), female: 28 (70%); non-atopic group (n=40)- male: 10 (25%) vs female: 30 (75%).

	<p>dental treatment at School of Dentistry of the University of Chile.</p> <p>2) School of Dentistry of the University of Chile and University of Chile Clinical Hospital.</p>	<p>Non-atopic patients. Inclusion: 1) 20- 65 yrs. of age, 2) no signs/ symptoms of immediate allergies at time of history taking.</p> <p>All. Exclusion: patients taking drugs such as topical and systemic steroids or antihistamine medications during the last month following the Allergy Centre of the Clinical Hospital protocol.</p>							
Sundstrom 2010 ⁷⁸	<p>1) Participants took part in Swedish population-based longitudinal study Betula Study which began in 1988. Betula Study currently includes 5 independent samples (S1-S5) recruited by random selection from the population registry. 1st test wave: conducted 1988–1990 with participants from S1, 2nd wave 1993–1995 (S1, S2,</p>	<p>Inclusion (treatment group): responded affirmatively to the question, "Do or did you have any health problems you think are related to amalgam fillings?"</p> <p>Exclusion: missing data on cognitive tests (n=4).</p>	<p>Adults. 4088 vs 346 reported having health problems vs 342 with complete data included</p>	<p>1) NR</p> <p>2) Missing: 3 for education, 2 for employment status, 17 for marital status.</p>	<p>Amalgam - 58.9 years (12.3) [NR] Control- 58.9 years (12.3)</p>	<p>Smoking status, %. Current smoker: Amalgam -44.4 vs Control- 44.4. Sick-listed, %: Amalgam: 7.9 vs Control: 4.1</p>	<p>1) Amalgam group: amalgam fillings vs control: NR</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p>Betula project 5 waves 1998-2005. [Cross-sectional analysis (n=342): NA.]</p> <p>[Longitudinal analysis: (n=81 participants with amalgam-related complaints and matched controls with data available approx. 5 years before onset of</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Amalgam group (n=342) Women : 65.8%; Control (n=342) Women: 65.8%, No significant difference.</p> <p>Occupation. Amalgam Group (n = 342) vs. Control (n = 342). p-value Employment status^{aa} (see missing values column) Employed, %: 44.4 vs 50.9, NS Unemployed, %: 3.2 vs 1.3, NS Studying, %: 2.7 vs 2.6, NS Early retirement, %:</p>

	and S3), 3 ^d 1998–2000 (S1, S2, S3, and S4), and 4th 2003–2005 (S1, S3, and S5). Participants in present study from all samples: (S1, N = 104; S2, N = 91; S3, N = 90; S4, N = 29; and S5, N = 28), and all test waves (T1, N = 56; T2, N = 171; T3, N = 75; and T4, N = 40). 2) NR							complaints]	13.0 vs 5.3, p < 0.05 Retired due to advanced age, % 36.6 vs. 36.0, NS Sick-listed, %: 7.9 vs. 4.1, p < 0.05. Education. Mean (SD) (see missing values column) Amalgam: 10.3 (3.8) vs. Control: 10.2 (3.7), p value - N
Sundstrom 2011 ⁷⁹	1) See Sundstrom 2010. 2) See Sundstrom 2010.	Treatment group. <u>Inclusion:</u> See Sundstrom 2010. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) severe visual or auditory handicaps, 2) mental retardation, 3) dementia diseases 4) first language not Swedish. 5) Missing data on life events (n=9) Control group. <u>Inclusion:</u> matched one-by-one for age, gender, education, test sample and test wave selected from the same population and included in the cross-sectional sample	Adults. 4088 vs 346 reported having amalgam-related complaints vs 337 amalgam related health complaints with complete data participated + 337 control (no complaints)	1)NR 2)Missing data:3 for education, 2 for employment status, 17 for marital status. A total of 346	Amalgam: 58.8 years (12.2) [NR]; Control 58.8 years (12.2) [NR]	Amalgam related complaints vs Control. <u>Smoking status, %-</u> Current smoker: 44.5 vs 43.3; <u>Psychiatric disorders, %:</u> 13.4 vs 5.6 <u>Sick listed, %:</u> 8.0 vs 4.1	1) Amalgam group: amalgam fillings vs control: NR 2)NR	Betula project 5 waves 1998-2005. [Cross-sectional analysis: 337 amalgam health complaints + 337 controls: NA] [Longitudinal analysis: 81 participants with amalgam-related complaints	Gender/sex. Women. Amalgam: 65.6% vs control: 65.6 %, NS Occupation. Amalgam group (N = 337) vs Controls (N = 337). P value- Employment status ^{aa} (see missing values column)- Employed, %: 44.8 vs 51.3 NS Unemployed, %: 3.3 vs 1.2 NS Studying, %: 3.6 vs 3.0 NS;

								matched controls, data available approx. 5 years before onset of complaints]	Early retirement, %: 13.4 vs 5.0 <0.05 Sick listed, %: 8.0 vs 4.1 Education (see missing values column). Mean (SD): Amalgam 10.4 (3.8) vs. Control: 10.3 (3.7), NS
Suter 2016 ⁸⁰	1)Retrospective review of records: database that consecutively recorded all patients subjected to patch testing in Department of Oral Medicine, at King's College Hospital Dental Institute between November 2007 and June 2014. 2) See recruitment method.	Inclusion: Patients recorded in database: 1) had a skin patch test because of presence of OLR that was noted to have an association with any dental restoration(s) 2) or cases with atypical OLR (e.g. erythematous lesion or lichen planus-like aspect limited to local area without direct contact to restoration and without signs of OLP elsewhere) , 3) or an OLP resistant to treatment 4) typical features such as reticular striae, white plaque and/or an erosive mucosal patch clearly described in the files along with provisional diagnosis of OLR, atypical OLR or as OLP resistant to treatment made by	Adults. 173 patients skin patch tested between June 2005- June 2014 vs 115 eligible entered to clinical audit vs 87 patients followed up.	1)NA 2)NR	54 years (NR) [23 -86]	Patients with OLR. Patch test positive (dental materials), N (%): 78 (67.8%), Patch test positive (non-dental contactants): 13 (11.3), Patch test negative n=24 (20.9). Current smoker, n (%) - Yes, n (%): 16 (13.9%); No: 99 (86.1%). Clinical presentation. Mixed red + white patches: n = 69, 60%. Only keratotic (white) (reticular or plaque-like) patches n = 40, 34.8%; Only red/erosive patches: n = 6, 5.2% Desquamative gingivitis: 0	1)Patients with amalgam fillings: (n=29, 29.6%) 2)NR	Clinical audit of files 2005-2014 [From the time of diagnosis of OLR 87 patients (75.7%) had been followed up in oral medicine unit 3-174 months, with a mean 31.4 months. [Follow-up following patch testing: 3 to 71 months.]	Gender/sex, n (%). Female: 84 (73%); Male: 31 (27.0%). Race/ethnicity. Total vs patch test positive (dental materials) vs patch test positive (non-dental contactants) vs patch test negative, n(%): White: 63 (72.4) vs 45 (75.0) vs 8 (80.0) vs 10 (58.8) Asian: 7 (8.0) vs 4 (6.7) vs 1 (10.0) vs 2 (11.8) Chinese: 3 (3.4) vs 2 (3.3) vs 0 (0) vs 1 (5.9) Middle East: 4 (4.6) vs 4 (6.7) vs 0 (0) vs 0 (0) Black: 7 (8.0) vs 4 (6.7) vs 1 (10.0) vs 2 (11.8) Other: 3 (3.4) vs 1 (1.7) vs 0 (0) vs 2 (11.8)

		<p>an oral medicine specialist.</p> <p><u>Exclusion:</u> patients having had skin patch test undertaken for other reasons (denture-related stomatitis or intolerance, stomatodynia, lip swelling, perioral dermatitis, non-specific gingivitis)</p>				<p><u>Sites affected.</u> Single (1/2) mucosal sites affected: n=70 (60.9%). 3 ≤ sites with mucosal Reactions: n= 45 (39.1%). The different locations of the oral cavity affected by OLR presented in Table 2 in paper.</p>			<p>Unknown: 28 vs 18 vs 3 vs 7^{bb}</p>
Tadin 2014 ⁸¹	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2) Department of Endodontic and Restorative Dentistry, School of Dental Medicine, University of Zagreb.</p>	<p><u>Inclusion:</u> 1 ≤ class V restoration by composite material. Indications for restoration: included non- carious cervical lesions of hard dental tissue. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) consumption of 2 or more alcohol units three or more/wk, 2) oral lesions, 3) history malignant diseases, 4) exposure to materials used in orthodontics or removable/fixed prosthodontics</p>	<p>Adults. NR vs NR vs 30 participated</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>48.1yrs (7.47) [38-59]</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>1)NR</p> <p>2)See inclusion criteria</p>	<p>NR [180 days post restoration]</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Total- Male: n=18 vs Female: n=12; Per group- Male: n=9 vs female: n=6.</p>
Tseng 2020a [MS] ⁸²	<p>1)LHID2010 includes all original claims data and registration files from 2000 to 2013 for 1 million individuals randomly</p>	<p>MS group. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) disease diagnoses defined according to ICD-9-CM) 2) 2 ≤ consensus diagnoses of MS in order to increase validity of diagnoses. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) cases from the NHI</p>	<p>Adults. LHID2010: 1 million in database vs 1224 vs NA</p>	<p>1)NA</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Total: 50.61 years (16.8) [NR]. MS: 50.61 years (16.46) [NR]. Non-MS: 50.69 years (17.20) [NR]</p>	<p>Total patients with and without MS (n = 1224) vs MS (n = 612) Non-MS (n = 612). <u>CCI score, n (%)</u>:- 0: 267 (21.81%) vs 121 (19.77%) vs 146 (23.86%);</p>	<p>1)MS group. Amalgam: n=366; no amalgam: n=246. Non-MS group. Amalgam: n=391; non-amalgam: n=221.</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Data and registration files: 2000-2013 [NA]</p>	<p>Total (n = 1224) vs. MS (n = 612) vs. Non-MS (n = 612). Gender/sex, n (%). p-Value: 0.279 Female: 804 (65.69%) vs 393</p>

	<p>sampled from the Registry for Beneficiaries NHI program in 2010.</p> <p>2)NA</p>	<p>program with missing data 2) individuals ≤18 years old 3) Patients diagnosed with MS (ICD-9-CM 340) before a history of AMF.</p> <p>Comparison group. Inclusion: subjects from the general population matched by gender, age, urbanization level, socioeconomic status and CCI using propensity score method at a 1:1 ratio.</p>				<p>1: 287 (23.45%) vs 140 (22.88%) vs 147 (24.02%); 2: 204 (16.67%) vs 109 (17.81%) vs 95 (15.52%); ≥3: 466 (38.07%) vs 242 (39.54%) vs 224 (36.60%).</p>		<p>(64.22%) vs 411 (67.16%) Male: 420 (34.31%) vs 219 (35.78%) vs 201 (32.84%).</p> <p>Place of residence, n (%) Urbanization p-Value=0.866 Urban: 764 (62.42%) vs 389 (63.56%) vs 375 (61.27%) Suburban: 334 (27.29%) vs 151 (24.67%) vs 183 (29.90%) Rural: 126 (10.29%) vs 72 (11.76%) vs 54 (8.82%).</p> <p>SES. Monthly income: p-vaue: 0.579 <NT\$ 20,000: 954 (77.94%) vs 472 (77.12%) vs 482 (78.76%) NT\$ 20,000–40,000: 166 (13.56%) vs 87 (14.22%) vs 79 (12.91%) >NT\$ 40,000: 104 (8.50%) vs 53 (8.66%) vs 51 (8.33%).</p>	
<p>Tseng 2020B [ET]⁸³</p>	<p>1) See Tseng 2020a</p> <p>2)See Tseng 2020a</p>	<p>Inclusion: 3 ≤ consensus diagnoses of ET.</p> <p>Exclusion: 1) subject ≤ 20 yrs old 2)</p>	<p>Adults. LHID2010: 1 million in database vs 6016 vs NA</p>	<p>1)NA</p> <p>2)NR</p>	<p>Total: 65.4 years (17.5) [NR]; ET: 65.2 years (17.7) [NR]; Non-ET:</p>	<p>Total patients with and without ET (N = 6016) vs ET (n = 3008) vs Non-ET (n = 3008), n (%).</p>	<p>1)Amalgam fillings, n population (%). Total pop. (n=6061): 247 (4.11%) vs ET (n=3008): 132</p>	<p>Data and registration files: 2000-2013 [NA]</p>	<p>Total vs ET vs non-ET. Gender/sex, n (%). p-value: 0.665</p>

		individuals who withdrew from NHI program 3) individuals with missing data in LHID2010 4) patients with history of Parkinson's disease (ICD-9-CM 332), 5) patients diagnosed with ET (ICD-9-CM 333.1) before a history of AMF.			65.6 years (17.4) [NR].	CCI score- 0: 798 (13.26%) vs 325 (10.80%) vs 473 (15.72%); 1: 1023 (17.00%) vs 519 (17.25%) vs 504 (16.76%); 2: 1003 (16.67%) vs 526 (17.49%) vs 477 (15.86%); ≥3: 3192 (53.06%) vs 1638 (54.45%) vs 1554 (51.66%)	(4.39%); vs non-ET (n=3008): 115 (3.82%). 2)NR		Female: 3373 (56.07%) vs 1671 (55.55%) vs 1702 (56.58%). Male: 2643 (43.93%) vs 1337 (44.45%) vs 1306 (43.42%). Place of residence. Urbanization- p-value=0.724. Urban: 3801 (63.18%) vs 1902 (63.23%) vs 1899 (63.13%) Suburban Total: 1668 (27.73%) vs 840 (27.93%) vs 828 (27.53%) Rural. 547 (9.09%) vs 266 (8.84%) vs. 281 (9.34). SES. Monthly income. p-value: 0.849. <NT\$ 20,000: 4691 (77.99%) vs 2349 (78.13%) vs. 2342 (77.86%); NT\$ 20,000–40,000: 839 (13.95%) vs 417 (13.86%), vs 422 (14.03%). NT\$ 40,000: 486 (8.08%) vs 242 (8.05%) vs 244 (8.12%).
Weber 2012 ⁸⁴	1) SCC arm - recruited from the dermatology	SCC arm. Inclusion: 1) 18 ≤ yrs. old 2) history of biopsy-proven oral SCC.	Adults. NR vs NR vs 113.	1)NR 2)NR	SCC (n=64) - 63 years (12) [NR]; Control (n=48): 67	Oral SCC (n=65) vs Control Patients (n=48). Smoking status-	1)Metal restorations 2)NR	Recruitment: 2000-2008 [Initially 14	Gender/sex. SCC group vs control patients. Males: 34 (52%)

	<p>and otorhinolaryngology departments of Mayo Clinic in Phoenix, Arizona, and Rochester, Minnesota. From June 1, 2000- October 1, 2000. Contact letters sent to all patients who had been seen in the previous 2 years if they had history of oral SCC. Offered opportunity to undergo Mayo Clinic metal patch test series at no charge.</p> <p>Control arm - same time period (summer 2003-fall 2008) by soliciting volunteers via an insert accompanying patient appointment cards sent by mail and via handouts when patients presented for physician appointments in the</p>	<p>Control arm. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) 18 ≤ yrs. old 2) no history of any oral disease.</p> <p>All patients agreed to be available for the duration of patch testing (initially 14 days, which was decreased to 5 days 1 year into the study to facilitate enrolment)</p> <p>Both groups. <u>Exclusion:</u> 1) pregnancy 2) use of any form of immunosuppressive medication.</p>			<p>years (12) [NR].</p>	<p>Current smoker, n (%): 10 (15%) vs 2 (4%), p= 0.07 Past smoker, n (%): 21 (32%) vs 15 (31%), p= 0.91 Smoking history (pack-years) (mean (SD)): ; 35 (28) vs 25 (17), p= 0.18 Current use of chewing tobacco: 0 (0%) vs 0 (0%) Previous use of chewing tobacco: 3 (5%) vs 0 (0%) 0.26 Years of chewing tobacco use (mean (SD)): 29 (21) vs 0 (0) <u>Drinking behaviour-</u> Current drinker, n (5): 32 (49%) vs 25 (52%), p= 0.76 Past drinker, n (5): 15 (23%) vs 4 (8%), p= 0.04 Sustained ethanol use (>6 servings per week for >39 years): 14 (22%) vs 9 (19%), p= 0.72 Degree of ethanol use (servings/day × number of years; mean (SD)): 65 (80) vs 38 (43), p= 0.11 <u>Risk:</u>- p= 0.50. Low: 25 (38%) vs 23 (48%); Medium 16 (25%)</p>		<p>days then reduced to 5 days 1 year into the study]</p>	<p>vs 14 (29%), p=0,01.</p> <p>Race/ethnicity. SCC vs Control: White: 42 (95%) vs 45 (94%).</p>
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	<p>dermatology department or the otorhinolaryngology department at the Arizona site.</p> <p>2) Dermatology and otorhinolaryngology departments of Mayo Clinic in Phoenix, Arizona, and Rochester, Minnesota.</p>					<p>vs 12 (25%); High: 24 (37%) vs 13 (27%) <u>Ever had eczema or dermatitis:</u> 12 (18%) vs 11 (23%), p= 0.56 <u>Wore gold jewellery:</u> 62 (95%) vs 44 (94%), p= 0.69 <u>Wore gold jewellery in piercings:</u> 25 (38%) vs 27 (57%), p= 0.047 <u>Had rash from gold jewellery:</u> 6 (9%) vs 6 (13%), p=0.58 <u>Atopy:</u> 29 (45%) vs 24 (50%), p= 0.57 <u>Wore nickel-containing jewellery:</u> 41 (64%) vs 36 (77%),p= 0.16 <u>Wore nickel-containing jewellery in piercings:</u> 19 (30%) vs 26 (55%), p= 0.007 <u>Had rash from nickel-containing jewellery:</u> 9 (15%) vs 13 (27%), p=0.11</p>			
Wright 2012 ⁸⁵	<p>1)Children with autism: A local ASDs Forum is a multidisciplinary group that assesses and</p>	<p>ASD Group. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) children with ASD diagnosed according to the RDC from the WHO International Classification of</p>	<p>Children. NR vs NR vs 251</p>	<p>1)NR 2) ASD (n=54) vs Special School (n=34) vs Mainstream School (n=121)</p>	<p>ASD vs Special School vs Mainstream School vs Sibling.</p>	<p>NR</p>	<p>1)ASD vs Special School vs Mainstream School vs Sibling. <u>N of amalgam dental fillings, n (%)</u>-</p>	<p>NR [NA]</p>	<p>Gender/sex, n (%). ASD vs Special School vs Mainstream School vs Sibling. Male: 42/53 (79%) vs 18/34</p>

	<p>diagnoses all local children. All families on their database were sent info. about the research from their clinician and those giving informed consent were recruited into the study.</p> <p>Controls: healthy children without autism (or any previous assessments for ASD) from both special schools and mainstream schools were recruited in cohorts from schools supportive of the research</p> <p>2) School, home, clinic.</p>	<p>Diseases system version 10 and established across home, school and clinic; 2) siblings of children with ASD;</p> <p>Controls. Inclusion: 1) healthy children without autism; 2) special school children (A special school mainly educates children with learning disabilities in the first percentile range)</p> <p>Exclusion: any known metabolic or neurological disorder. Children excluded from control group if had received an assessment for an ASD or concerns raised by the teacher that the child might be on the autism spectrum.</p>		<p>vs Sibling (n=42). Returned urines from consented children 47 (87%) vs 28 (82%) vs 115 (95%) vs 40 (95%)</p>	<p>9.6 yrs. (3.6) [NR] vs 12.6 yrs (3.5) [NR] vs 8.8 (2.4) [NR] vs 12.1 yrs (3.6) [NR]</p>		<p>No fillings: 36 (88%) vs 22 (79%) vs 72 (74%) vs 24 (83%).</p> <p>1 or more: 5 (12%) vs 6 (21%) vs 26 (26%) vs 5 (17%);</p> <p>N of amalgam dental fillings, m (SD)- 0.4 (1.3) vs 0.5 (1.3) vs 0.7 (1.4) vs 0.3 (0.8).</p> <p>2)NR</p>		<p>(53%) vs 65/119 (55%) vs 17/42 (41%).</p>
Zwicker 2014 ⁸⁶	<p>1) Our data set provides info. on participants in the Pure North S'Energy Foundation program (henceforth "Pure North"), a philanthropic</p>	<p>Treatment group. Inclusion: 1) individuals who had amalgam fillings completely removed, 2) have a post-removal mercury measure at least six months after removal.</p>	NR vs NR vs 955	<p>1) NA</p> <p>2) NR</p>	<p>Treatment group: 53.7 years (9.5) [NR]; Positive amalgam group: 54.3 years (9.0) [NR]; Never Amalgam group: 46.7 years (14.3) [NR].</p>	<p>Treatment group (n=250) vs positive amalgam group (n=167) vs never amalgams (n=538). Urine Hg ((µg/g-creatinine), mean (SD) [n of observations]- Baseline Hg</p>	<p>1) N. of amalgam surfaces at baseline- Treatment group (n=250): 18.4 (12.9); positive amalgam group (n=167): 23.7 (13.8) ; never amalgam (n=538): 0</p>	<p>Individual in Pure North programme between Sept. 2010 and Aug. 2013</p> <p>[Urine Hg levels: in the treatment</p>	<p>Gender/sex. Treatment group (N=250) vs Positive Amalgam group (N=167) vs Never Amalgam group (N=538). Female: 57% vs 60% vs 33%.</p>

	<p>wellness and chronic-disease prevention program based in Calgary, Alberta, Canada. Participants from general public self-selected into program. Sample includes individuals in Pure North program between September 2010-August 2013. Participants enrolled after January 2013 with income over \$25000 required to pay a fee for program ranging from \$600-3000 depending on income. This involved 6 people in the urine Hg measure group and 5 people in the self-reported symptom group.</p>	<p>Positive amalgam group. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) a positive n. of amalgam surfaces throughout the study period. 2) have a second urine Hg measure at 6 ≤ months after their first measure <u>Exclusion:</u> Individuals with differences in n, of amalgams surfaces > 5.</p> <p>Never amalgam group. <u>Inclusion:</u> 1) sample of Pure North participants who have never had amalgam fillings. 2)baseline Hg level measures</p>			<p>overall: 1.61 (1.27) vs 1.67 (1.64) vs 0.78 (1.43); Baseline Hg males only: 1.18 (0.97) [107] vs 1.42 (1.72) [67] vs 0.54 (0.77) [358]; Baseline Hg Females Only: 1.92 (1.37) [143] vs 1.85 (1.56) [100] vs 1.24 (2.14) [180]; % above HBM-1 (proportion): 3.2% (8/250) vs 3.0% (5/167) vs 0.9% (5/538). <u>Self-reported symptoms-</u> Headache: 3.86 (2.40) vs 3.83 (2.38); Memory loss: 4.56 (2.41) vs 4.69 (2.73); Depression: 3.82 (2.50) vs 3.99 (2.37); Fatigue: 5.91 (2.78) vs 5.76 (2.72). Anxiety: 4.36 (2.44) vs 4.35 (2.32). Moody: 3.78 (2.35) vs 3.66 (2.20). Confusion: 2.88 (2.28) vs 2.79 (2.22); Stomach problems: 4.23 (3.10) vs 3.71(2.91). Loss of sense of smell and taste:</p>	<p>2)NR</p>	<p>and positive dental amalgam groups at baseline and after at least 6 months post amalgam removal, or after starting the Pure North program; Changes in 14 self-reported symptoms: in treatment and positive amalgam groups after at least one year.]</p>	
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	2)Dental setting as part of a personalized wellness and chronic-disease prevention program.					2.08 (1.95) vs 2.03 (2.16); Hand shakiness: 2.41 (2.20) vs 2.44 (2.34); Parastehsia: 2.36 (2.35) vs 2.51 (2.43); Dropping things: 2.45 (2.23) vs 2.33 (2.18); Coordination problems: 2.27 (1.88) vs 2.22 (2.01). Muscle weakness: 3.23 (2.51) vs 3.16 (2.45)			
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Abbreviations: AA: arachidonic acid; ADA: American dental association; ADD: attention deficit disorder; ADHD: attention deficit hyperactivity disorder; ALS: amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; AMF: amalgam fillings; ASD: autism spectrum disorder; ATEC: Autism severity questionnaire; ATP: Supplementary Pension Fund Register; BASC-SR: Behaviour Assessment System for Children; BD: bipolar disorder; BIS-GMA: 2,2-bis-[4-(2-hydroxy-3-methacrylo-xypropoxy)phenyl]-propane; BMI: Body Mass Index; BOP: bleeding on probing; CAD: coronary artery disease; CBCL: Child Behaviour Checklist; CCI: Charlson's Comorbidity Index; CEJ: cemento-enamel junction; CKD: chronic kidney disease; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; CRR: composite resin restoration; CRS: Civil Registration System; CTG: connective tissue graft; C-TONI: Comprehensive Test of Nonverbal Intelligence; CTS: carpal tunnel syndrome; CVD: cardiovascular disease; DA: dental assistants; DHA: docosahexaenoic acid; DM: Diabetes Mellitus; DMSA: Dimercaptosuccinic acid; DSM-IV: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fourth Edition; DT: dental technicians; ET: essential tremor; FPD: fixed partial dentures; FPI-R: inventory assessing basic personality traits; GCI: general cognitive index; GH: gestational hypertension; GI: gastrointestinal; GP: general practitioner; GPD: general practice dentist; GST: glutathione-S-transferases; HBM: Human Biomonitoring Commission; HEMA: hydroxy-ethyl methacrylate; Hg: mercury; Hg⁰:mercury vapour; HOME: Home Observation for Measurement of the Environment; h/wk: hours per week; ICD-9-CM: International Classification of Diseases, 9th Revision, Clinical Modification; ID: intellectual disabilities; IQR: interquartile range; IR: incidence rate; ITT: intention to treat; IQ: intelligence quotient; IVDK: Information Network of Departments of Dermatology; K-BIT: Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test; kg/m²: weight (kilograms) per height ² (square metres ²); LCR: Lichenoid contact reactions; LEL: lower exposure limit; LHID: Longitudinal Health Insurance Database; LMM: Labour Market Module; MBRN: Medical Birth Registry of Norway ; MDI: mental development Index; MeHg: methylmercury; mg/mL: milligrams per millilitres; MIT: Massachusetts Institute of Technology; MMA: methyl methacrylate; MoBa: Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study; MS: multiple sclerosis; MUPS: medically unexplained physical symptoms; NA: not applicable; NBC: National Drug Code; NCCL: non-carious cervical lesions; NECAT: New England Children's Amalgam Trial; NHANES: National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey; NHI: National Health Insurance; NHIRD: National Health Insurance Research Database; NHRI: National Health Research Institutes; NHS: neurological hard signs; nmo/L: nanomoles per litre; NOK: Norwegian Krone ; NR: not reported; NS: not significant; NT\$: New Taiwan Dollar; OCD: occupational contact dermatitis; OD: operative dentistry; OLL: oral lichenoid lesions; OLP: oral lichen planus; OLR: oral lichenoid reactions; PBI: Papilla Bleeding Index; PBM: pharmaceutical benefits manager; PD: Parkinson's disease; PDD: pervasive developmental delay; PDI: psychomotor developmental index; PLS: Preschool Language Score; PPD: Probing pocket depths; ppm: parts per million; PROCESS: Paediatric Review of Children's Environmental Support and Stimulation; PRR: Preventive resin restoration; pSS: Primary Sjögren's syndrome; PUFA: polyunsaturated fatty acids; RA: rheumatoid arthritis; RAHP: Register of Authorisation of Health-Care Personnel ; RBC: resin-based composite; RDC: Research Diagnostic Criteria; Rh: Rhesus factor; RMGIC: Resin Modified Glass Ionomer Cement; RTI: Research Triangle Institute; SAM: questionnaire assessing dispositional self-consciousness; SCC: squamous cell carcinoma; SCDNS: Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study; SCDS: Seychelles Child Development Study; SD: standard deviation; SES: socioeconomic status; SHIP: Study of Health in Pomerania; SLE: systemic lupus erythematosus; TBI: Traumatic Brain Injury; THFMA: tetrahydrofurfuryl methacrylate; TPA: third party administrator; UEL: upper exposure limit; US: United States; WASI: Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence; WHO= World Health Organization; W-J: Woodcock-Johnson; wk: week; µg/ dl: microgram per decilitre; µg/L: micrograms per litre; \$CAN: Canadian Dollar; \$US : US dollar.

Footnotes: a: Age-standardised (European standard population) incidence rate per 100 000 person-years. To make the rates comparable we only included women in all occupational groups; b: If a person had worked in a dental clinic and a general practitioner's clinic (n=1198) or a lawyer's office (n=492) or had had all three jobs (n=28), we only included the employment information from the dental clinic; c: no specific characteristics of place of residence are given, d= The registration of education completed outside Norway is incomplete; e: discrepancy in reporting these values. Number

reported here are those in Table 1 footnotes in the paper. The following values are reported narratively in the paper: Pregnancies with missing information for maternal education (n = 3497), smoking habits (n = 677), and alcohol consumption during pregnancy (n = 9975); f= Davidson PW, Strain JJ, Myers GJ, Thurston SW, Bonham MP, Shamlaye CF, et al. Neurodevelopmental effects of maternal nutritional status and exposure to methylmercury from eating fish during pregnancy. *Neurotoxicology*. 2008; 29(5):767–775; g: n =333; h: Children’s Amalgam Trial Study Group. The Children’s Amalgam Trial: design and methods. *Control Clin Trials*. 2003;24:795-814; i= The number of trial participants includes those who later withdrew (85 of 534, 42 in the amalgam group and 43 in the composite group); j= Race was self-reported by the parents of the children. The ‘other’ category included individuals who identified themselves as Asian, Pacific Islander, Native American, biracial, or other, which they were asked to specify; k= as previously reported in the NECAT study design (see footnote h), the Boston site is considered urban and the Maine site is rural; l= Socioeconomic status index was calculated by using household income and education level of the primary caregiver and standardized to the US population; m= Self-reported by the mother of the participant during baseline interview; n= Socio-economic status was calculated based on both household income and maternal education levels and standardized to the general U.S. population of New England area households; o= self-reported by parent/guardian; p= sealed with either preventive sealant or preventive resin restoration; q= Data from initial examination and Questionnaire 1 used as baseline values in the study; r= data obtained from Table in Supplementary material; s: not specified whether mean or median); t: significantly different CI compared with ‘noninflammatory oral complaints; u= information about X-ray exposure and dietary habits collected but not reported; v: Discrepancy in mean reporting. Paper narratively reports mean to be 59 but see Table 1 in paper where it is reported as 49; w: Arbuckle TE, Fraser WD, Fisher M, Davis K, Liang CL, Lupien N, Bastien S, Velez MP, von Dadelszen P, Hemmings DG, Wang J. Cohort profile: the maternal-infant research on environmental chemicals research platform. *Paediatric and perinatal epidemiology*. 2013 Jul;27(4):415-25.; x: To see this data stratified by whether women had/didn’t have a replacement within 12 months prior to 1st trimester visit see Table 1; y=Insured classification: First category: conscription, government employee, private school staff and citizenship business. Second category: employee and professional trade unions. Third category: peasant association, fishermen’s association, water conservancy association. Fourth category: low-income household. Fifth category: veteran; z= assuming that these are the OLR patient group although not explicitly stated in paper; aa: Percentages sum to more than 100% because participants could mark more than one employment status category; bb= the group of unknown ethnicity is excluded from percentage calculation and statistical analysis.

Key: *: setting reported as NA when data obtained from databases/medical records rather than collected at a specific setting; †= where possible, sample size reported using the format “N. approached vs n eligible to participate vs n consented to participate”. However, this is not always available from studies so note alternative specific reporting might be used for some studies; ‡= attrition/withdrawal reported as NA when data is obtained retrospectively from records and therefore participants cannot actively withdraw; §=when mean/median NR, alternative age-related information given, **= POGRESS+ characteristics at baseline might include the following: place of residence; race/ethnicity/culture; occupation; gender/sex; religion; education; socioeconomic status; social capital; personal characteristics associated with discrimination; features of relationships.

References

1. Duplinsky Thomas G, Cicchetti Domenic V. The Health Status of Dentists Exposed to Mercury from Silver Amalgam Tooth Restorations. *International Journal Of Statistics In Medical Research*. 2012;1(1):1-15.
2. Franzblau A, d'Arcy H, Ishak MB, et al. Low-level mercury exposure and peripheral nerve function. *Neurotoxicology*. 2012;33(3):299-306.
3. Heratizadeh A, Werfel T, Schubert S, et al. Contact sensitization in dental technicians with occupational contact dermatitis. Data of the Information Network of Departments of Dermatology (IVDK) 2001-2015. *Contact Dermatitis*. 2018;78(4):266-73.
4. Hilt B, Svendsen K, Syversen T, et al. Occurrence of cognitive symptoms in dental assistants with previous occupational exposure to metallic mercury. *Neurotoxicology*. 2009;30(6):1202-6.
5. Hilt B, Svendsen K, Syversen T, et al. Occurrence of cognitive and neurological symptoms in norwegian dentists. *Saf Health Work*. 2011;2(2):176-82.

6. Jones L, Bunnell J, Stillman J. A 30-year follow-up of residual effects on New Zealand School Dental Nurses, from occupational mercury exposure. *Hum Exp Toxicol*. 2007;26(4):367-74.
7. Thygesen LC, Flachs EM, Hanehoj K, et al. Hospital admissions for neurological and renal diseases among dentists and dental assistants occupationally exposed to mercury. *Occup Environ Med*. 2011;68(12):895-901.
8. Adams JB, Romdalvik J, Levine KE, Hu LW. Mercury in first-cut baby hair of children with autism versus typically-developing children. *Toxicological & Environmental Chemistry*. 2008;90(4):739-53.
9. Bjorkman L, Lygre GB, Haug K, Skjaerven R. Perinatal death and exposure to dental amalgam fillings during pregnancy in the population-based MoBa cohort. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(12):e0208803.
10. Daniels JL, Rowland AS, Longnecker MP, et al. Maternal dental history, child's birth outcome and early cognitive development. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2007;21(5):448-57.
11. Lindbohm ML, Ylostalo P, Sallmen M, et al. Occupational exposure in dentistry and miscarriage. *Occup Environ Med*. 2007;64(2):127-33.
12. Heggland I, Irgens A, Tollanes M, et al. Pregnancy outcomes among female dental personnel--a registry-based retrospective cohort study. *Scand J Work Environ Health*. 2011;37(6):539-46.
13. Lygre GB, Haug K, Skjaerven R, Bjorkman L. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam and pregnancy outcome. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2016;44(5):442-9.
14. Lygre GB, Aase H, Haug K, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam and risk of symptoms of attention-deficit and hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2018;46(5):472-81.
15. Naimi-Akbar A, Sandborgh Englund G, Ekblom A, et al. Cognitive function among sons of women who worked in dentistry. *Scand J Work Environ Health*. 2012;38(6):546-52.
16. Naimi-Akbar A, Sandborgh-Englund G, Ekblom A, et al. Mortality among sons of female dental personnel--a national cohort study. *J Perinat Med*. 2014;42(5):655-61.
17. Watson GE, Lynch M, Myers GJ, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam: evidence from the Seychelles Child Development Study main cohort. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2011;142(11):1283-94.
18. Watson GE, Evans K, Thurston SW, et al. Prenatal exposure to dental amalgam in the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study: associations with neurodevelopmental outcomes at 9 and 30 months. *Neurotoxicology*. 2012;33(6):1511-7.
19. Watson GE, van Wijngaarden E, Love TM, et al. Neurodevelopmental outcomes at 5 years in children exposed prenatally to maternal dental amalgam: the Seychelles Child Development Nutrition Study. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*. 2013;39:57-62.
20. DeRouen TA, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Neurobehavioral effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2006;295(15):1784-92.

21. Geier DA, Carmody T, Kern JK, et al. A significant relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and urinary porphyrins: a further assessment of the Casa Pia children's dental amalgam trial. *Biometals*. 2011;24(2):215-24.
22. Geier DA, Carmody T, Kern JK, et al. A significant dose-dependent relationship between mercury exposure from dental amalgams and kidney integrity biomarkers: a further assessment of the Casa Pia children's dental amalgam trial. *Hum Exp Toxicol*. 2013;32(4):434-40.
23. Lauterbach M, Martins IP, Castro-Caldas A, et al. Neurological outcomes in children with and without amalgam-related mercury exposure: seven years of longitudinal observations in a randomized trial. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2008;139(2):138-45.
24. Martin MD, Woods JS, Leroux BG, et al. Longitudinal urinary creatinine excretion values among preadolescents and adolescents. *Transl Res*. 2008;151(1):51-6.
25. Roberts MC, Leroux BG, Sampson J, et al. Dental amalgam and antibiotic- and/or mercury-resistant bacteria. *J Dent Res*. 2008;87(5):475-9.
26. Woods JS, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Biomarkers of kidney integrity in children and adolescents with dental amalgam mercury exposure: findings from the Casa Pia children's amalgam trial. *Environ Res*. 2008;108(3):393-9.
27. Woods JS, Martin MD, Leroux BG, et al. Urinary porphyrin excretion in children with mercury amalgam treatment: findings from the Casa Pia Children's Dental Amalgam Trial. *J Toxicol Environ Health A*. 2009;72(14):891-6.
28. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Barregard L, et al. Neuropsychological and renal effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA*. 2006;295(15):1775-83.
29. Barregard L, Trachtenberg F, McKinlay S. Renal effects of dental amalgam in children: the New England children's amalgam trial. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2008;116(3):394-9.
30. Bellinger DC, Daniel D, Trachtenberg F, et al. Dental amalgam restorations and children's neuropsychological function: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2007;115(3):440-6.
31. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Daniel D, et al. A dose-effect analysis of children's exposure to dental amalgam and neuropsychological function: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2007;138(9):1210-6.
32. Bellinger DC, Trachtenberg F, Zhang A, et al. Dental amalgam and psychosocial status: the New England Children's Amalgam Trial. *J Dent Res*. 2008;87(5):470-4.
33. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Hauser R, et al. Dental composite restorations and neuropsychological development in children: treatment level analysis from a randomized clinical trial. *Neurotoxicology*. 2012;33(5):1291-7.
34. Maserejian NN, Trachtenberg FL, Hauser R, et al. Dental composite restorations and psychosocial function in children. *Pediatrics*. 2012;130(2):e328-38.

35. Maserejian NN, Hauser R, Tavares M, et al. Dental composites and amalgam and physical development in children. *J Dent Res*. 2012;91(11):1019-25.
36. Maserejian NN, Shrader P, Brown OA, et al. Dental sealants and composite restorations and longitudinal changes in immune function markers in children. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2014;24(3):215-25.
37. Maserejian NN, Shrader P, Trachtenberg FL, et al. Dental sealants and flowable composite restorations and psychosocial, neuropsychological, and physical development in children. *Pediatr Dent*. 2014;36(1):68-75.
38. Shenker BJ, Maserejian NN, Zhang A, McKinlay S. Immune function effects of dental amalgam in children: a randomized clinical trial. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2008;139(11):1496-505.
39. Bjorkman L, Musial F, Alraek T, et al. Removal of dental amalgam restorations in patients with health complaints attributed to amalgam: A prospective cohort study. *J Oral Rehabil*. 2020;47(11):1422-34.
40. Bjorkman L, Musial F, Alraek T, et al. Mercury, silver and selenium in serum before and after removal of amalgam restorations: results from a prospective cohort study in Norway. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2023;81(4):298-310.
41. Sinha N, Hamre HJ, Musial F, et al. Health complaints before and at one and five years after removal of dental amalgam restorations - data from a prospective cohort study in Norway. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2024;83:219-29.
42. Sjursen TT, Lygre GB, Dalen K, et al. Changes in health complaints after removal of amalgam fillings. *J Oral Rehabil*. 2011;38(11):835-48.
43. Bjorkman L, Brokstad KA, Moen K, Jonsson R. Minor changes in serum levels of cytokines after removal of amalgam restorations. *Toxicol Lett*. 2012;211(2):120-5.
44. Bjorkman L, Sjursen TT, Dalen K, et al. Long term changes in health complaints after removal of amalgam restorations. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2017;75(3):208-19.
45. Melchart D, Vogt S, Kohler W, et al. Treatment of health complaints attributed to amalgam. *J Dent Res*. 2008;87(4):349-53.
46. Weidenhammer W, Hausteiner C, Zilker T, et al. Does a specific dental amalgam syndrome exist? A comparative study. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2009;67(4):233-9.
47. Weidenhammer W, Bornschein S, Zilker T, et al. Predictors of treatment outcomes after removal of amalgam fillings: associations between subjective symptoms, psychometric variables and mercury levels. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 2010;38(2):180-9.
48. Ahlgren C, Axell T, Moller H, et al. Contact allergies to potential allergens in patients with oral lichen lesions. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2014;18(1):227-37.

49. Cabana-Munoz ME, Parmigiani-Izquierdo JM, Bravo-Gonzalez LA, et al. Increased Zn/Glutathione Levels and Higher Superoxide Dismutase-1 Activity as Biomarkers of Oxidative Stress in Women with Long-Term Dental Amalgam Fillings: Correlation between Mercury/Aluminium Levels (in Hair) and Antioxidant Systems in Plasma. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(6):e0126339.
50. Cabana-Munoz ME, Parmigiani-Izquierdo JM, Camacho Alonso F, Merino JJ. Increased Systemic Malondialdehyde Levels and Decreased Mo/Co, Co/Fe(2+) Ratios in Patients with Long-Term Dental Titanium Implants and Amalgams. *J Clin Med*. 2019;8(1).
51. Chen KH. Association between Parkinson's Disease and Dental Amalgam Filling: A Study of Nationwide Population-Based Case Control in Taiwan. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*. 2020;18(5):7159-65.
52. Chen KH, Yu HC, Chang YC. Analysis of dental amalgam fillings on primary Sjogren's syndrome: A population-based case-control study in Taiwan. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2021;100(47):e28031.
53. Daume L, Kreis C, Bohner L, et al. Clinical characteristics of oral lichen planus and its causal context with dental restorative materials and oral health-related quality of life. *BMC Oral Health*. 2021;21(1):262.
54. Dermata A, Papageorgiou SN, Fragkou S, Kotsanos N. Comparison of resin modified glass ionomer cement and composite resin in class II primary molar restorations: a 2-year parallel randomised clinical trial. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent*. 2018;19(6):393-401.
55. Eyeson J, House I, Yang YH, Warnakulasuriya KA. Relationship between mercury levels in blood and urine and complaints of chronic mercury toxicity from amalgam restorations. *Br Dent J*. 2010;208(4):E7; discussion 162-3.
56. Forkel S, Schubert S, Corvin L, et al. Contact allergies to dental materials in patients. *Br J Dermatol*. 2024;190(6):895-903.
57. Frisk P, Danersund A, Hudecek R, Lindh U. Changed clinical chemistry pattern in blood after removal of dental amalgam and other metal alloys supported by antioxidant therapy. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2007;120(1-3):163-70.
58. Gavic L, Gorseta K, Glavina D, et al. In vivo assessment of genotoxicity in buccal cells of children undergoing tooth restoration. *Cent Eur J Public Health*. 2019;27(4):312-9.
59. Halperin-Sternfeld M, Saminsky M, Machtei EE, Horwitz J. The association between dental proximal restorations and periodontal disease: A retrospective 10-18 years longitudinal study. *Quintessence Int*. 2016;47(3):249-59.
60. Hsu YC, Chang CW, Lee HL, et al. Association between History of Dental Amalgam Fillings and Risk of Parkinson's Disease: A Population-Based Retrospective Cohort Study in Taiwan. *PLoS One*. 2016;11(12):e0166552.
61. Hu CJ, Yu HC, Chang YC. Investigation of the Impact of Dental Care via Composite Resin Restoration among Children with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: A Registry-Based Nested Case-Control Study. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2021;9(7).
62. Lartitegui-Sebastian MJ, Martinez-Revilla B, Saiz-Garcia C, et al. Oral lichenoid lesions associated with amalgam restorations: a prospective pilot study addressing the adult population of the Basque Country. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal*. 2012;17(4):e545-9.
63. Leybovich M, Bissada NF, Teich S, et al. Treatment of noncarious cervical lesions by a subepithelial connective tissue graft versus a composite resin restoration. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent*. 2014;34(5):649-54.

64. Lin PY, Wang J, Chiang YC, et al. Risk of subsequent attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder among children and adolescents with amalgam restorations: A nationwide longitudinal study. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2018;46(1):47-53.
65. Louopou RC, Trottier H, Arbuckle TE, Fraser WD. Dental amalgams and risk of gestational hypertension in the MIREC study. *Pregnancy Hypertens.* 2020;21:84-9.
66. Lygre GB, Sjørusen TT, Svahn J, et al. Characterization of health complaints before and after removal of amalgam fillings--3-year follow-up. *Acta Odontol Scand.* 2013;71(3-4):560-9.
67. Lynch M, Ryan A, Galvin S, et al. Patch testing in oral lichenoid lesions of uncertain etiology. *Dermatitis.* 2015;26(2):89-93.
68. Ma KS, Thota E, Huang JY, et al. Onset of oral lichen planus following dental treatments: A nested case-control study. *Oral Dis.* 2023;29(3):1269-81.
69. Marell L, Tillberg A, Widman L, et al. Regression of oral lichenoid lesions after replacement of dental restorations. *J Oral Rehabil.* 2014;41(5):381-91.
70. Mikhailichenko N, Yagami K, Chiou JY, et al. Exposure to Dental Filling Materials and the Risk of Dementia: A Population-Based Nested Case Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2019;16(18).
71. Montebugnoli L, Venturi M, Gissi DB, Cervellati F. Clinical and histologic healing of lichenoid oral lesions following amalgam removal: a prospective study. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol.* 2012;113(6):766-72.
72. Naimi-Akbar A, Svedberg P, Alexanderson K, et al. Health-related quality of life and symptoms in patients with experiences of health problems related to dental restorative materials. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2013;41(2):163-72.
73. Perng WT, Ma KS, Hung HY, et al. Dental caries and risk of newly-onset systemic lupus erythematosus: a nationwide population-based cohort study. *Curr Med Res Opin.* 2023;39(2):307-17.
74. Pettini F, Savino M, Corsalini M, et al. Cytogenetic genotoxic investigation in peripheral blood lymphocytes of subjects with dental composite restorative filling materials. *J Biol Regul Homeost Agents.* 2015;29(1):229-33.
75. Pezelj-Ribaric S, Prpic J, Miletic I, et al. Association between oral lichenoid reactions and amalgam restorations. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2008;22(10):1163-7.
76. Ptak DM, Solanki A, Andler L, et al. The Pulpal Response to Crown Preparation and Cementation. *J Endod.* 2023;49(5):462-8.
77. Rojas-Alcayaga G, Carrasco-Labra A, Danus P, et al. Determination of susceptibility to sensitization to dental materials in atopic and non-atopic patients. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal.* 2012;17(2):e320-4.
78. Sundstrom A, Bergdahl J, Nyberg L, et al. Cognitive status in persons with amalgam-related complaints. *J Dent Res.* 2010;89(11):1236-40.
79. Sundstrom A, Bergdahl J, Nyberg L, et al. Stressful negative life events and amalgam-related complaints. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol.* 2011;39(1):12-8.

80. Suter VG, Warnakulasuriya S. The role of patch testing in the management of oral lichenoid reactions. *J Oral Pathol Med.* 2016;45(1):48-57.
81. Tadin A, Galic N, Mladinic M, et al. Genotoxicity in gingival cells of patients undergoing tooth restoration with two different dental composite materials. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2014;18(1):87-96.
82. Tseng CF, Chen KH, Yu HC, et al. Dental Amalgam Fillings and Multiple Sclerosis: A Nationwide Population-Based Case-Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(8).
83. Tseng CF, Chen KH, Yu HC, Chang YC. Association between Dental Amalgam Filling and Essential Tremor: A Nationwide Population-Based Case Control Study in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2020;17(3).
84. Weber ME, Yiannias JA, Hougeir FG, et al. Intraoral metal contact allergy as a possible risk factor for oral squamous cell carcinoma. *Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol.* 2012;121(6):389-94.
85. Wright B, Pearce H, Allgar V, et al. A comparison of urinary mercury between children with autism spectrum disorders and control children. *PLoS One.* 2012;7(2):e29547.
86. Zwicker JD, Dutton DJ, Emery JC. Longitudinal analysis of the association between removal of dental amalgam, urine mercury and 14 self-reported health symptoms. *Environ Health.* 2014;13:95.